

The activated post-industrial waterways as the contested heritage livescape: a model of engagement with the Forth and Clyde canal and the river Clyde

Eleni Koumpouzi, BA, BA (Hons), MA, MSc

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Abstract

In contributing to the place-making and wider cultural planning of contemporary urban waterways in former industrial areas, governments and local authorities have welcomed the preservation of historic waterways by re-inventing use for rivers and canals and their heritage assets such as historic ships and boats. (Carter 2016). The post-industrial waterscape, is the landscape where the amalgamation of human and non-human actants (Bennett 2010) and tangible and intangible heritages (Lenzerini 2011) are in a state of constant negotiation (Ingold 2012) and contestation (Smith 2016). The locality of the post-industrial waterways is the transient landscape where agents appear to be embedded within hierarchical approaches to knowledge and ownership of the heritage environment (Berg 2004; Smith 2006). Local communities experience transiency, juxtaposed with the liminality of the historic waterways (as places in-between) in the way they engage with heritage, struggling to establish familiarity with the historic place, agency and a sense of ownership (Keating et al 2012).

This study aimed to plan, design and lead primary research in the post-industrial waterways in and around Glasgow; to analyse a case study and interviews with cultural organisations on the river Clyde and the Forth and Clyde canal; and to create a model of public engagement with heritage. The study examined to what extent local communities who experience transiency (due to disadvantage and perceived marginalisation) engage with the historic waterways in their everyday life, activating them by being on the water, and how this activation informs heritage practices.

The case study engaged local community groups in the Forth and Clyde canal's areas of Maryhill and Kirkintilloch, in and around Glasgow, and the interviews engaged two cultural organisations that use the crafts of boat-building and boating, on the river Clyde, as heritage activation to achieve community cohesion. During the case study, the groups of participants took part in boat-building workshops, which produced three small boats and their oars, boat handling activities, two celebratory events, the production of films, one exhibition, and the participants used the boats they built in three community festivals on the canal and the river.

Ethnographic and auto-ethnographic observations, participatory action investigation and visual methods of data analysis were used, creating a body of evidence and a visual portfolio that support the concept of the activated and contested heritage *livescape*.

The *livescape* revealed that complex and problematic engagement with post-industrial waterways' heritage would demand a thorough understanding of the complexity of the locality's perception of the past as much as the familiarity with the particular landscape.

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Abbreviations

AHD: Authorised Heritage Discourse

CHO: Community Heritage Officer (the researcher's professional role in CanalCraft)

CMT: Clyde Maritime Trust

ED: East Dunbartonshire

EDC: East Dunbartonshire Council

EDHHF: East Dunbartonshire History and Heritage Forum

EDLC: East Dunbartonshire Culture and Leisure Trust

FCC: Forth and Clyde Canal

FCCS: Forth and Clyde Canal Society

GCC: Glasgow Canal Coop

GCC: Glasgow City Council

GCP: Glasgow Canal Project

GM: Glasgow Museums

GRACE: Group Recovery Aftercare Community Enterprise

LGBTI+ YS: Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Intersex Youth Scotland

MGS: Museum Galleries Scotland

MIN: Maryhill Integration Network

NLHT: National Lottery Heritage Trust

SC: Scottish Canals

SRC: Scottish Refugee Council

ST: Seagull Trust

WC: Women's Centre

Chapter I Introduction

1. Situating the Study

This study is situated on one hand within the field of critical heritage studies (Winter, 2013:533) and specifically in the discourses on contemporary urban heritage practices and process (Harrison, 2013:165) in today's diverse and multicultural communities (Smith, 2016). On the other hand, it sits within the field of urban geography and speaks to discourses on more-than-representational space (Lorimer, 2005) and the role of place-making strategies towards a sense of belonging through engagement in the city. The study examines in detail participation and engagement with urban and inland heritage waterways by transient and marginalised communities.

My background is in the visual arts and I have been curating art projects with a community focus for over twenty years, in Britain and other countries. Therefore, creativity and practice are ontologically part of the study, and they are approached as the way of understanding environments. Practice has been fundamental to me in my previous work as a visual artist and curator. I have worked in the UK and internationally for over twenty years curating conceptual art exhibitions, particularly outside the conventional art gallery space and in disused urban spaces, exploring city dwelling and personal space. My career as an artist was based on a series of engaging projects within urban environments that local communities had occupied during the ongoing regeneration processes. Through my artwork, I engaged disadvantaged and marginalised from decision making processes, community groups, in re-imagining their locality by co-producing events and actions, outside the designed and authoritative processes of local authorities and power institutions. The body of work created through those projects have been kept in my own archive which includes films, photographs and drawings.

I also have a background as a heritage professional who has worked in museums such as the Auld Kirk Museum in Kirkintilloch, where I volunteered digitising the collection and researching exhibitions, and The Tall Ship in Glasgow, where I worked as the Interpretation and Museum officer, looking after the collection and developing exhibitions and tools for engagement with the ship.

As a PhD researcher, I am also a boater and a paddler, who uses the urban and inland waterways regularly. I have been a member of local kayak clubs for over ten years, practicing my skills in the Forth and Clyde canal (FCC). I have volunteered since 2017 with the Forth and Clyde Canal Society (FCCS), being trained in navigating their canal boats and being a crew member in the cruises they organise on the canal, with local community groups.

Through this previous experience, I come to this research with the belief that heritage is practice and it is processual, and it is situated in the everyday life of its environments, the locality, and it is not a separate entity.

As I began this study with the ontological assumption that heritage is a reality in the everyday realm, I also presume it affects and is affected by the human and the non-human elements in its environment. Thus, objects, the fauna and the flora of the heritage landscape possess the ability to affect the heritage process. I frame this as the *locality*, the amalgamation of the communities and non-human elements that comprise the heritage landscape.

Furthermore, the heritage locality is experienced as interactions between the tangible and intangible elements in the changing historic environment. The historic waterways in and around Glasgow, and specifically the Forth and Clyde canal and the river Clyde where I focused my study are integrated into the everyday and they are constantly changing due to the impacts of place-making processes (McCann, 2002). These processes affect the tangible elements of the historic environment, through the developments such as the Riverside Museum and the Southbank marina in Kirkintilloch, and the intangible elements through, for example, new ways of interacting with river and canal waterfronts. The local communities who experience the historic environment may also be affected by mobility (migration), dislocation and lack of access to decision-making. This combination of factors suggests that these communities are transient. Transiency, therefore, in the locality is defined by changes in communities' familiarity and adjustment to the historic environment and its heritage, which affects sense of belonging.

During my work at the Tall Ship in Glasgow and my volunteering work with the Forth and Clyde Canal Society before this research I observed that familiarity and agency in the social and public space of the historic waterways becomes problematized when gaps in engagement with the local heritage environment present tensions, occurring between the authorised heritage discourse (AHD) (Smith, 20016) and direct participation

with the historic waterways. A good example of this is the regenerated area of Pointhouse, which is the area where the Riverside Museum and The Tall Ship are located today. The place has been developed from the Pointhouse Shipyard, founded in 1862 by A and J Inglis. There is no evidence of the shipyard today, as substantial alteration of the site has taken place, with filling in of the berths to create easier access to the water and river view. The Riverside Museum which has been developed on the site is an iconic and inspirational building, which was materialised with a budget of over £60 million, and became a symbol of Glasgow's renewal through culture strategy (O'Neill and Rogerson, 2018). The Tall Ship is moored in front of the museum and both buildings are free to visit. However, despite the efforts to make the river and the museums accessible to a wider public, during my work at The Tall Ship as a museum officer, I observed that there were sections of the public that didn't visit the area, for example young adults, or visitors didn't connect with the river directly, for example through a boating activity. I observed that engagement took place only through organised activities which were controlled by clubs such as the Sea Cadets and institutions such as the Clyde Maritime Trust (CMT) which controlled the access to the slipway. One needs to be a member of the cadets to have access to the equipment and expertise to access the water, or one needs to fulfil the criteria of competence and knowledge of being on a boat to be allowed to use the slipway. In both ways, although these barriers guarantee safety to the public, on the other hand they present barriers to the wider public to access the river. Visiting an iconic building such as the Riverside Museum also present barriers as the shipbuilding site where shipbuilding occurred has been altered substantially to give space to an architectural monument. These actions, the alteration of the historic environment and the re-assignment of a culturally specific place, have impacted the way local communities engage with the river that runs through their neighbourhoods, with which they used to be familiar because it provided their livelihood.

As a heritage professional working with museums, local authorities and institutions which care for heritage outside the museum sector, I observed that AHD has been responsible for changes in locality and facilitation of place-making processes in cities, and particularly in Glasgow (Vallerani and Visentin, 2018). I understood that this power of the authorised heritage institutions to control the historic environment has created tensions in the heritage localities which are connected to knowledge hierarchies within the heritage environment. There are gaps in understanding and acknowledging who holds the knowledge of the specific environment and consequently who makes the decisions about the ways local communities will engage with their locality,

according to that knowledge. At or near the top of this knowledge hierarchy are heritage professionals and institutions, urban planners, architects and local authorities, and I myself as a researcher coming from an academic point of view found my position right within these tensions.

Experiencing first-hand the place-making strategies as part of urban regeneration and the development of the apparently derelict and disused parts of the post-industrial places (Pierce et al, 2010; DeSilvey, 2017), for example the development of the north bank of the river Clyde with the Riverside museum and the Tall Ship, I chose to focus the study on Glasgow's post-industrial urban and inland waterways, acknowledging that tangible and intangible heritage assets in these landscapes (Vallerani and Visconti, 2018) have been used to facilitate place making (McCann, 2002). At the same time, the developments in the last decades, have disrupted these heritage landscapes by altering them, creating transiency (Clark, 2009; Mooney, 2004), and consequently affecting the community's engagement with them, the sense of belonging and agency (Gray, 2018). At the time, I felt that the localities were changing rapidly, for example with new residential developments springing up at the river's and canal's waterfronts, one on the plot next to the Riverside and also at the new mooring spots at the Claypits on FCC. I wanted to find out how the communities who do not usually participate in their local heritage (the publics that did not visit the museums, or were not part of the boating communities) were perceiving the changes, and what kind of engagement could connect them more with the heritage they were inhabiting in their everyday. An example of that is the Southbank marina in Kirkintilloch. When I first visited the marina in 2008, historically an old canal basin and the site of two boatyards, it had been developed into boat mooring places, with new office blocks that housed the East Dunbartonshire Council's headquarters. The plan was that the new buildings would serve as leisure outlets, with cafes and shops. Soon after the Southbank Marina was built, the financial crisis occurred and none of the original plans materialised. This resulted to the buildings becoming offices, and the boat moorings being used by a very small number of boat residents. The marina is visited during the day by canal towpath walkers and passers-by, however at night it is a fairly deserted place. I used the marina regularly through the FCCS, as their boats are moored there from time to time, specifically during events such as Doors Open Days and the Kirkintilloch festival. During the time I first visited Southbank Marina and until I started this study in 2017, I observed that the public engaged with the marina mainly during the events, however there is very limited access to the boats, and apart from a few privately owned boats, all other activities on the water take place

through organised clubs (kayak, canoe, and the FCCS). Scottish Canals (SC) use the marina for the training of volunteers in canal conservation and maintenance activities. The FCCS run free boat rides during the festival and there are canoe rides organised by local clubs. The rest of the year, the public is not encouraged to engage with the canal nor the marina, unless engagement happens through membership of a club or participation in an organised activity by an authority.

Therefore, I started this research by using as foci for the study the Forth and Clyde canal and the river Clyde, in Glasgow, as post-industrial heritage urban landscapes. In these localities, by examining engagement with local heritage I wanted to identify the transient element of the localities, in terms of place and the communities that occupied them, therefore I focused my study on communities that had less opportunities to engage with heritage: marginalised groups and communities and groups who are considered outside the decision-making process. I called these communities transient, because for the purpose of my study, they were experiencing the changes of their localities but also, they experienced change themselves in their everyday life. Thus, I worked with women's' groups, LGBTI+ youth group, refugee and asylum seekers.

I based my research on the question of the ways in which local, transient communities participated with local heritage and how this participation informed the heritage process. In answering this question, I aimed to examine transient communities' participation and involvement within the post-industrial cultural landscape in Glasgow, focusing on heritage assets, such as the FCC and the river Clyde, and to identify possibilities for the same communities to activate this heritage landscape and aspects of further participation. In order to achieve those aims by using my previous experiences and background as an arts practitioner, a curator and heritage professional, but also a boater and paddler who is used to being on the water, I felt that practice-led research was appropriate. Practice-led type research would allow me to put the practice first, being on the water and in a practice (participation) situation. Turning the focus of the thesis on the practice element was necessary because the activities, participation and observations would result in a set of outcomes, and the body of work that the outcomes generated would be the 'embodiment' of the concepts of the thesis. The thesis would work as the background explanation of the body of work, the theorisation of the concept of the livescape. Therefore my objectives were to plan, design and lead primary research in the heritage waterways in Glasgow, analyse a case study and interviews with cultural organisations in the areas of focus, and create a model of public engagement with the heritage landscape.

In order to achieve the objectives of the research, I needed to identify potential partners and groups available and willing to collaborate. As I was already a member of the FCCS, they agreed in being the leading group on a community heritage project that will improve their access to a wider audience and to re-connect them with the localities of the canal, and particularly with communities that do not usually engage with the waterway. At the same time, I would help the FCCS run the project, by employing my previous work experiences, and at the same time be an observer for the purpose of this research. CanalCraft became the community heritage project on which I based this research, funded by the National Lottery Heritage Fund (NLHF) and that project lasted for one year. CanalCraft developed along with the PhD research, from a Scoping Study (discussed further in Chapter IV), and it became the platform where the activities took place, and I used parts of the CanalCraft project as the case study for the PhD research. I will discuss further parts of CanalCraft as the case study in Chapter IV.

This introductory chapter presents the background of the study and delineates the foundation for the research. It presents the main problem of the research question, aims and objectives of the study. Then, the study's significance for the fields concerned will be presented along with identified limitations. Finally, the chapter will lay out the structure of the thesis in line with the forthcoming chapters.

2. Glasgow and its historic waterways – the heritage landscape

2.1 Glasgow's historic waterways

The tourist economy of cities, such as Glasgow (Clyde Waterfront, n.d.) have directly affected policies of urban renewal, with the cultural and heritage environments of the waterways as income generating assets, whilst cultural economy mentality has had an effect on the way the local authority envisages the place (Hutton, 2016).

Glasgow's status as City of Culture was seen as a positive force and a 'push' for change and economic growth, following a general tendency around Europe and further afield (Evans, 2009) for re-birth and re-invention of cities as new cultural clusters. The commodification of culture and heritage and an acceptable and attractive 'veneer' to the appearance of the city meant that distinctive cultures that prevailed in the city were affected by the development. Paddison and Miles (2020) discuss how the 'characteristic ways of life' of city dwellers were in danger of disappearing. As the cultural city narrative unravels (Florida 2002) and with it a new plan for

tourism and economic growth through heritage and culture, so the city becomes subject to intense regeneration, building development initiatives and, unavoidably, gentrification, most of the time driven by public and private collaborations (Punter, 2009). These scholars have explained how these new forms of synergies have replaced the old scheme, based on water and dependent on industrial production, manufacturing, shipping and goods exchange.

Glasgow became the City of Culture in 1990, which put cultural planning at the forefront of city planning and regeneration (Ghelfi, 2017). Plans for Glasgow to re-invent itself as a cultural city began and maritime heritage organisations played an important and central part in the new cultural narrative that was emerging (Varna 2014).

Glasgow, with substantial historic and heritage capital, especially on its waterways, deriving from the profitable shipbuilding, manufacturing and shipping industry, on a global scale, has retained evidence of the past in the museum and cultural sector, with archives and collections such as the Hunterian and City of Glasgow's own (Collections, Glasgow Life). Glasgow boasts a peripheral industrial history and heritage as well, which flourished parallel to the inner-city industry, and which resulted in the construction of the Forth and Clyde Canal (Hutton, 2002).

The historic waterfront of the river Clyde, which contributed to the development of Glasgow to a global city of industry, commerce and culture in the last three hundred years, has provided the material for the creation of a new approach to the economic development of the city through tourism.

Glasgow also boasts a canal system, and the canal that is still open, the Forth and Clyde Canal, which along with the river Clyde created the post-industrial heritage that regeneration planning employs today. Thus, the river Clyde and the Forth and Clyde canal have a long common history of seafaring, shipbuilding and global trade that extends across three centuries and they equally share heritage assets, which are still visible today, around the river, in the city and in the areas around Glasgow, where former industries thrived. Examples of heritage assets on the river are The Tall Ship (Glenlee), T.S. Queen Mary, Ferry No8, Western boathouse, Fairfield Heritage Centre and GalGael, a charity that utilised boat building to engage the river with local communities in Govan. On the canal, any craft that uses the water helps in preserving its fabric. Charities such as the Forth and Clyde Canal Society, the Seagull Trust and Lambhill Stables all use boats to promote the history of the waterway but also to safeguard the navigability of the canal.

‘Marine heritage projects, in Glasgow, such as the rescue and restoration of the Glenlee, carried the material that was necessary for the city’s new branding (McCafferty et al (eds), 2009). The new trajectory for the economic growth ‘suggested’ that feelings of nostalgia, place-making and the pride of place, history and heritage will be prominent factors. Preservation, restoration and conservation of that heritage will be priority’ (River Clyde Project Group 1989)

2.2 Glasgow’s heritage assets and place-making

Marine heritage organisations in the city of Glasgow, based on their post-industrial past, carried the material that was necessary for Glasgow’s regeneration (O’Neill and Rogerson, 2018). An example is the Clyde Maritime Trust (CMT), which is responsible for the rescue and restoration of the Glenlee, The Tall Ship at the Riverside. The Tall Ship at the Riverside is a museum ship, and it is run by the CMT. The CMT is a charity that rescued the ship by bringing it back to Glasgow and now focuses on restoring and preserving the Glenlee and other historic vessels associated with the history of the river Clyde. Since 2014, The Tall Ship has collaborated with another charity, GalGael, in the Anchor and Sail project. The project gave the opportunity to the Tall Ship to utilise its boat building workshop to engage with a different audience and to attract hard to reach participants through craft and transmission of traditional skills.

Both organisations share volunteers and expertise. Ferry no8, one of the historic Clyde ferries, for example, was originally bought by FCCS after it finished operating in the Clyde. The ferry operated as Ferry Queen on the Forth and Clyde canal for several years before she was bought by the CMT. The boat is now moored at Kelvin Harbour.

GalGael is a charity focusing on transforming people’s lives through the activities of boating, boat building, craft and wood working. The organisation believes that people gain confidence through understanding where they come from and through feeling proud of their achievements, and being on the water in the river Clyde is one of the charity’s main activities.

Lambhill Stables is a charity, helping the local community fight back against the effects of multiple deprivation and try to inject a ‘pride of place’ by encouraging heritage engagement and community activities. The Stables have recently completed a heritage project, Coal, Canal and Cottages, funded by the Heritage Lottery Fund. The project promoted heritage engagement in the local community and encouraged participants to reflect on

how local post-industrial heritage of the canal still influences their life (Lambhill Stables. History and Heritage Group, 2020).

As the post-industrial heritage of the river Clyde has been widely celebrated and it is one of the driving forces of the regeneration of the areas surrounding the river, Glasgow's other arterial waterway, the canal system, has its own development planning, which has regenerated some of the areas around the canal. The canal's renewal strategy developed through the Millenium Link, the planning project which provided the platform for the re-opening and restructuring the Forth and Clyde Canal (Millenium Link:7). Heritage has played an important role in the regeneration of the Forth and Clyde Canal with projects such as the Glasgow Canal Project, which amalgamates the cultural, leisure, business, and environmental sectors under the common aim of canal re-invention as a sustainable heritage asset, aiming at a new use (Glasgow Canal Project, 2018).

The two waterways have been central to the renewal plans for the city of Glasgow. The renewal was manifested through the process of cultural planning and development, which previous studies suggest posed solutions and challenges at the same time (Punter 2011). The concept that prevails in the majority of the analysis of urban regeneration is critical of how event-based, experience-centred (Richards and Palmer, 2010), cultural tourism has taken over planning in many developed cities around the globe. In particular, Glasgow city planners and developers have used the concept of culture in order to regain the status of the global city (Mooney, 2004).

Furthermore, literature suggests that regeneration plans and public-private sector schemes formulated to implement a renewed cultural landscape and planning in the city have not achieved the community inclusion that was expected (Varna 2016).

At the canal, Scottish Canals is responsible for the accessibility on the Forth and Clyde canal for local communities. However, crime incidents at the canal towpaths have also alarmed the local communities in the areas of the canal that feel isolated. The canal is a construction with organic qualities and its constant use is pivotal to its survival. In the recent months, four bridges on the Forth and Clyde Canal failed to operate which resulted in parts of the canal to be closed to navigation, which poses a threat to the survival of the waterway and consequently to negative perceptions by the adjacent communities.

Paxton, in his report on the regeneration of the Forth and Clyde and Union canals, had warned that “[t]he project’s sustainability, however, must be within a socio-environmental framework. The canal in itself must generate sufficient revenue income through charges to boat users, wayleaves and water charges to sustain the navigable waterway to the environmental quality standards of today and of the future. Only then will the ‘enviro-capital investment’ be justified” (Paxton, 2000:11). Nevertheless, local communities who live in proximity to the river and the canal are expected to adjust to a new kind of gentrification via city planning (Gillick and Ivette eds, 2018).

The river is a symbol for change, decline, deprivation and social struggle. These elements of collective conscience and popular perception of the city’s waterfront has sparked discussion on the idea of public space and its meaning and how the current economic system has influenced the resonance of regeneration planning. The Clyde’s waterfront has been seen for the last 28 years as a solid base on which a heritage narrative structure for the river and the city as a whole could be created and fostered for regeneration purposes.

‘On the Clyde’s waterfront, big investment driven by the local authority has developed a cultural environment, with new inspirational buildings such as the Hydro, BBC, Science Centre, Scottish Exhibition Centre (SEC, or the ‘Armadillo’) and the Riverside Museum. Despite the rich heritage collection, Glasgow, unlike Edinburgh, had to create a cultural base which greatly depends on performance and music events’
(Yi-De Liu and Chi-Fan Lin, 2011).

Following the closure of the Forth and Clyde Canal in January 1963, years of neglect and decay left the canal in an appalling state, much to the dismay of many people. The canal became a place not to be near, with parents warning children of danger and press and politicians pushing for it to be filled in. The canal needed some person or persons to revive its historical and picturesque past and to try to bring the canal back into use.

The Scottish Inland Waterways Association was formed in 1971, its aim to promote both conservation and restoration of all Scottish canals and waterways. From this and other groups launching campaigns to relaunch the canals, people began to work to clean up and restore the canal system all over Scotland.

Working parties were formed and clean ups involving people from all walks of life, both young and old participated in clearing rubbish and litter from the canal channels. Boat trips and boat rallies followed, and

efforts made to raise funds to continue the battle to reopen a canal system which had been blocked at many points along its length. Eventually local plans were drawn up with Local Authority involvement and interest seemed to be growing.

In April 1980 the Forth and Clyde Canal Society was formed. The interest by Local authorities prompted some Scottish Inland Waterway Association members to begin to focus locally rather than nationally and the new Forth and Clyde Canal Society grew with support from canal-side local communities. In conjunction with local bodies, they ran boat events and barge trips as well as arranging clean up groups.

The Society worked to raise public awareness by attending and organising meetings and giving talks, whilst all the while lobbying those in authority. Gradually things began to change, with lock gates being repaired or replaced and environmental improvements and towpath repairs. More people began using the canal, both on the water as well as the towpaths, and this encouraged British Waterways, the canals operating authority at that time, to bid for money from the National Lottery Millennium Commission to complete the restoration.

The Forth and Clyde Canal Society played a major role in ascertaining the public support for reopening the canal and obtained thousands of signatures from supporters which were then passed to British Waterways. This list of signatories was then given to the National Lottery Millennium Commission by British Waterways to help support their bid for finance. The bid succeeded and the restoration work continued. The founding aim of the Forth and Clyde Canal Society had been achieved.

The society, which owns three boats, engages with the public in heritage activities (heritage cruises, commemoration flotillas, guided tours on the canal, and dedicated events on the canal's history and represents the FCC in various heritage and historical community organisations and forums).

Members of the FCCS, who are all volunteers, are also engaged in the maintenance of the society's boats.

Members, some of them with a boat master's license and engineering expertise, undertake all the maintenance work for the three boats and prepare them for the MCA inspection. This is a very important part in the organisation's operations as this is essential certification in order to be able to carry more than 12 people on board, in every single journey.

The FCCS is the only organisation that offers regular and scheduled boat trips on the Forth and Clyde Canal in and around Glasgow. The organisation has a stable and dedicated membership; however, its aging demographic has raised concerns for the future of the organisation.

Current members continue to work to promote the Forth and Clyde Canal and to ensure its continued success. The society uses the canal to run boat trips, hold meetings and give talks on the canal and its history. They remain vigilant of the current canal authority, Scottish Canals, to see what they are doing to maintain, protect and promote the canal.

The Society has an archive of past journals that were published since its formation. The journals, Canal News, are an important testimony to the work that was going on during the restoration and the campaign, the millennium Link project and the current situation after twenty years since the opening of the waterway back to navigation.

Heritage has played an important role in the regeneration of the FCC with platforms such as the Glasgow Canal Project, which amalgamates the cultural, leisure, business, and environmental sectors. This operates under the common aim of canal re-invention as a sustainable heritage asset with the aim at achieving new ways of engagement (Glasgow Canal Project, 2018).

Thus, the river Clyde and the Forth and Clyde Canal have been central to the renewal plans for the city of Glasgow. The renewal was manifested through the processes of place-making, cultural planning and development, which posed solutions and challenges at the same time (Hutton, 2002; Paxton et al, 2000; River Clyde Project Group, 1989; Berry et al, 2013; Punter, 2011).

Regeneration plans and public-private sector schemes, formulated to implement a renewed cultural landscape and place-making in the city, have not achieved the community inclusion that was expected. According to Varna (2014:123), "key issues such as the quality of pavements, lighting and street furniture, the presence of green space and the importance of connectivity and visibility of public places by the water's edge" were not implemented. This was at the expense of the communities adjacent to the river Clyde (Gray, 2018).

Local communities who live in proximity to the river and the canal were expected to adjust to a new kind of gentrification through place-making. Glasgow Canal Regeneration Partnership has been in action to help with

strategic investment in the canal to connect again communities with the waterway, with projects such as the Whisky Bond and Pinkstone Watersports to name a few (Gillick and Ivett Eds, 2018).

2.3 Glasgow's communities and participation with the heritage assets of Glasgow's waterways

Engaging communities that are affected by the post-industrial waterways in terms of locality and proximity through the practice of heritage presents challenges and underlines competing attitudes towards urban blue spaces and water flows (Haeffner et al., 2017). The urban renewal trajectory followed by most municipalities in and around Glasgow means that neglected areas, which had high crime rates and unsafe living conditions, have to be changed in order to meet the rising demand for housing, employment and leisure (Lennon, 2016). New buildings began to appear along the Clydeside, such as the SEC in 1997, the Science centre in 2001, and the Riverside Museum in 2011. On the Forth and Clyde canal, the development of the towpath, the Kirkintilloch marina in 2008, the National Theatre building in 2016, repaired locks, and other canal features and assets meant that the new places could host new kinds of communities in the locality.

The alteration of the locality and the attraction of new communities stimulated tensions in the recognition of the meaning of 'local community' (Bauman, 2001), transiency, and sense of belonging in public spaces – publicness (Varna and Tiesdell, 2010). Community focused organisations formed bonds with their localities and were developed as heritage assets along the waterways, promoting their public spaces and belonging through invitations to learn new skills. Thus, examples of these heritage assets on the river are The Tall Ship (Glenlee), T.S. Queen Mary, Ferry No8, Western boathouse, Fairfield Heritage Centre and GalGael (as previously mentioned). On the Forth and Clyde Canal, any craft that uses the water helps in preserving its fabric and keep the canal open to boat use. Charities such as the Forth and Clyde Canal Society, the Seagull Trust, based in Kirkintilloch, and Lambhill Stables, all use boats to promote the history of the waterway but also to safeguard the navigability of the canal.

To discuss the current modes of engagement with the historic waterways in and around Glasgow and the heritage uses (Smith, 2016), I organised a seminar with the help of the Riverside Museum. Speakers from three museums, four community projects, and two boating organisations from the river and the canal spoke about engaging local communities through the projects they had organised. Speakers were from CMT, Riverside Museum, GalGael, Glasgow Coastal Rowing Club, The West Boathouse, Archipelago Folkschool, Auld Kirk

Museum, FCCS, and Lambhill Stables (Appendix II). Speakers emphasized the importance of direct participation with the heritage of the waterways using examples of workshops, activities, gatherings, boat cruises, museum collection sessions their groups and organisations are working on. Problems included lack of accessibility for wider sections of local communities who are particularly disadvantaged and marginalised because they don't have the means to participate. In the seminar, accessibility through opportunities for engagement was discussed, and amongst others, the speaker from GalGael pointed out that as an organisation they realised that as they were interested in people's reality, they had to become real and physically immersed into it, and that is how they started taking people in the river with boats.

'Festivals, as place making tactics, based in historic waterscapes "claim distinction" and to establish "a sense of place"' (Richards and Palmer, 2010). The role of water is prominent. The 'fluvial sense of space' (Vallerani, 2018:2) has significance in place-making, when at the same time, cultural events, encouraged by cultural strategies in cities, aim to provide new meanings for post-industrial spaces (Hutton 2016). Thus, 'cultural festivals bring together, display and re-interpret a cultural legacy' (Barrio et al, 2012: 236), and at the same time reinforce a sense of belonging (Koumpouzi et al, 2022).

2.4 Craft, waterways use and social space

The study was developed in three places in and around the city of Glasgow: Maryhill, Kirkintilloch near the Forth and Clyde Canal, and the area of the Riverside, by the river Clyde. Maryhill and Kirkintilloch are historically significant to the city because they have a rich boat building past (Hutton, 2002) as they are the places where puffer boats were built during the industrial era. The Puffer was a boat instrumental in the development of coastal and remote communities on the West of Scotland. The West of Scotland's boatbuilding tradition has strong associations in the public consciousness. This included Clydeside and significant boatbuilding activities along the canal at Kirkintilloch and Maryhill. However, public consciousness associates boatbuilding heritage in the West of Scotland exclusively with Clydeside and not the canal. Boat building yards in all of these places of the canal are long gone (Hutton, 2002), and their locations have been redeveloped and altered through place-making strategies steered by the local authorities who sought to encourage new engagements with the localities (Gray, 2018).

At the time of the project, I was involved in the committee of a local heritage organisation, the East Dunbartonshire Heritage and History Forum (EDHFF). I had also worked at the Auld Kirk Museum as a volunteer archiving their collection online, and I had experienced first-hand the gaps in understanding of the local historic environment, by observing visitors in the museum. I had observed that local communities had experienced transiency (the changes in the locality's fabric) and at the same time lacked engagement with the canal as a monument to local industry. Locals would use the newly developed towpath but being on the water is restricted, because the canal is still considered as dangerous in public perception (Appendix II, Scoping Study Report). Public use of the canal in Maryhill and Kirkintilloch is free and encouraged by Scottish canals (Scottish Canals, n.d.), but for transient communities who experience deprivation and difficulties accessing services, being on water is costly and presents barriers. Locals would either have to own or hire a boat, go on an FCCS cruise or be part of a club. All those options demand time and carry financial costs. Added to this is the general understanding that had prevailed when the canal was closed to navigation: the canal is a dangerous place, and it is best to be away from the water. People are aware of the canal's history, however for communities that experience transiency, with limited resources and opportunities to access water activities or directly interacting, the canal has limited value as a monument or meaning as a waterway that creates a sense of ownership. At the time I started the research, I felt that further study was needed to understand the ways in which the local communities who had restricted capacity to engage with heritage understand the place, during the ongoing urban regeneration process, and how they engage with it through being on the water, if they had the opportunity.

At the same time, local heritage and cultural organisations such as the FCCS have understanding and knowledge of the heritage of the waterways (Hutton 2002). By cruising the canal, maintaining three boats, generating community events, collecting an archive, delivering talks and by just being there to advocate, be vigilant and offer services for the preservation of the canal as a monument, these volunteer groups manage to campaign and hold direct knowledge about the waterways that professionals and authorised experts do not often acquire. During the research, I observed through meetings that authorised organisations around the canal area, such as heritage organisations and the Scottish Canals, have a symbiotic relationship with the FCCS, and there have been instances that the authorised experts would follow advice or ask the group to act upon issues to do with preservation and navigation. At the same time, however, tensions were detected, as

authorised agencies are the main decision-making bodies, deciding the future role of the waterway, not always aligning with canal boaters' needs, for example the lack of sufficient amount of boathouses along the canal. Furthermore, community groups including the FCCS face barriers in accessing funds to generate projects to sustain ongoing relationships with the local communities, and in their capacity to initiate and maintain community engagement initiatives, and lack of expertise in fundraising, as their focus is on their core activities. On the river Clyde, specifically at the Riverside Museum and the Tall Ship, public engagement with the post-industrial heritage assets takes place through the museum's collections, and through visiting the ship, which is a museum object. There is also a rowing club operating at Kelvin Harbour, adjacent to Riverside, and the redeveloped grounds at the Riverside Museum host organised events throughout the year, such as music festivals and fayres. Through my work at the Tall Ship for four years, I had the capacity to observe and document communities' participation with the Riverside Museum and the Tall Ship. Along with boat-builders from GalGael, I co-designed and organised the first Clydebuilt Festival in 2017. My first-hand knowledge and experience of the heritage field at the Riverside enabled me to observe the way the Tall Ship, as an authorised heritage institution, and GalGael as a community and cultural organization that uses heritage in their activities, both in their way, develop meaning and sense of belonging to the locality and affect participation between communities and the river.

Therefore, my starting point for the research was to reach out to organisations along the river Clyde and the FCC localities and initiate a conversation with them to speculate engagement gaps and understandings between those organisations and the communities they aspire to serve, and their insights on that engagement against practices influenced by the authorised heritage discourse (Smith, 2016). In Appendix II, Scoping Study Report, I present the outcome of that initiative, a Seminar held at the Riverside Museum (Appendix II).

3. Engaging with the changing heritage environment of the waterways

Turning to literature and previous knowledge on public engagement with heritage, I understood that they have examined community participation in heritage and the problematized position of transient communities in decision making in the place-making process (Gray, 2018). Scholars have also examined liminality of the heritage environment (Miller, 2017) and how it is situated between the binaries of natural/cultural (Harrison,

2015) and tangible/intangible (Smith and Akagawa, 2009), and the everyday use of the heritage place and its relationship with the authorised heritage discourse (Smith 2006) and hierarchies of knowledge (Berg, 2004).

On the notion of knowledge of a locality, I was also interested in previous studies which have examined knowledge creation and understandings from a different perspective, through vitality (Bennett, 2010), the ability of the effects of non-human elements in the everyday realm (Ingold 2000), and the non-representational nature of the landscape (Thrift, 2004). Most importantly, I was interested in the writings of the philosopher Lefebvre, and particularly, through the analysis of the triad of the production of space (Lefebvre, 1968, 1991). Lefebvre's *lived space*, as the place generated by the life realm, which is contested and created indefinitely, was particularly relevant to my speculations on the way communities on the river and the canal occupy the space, and how it influences the heritage process.

Engaging directly with the heritage of the waterways generates knowledge and familiarity with the fluvial landscape (Vallerani, 2018) and encourages the use of historic waterways, as social space (Varna, 2014), creating a sense of ownership and the feeling that one could influence the environment one lives in. Lack of opportunities for direct participation in the heritage management and preservation of the local environment generates tensions between agencies and local transient communities, resulting in the alienation of parts of local communities from the decision-making processes (Zang and Gorp in Clark and Wise, 2018). Place making, as a regeneration tool, influenced understandings of the local changing environment (Gray, 2018; Mooney, 2004) and in problematic practices of acquiring consent to new developments (Kennedy, 2017), which affected decision-making processes and agency in the area. Furthermore, heritage institutions, such as heritage organisations and agencies, such as the Scottish Canals, being responsible in preserving large-scale monuments, influence decision making in the place making process by depending predominately on professional expertise (AHD) (Bagnall, 2007; Crooke, 2011; Nieroba, 2018), despite the fact that the river and the canal are parts of the everyday public realm and therefore they are part of the locality, peoples' neighbourhoods (Vallerani and Visconti 2018). Therefore, the ever-changing and liminal place of the heritage landscape (Downey et al, 2016; Keating et al, 2012; Miller, 2017), such as the regenerated areas of the river and the canal, with its tangible and intangible heritage assets (Byrne, 2009; Ahmad, 2006; Smith and Akagawa, 2009), in this case the canal's water and the canal boats, is activated by everyday life (Smith, 2016; Harrison, 2013), by the people who experience the heritage environment as part of their everyday lives (Certeau de,

1988; Bennett, 2005; Thompson, 2013; Bagnall, 2007). Although the literature covers public engagement with heritage in the regenerated urban environment, the way heritage engagement occurs in marginalised communities who experience change in the localities in focus in this study was not fully explored. Therefore, I led the research by having a set of questions in mind that complemented the main research question. How do community groups who experience transiency and appear marginalised and disadvantaged engage with the heritage of the waterways? I ask this question because the term 'local communities' incorporates all kinds of communities. As I explain in the literature review in Chapter II, there are communities who are mobile but they are not affected directly by the effects of marginalisation and deprivation by their mobility; an example of this kind of community is working nomads, whose mobility is elective. Considering the monumentality of the post-industrial urban waterways, to what extent do transient communities perceive that heritage as large-scale monuments? The purpose of that question is to reflect on the fact that the urban waterways cross neighbourhoods and this means that communities do not necessarily perceive the size of the canal or the river but they experience the sections they encounter in their everyday life. The question adds to the main research question because the study focuses on ways the waterways are viewed, which is different to monumentality, which implies a special status, such as memorials or statues. Furthermore, what are the heritage assets (the heritages) in the waterways and how do transient local communities view them? Assets are valuable things in a locality, and heritage assets are usually things with historic value, which relates to considerations about what is important and needs to be looked after. Although I, as a researcher, consider the canal and the river as 'assets', their historical value does not necessarily apply to the way transient communities view them. Thus, this question helps the study to focus on what a heritage asset is for the specific communities. It is valuable for the research also to ask what the possibilities are for participation in the waterways and how those local communities can acquire knowledge of the heritage local environment through participation, in order to affect the heritage process. This question leads the main question directly to the conceptualisation of the activated livescape, as a model of participation, and through that model to the emergence of heritage as processual. It is also directional towards the tension of knowledge as part of the heritage process. And finally, is there already participation in local heritage, perhaps not as it is understood by AHD, and how does this affect the heritage process? This last question relates back to monumentality and reflections on what constitute heritages to local transient communities who live with the canal and the river in their neighbourhoods and they already interact (participate) in their places. Because of these questions, I envisaged the heritage

waterways as relational space (Lefebvre, 1991) - where people form relationships with the local environment through their everyday life, rather than through the process of regeneration.

In this research, I viewed locality holistically, as a place where objects, actions, people and matter reside, and I presumed that when the locality gets activated that affects the understanding of heritage, as a whole and as part of the locality. I then focused on the ways these relationships are formed and found to be affectual.

Therefore, the presumption is that the relationships- interactions- between the different elements in the locality reveal the powers that allow or present barriers to these interactions. Thus, the tensions, as activation reveals, hold and at the same time expose the relationships that form this activation (and the power structures that underpin it), and the common components (human, non-human, tangible and intangible) that constitute the act of participation with the heritage landscape.

In order to achieve these aims I planned, designed and led primary research in two areas on the Forth and Clyde canal. I analysed a case study with local community groups from those areas and conducted interviews with two cultural organisations based along the river Clyde. Through these steps, I examined in depth how heritage participation took place, in an environment where local communities experienced transiency, and (pulled at) the tensions of this participation.

Analysing these tensions, uncovers the *activated and contested livescape*, or a way of understanding the heritage place through contestation (Smith, 2006). Studying interactions as tensions between transient local communities with the heritage of the altered historic urban landscape of the waterways, established a model of engagement, which revealed these tensions that worked in *and* through what Lefebvre (1991) described as *lived space*.

4. Towards an understanding of the engagement with the heritage landscape – the livescape

This study's main contribution to knowledge is its development of the *activated and contested heritage livescape*. The livescape is the method of engagement with the heritage environment to uncover Lefebvre's *lived space* (I expand on the connection with Lefebvre's theory later in Chapter II, Section 2.1).

Examining participation of communities who have been affected by change in their locality with the local heritage environment informs the heritage process and adds to the understanding of interactions between

heritage elements in the everyday realm. These interactions are significant for the formation of meaningful relations between communities and their locality, *the place*. As Jalas (2006:344) states, 'a practice is a specific, historical and socially shared way of understanding the world and engaging with the relevant objects'. This involves a focus on the direct interaction with the landscape by an accumulation of actors, who operate together in an 'intensive environment' (Dewsbury, 2011:148) as part of the everyday interactions and actions, and in doing so affect how heritage becomes. These interactions and *knowledges* (local knowledge) in the heritage environment expose hierarchical attitudes towards agency, for example the anglers at Firhill basin on the FCC have in depth knowledge of the watery environment from the canal's banks. At the same time, the heritage place is viewed by the place-making process as exclusive, and the knowledge for the place which affects decision-making usually deriving from qualified experts (Harrison, 2013). Thus, during regeneration of the FCC, purpose made platforms were created in specific places of the basin where anglers could fish from. Interactions such as these between local knowledge and authorised one affect the understanding of the heritage environment, influencing engagement, knowledge making and consequently sense of belonging; anglers now have limited access to places to fish as they have been encouraged to use the platforms instead of any place they would choose.

Thus, as public space is contested through the way communities occupy it (Lefebvre, 1991), I suggest that the activated livescape could unpack the tensions and create a model of participation for any heritage livescape.

Thus, the study's contribution to knowledge is threefold: first, methodologically, the practice led study created a portfolio with a body of work that reflected the way the activation of the livescape took place, a Portfolio, which is curated and presented online, and it is available for everyone to experience, as it stands alone, regardless if someone has access to the written part of the thesis. It is written in an accessible language so everyone can follow the process of research. The Portfolio shows the livescape activated, as it illustrates the activities (participation), interactions and relationships in the locality, as framed in this study, that present the tensions which underpin engagement with heritage (I present the creation of the online Portfolio further in Chapter III, Section 4.1.3) Secondly, empirically, the case study was based on the employment of traditional crafts as a method of activation of the environment. Dissemination of information and data took place through two celebratory events and an exhibition, which I analyse further in Chapter IV, Section 1.4.3, where the outcomes of the craft activities returned to the local community, in the form of film screenings, and

exhibitions of photographs and objects. Finally, theoretically, the study's contribution to knowledge is through the conceptualisation of the activated and contested heritage livescape. The livescape is the heritage landscape, which is situated in the everyday realm, it is activated through interactions, actions and relationships, by the locality which consists of human and non-human elements, which interact and affect themselves and the environment, and can be thought of as relational space. The interactions in the livescape are shot through with tensions, are the contested reality caused by experiencing the altered heritage landscape, and the struggle for familiarity, knowledge, and ownership. The livescape is a model of uncovering the lived space and the knowledges that shape the local environment that communities experience in their neighborhoods, and where *dominant* knowledge derives from. The livescape is a model of participation, which guides the heritage process towards a familiar and known heritage place, sense of belonging and agency in the locality where communities live.

5. Identified limitations in the study for the livescape

Methodologically, the study is based on the design of the case study, by employing a traditional craft (boat building), which in 2018 was characterised as viable, "but very much reduced and shipbuilding has vanished from some of its historic locations" ([Heritage Crafts](#)- Accessed June 2018). However, I recognise that the study would benefit from a broader and wider case study, even more than one, which could include more places and more participants. That way, data could be collected from a more diverse sample of people and places.

Furthermore, if funds had permitted, I would have opted for case studies in more than one city in Scotland, so that samples could be more generalised. In this study, because I used funds from a specific heritage project with targeted audiences, I had to focus on specific outcomes, areas and participants. If funding was not the issue, I would have reached out to more groups from different places. The selection of participants was based on availability and impacted by time restrictions (the heritage project had a one-year duration). Data collection was designed to fit the required timeline of the community heritage project, thus ideally, fieldwork would have benefited from a longer duration.

This study was designed and organised to fit with the activities of the specific groups, in the areas, where they operated to their scheduled programmes. Thus, my previous experience in the areas of study dictated the way I approached the design, and the decisions for the fieldwork, to fit in with the groups' scheduled activities. A

lot of the observations were based on unstructured activities, in some instances fitting in with participants' needs and schedules. This means that it would be difficult for other researchers to repeat the study exactly under the same circumstances. However, a future study could use the components and the structure of the case studies and adapt them to similar environments. The livescape as an inquiry tool and method of participation permits repetition, as long as the environment can be activated, and the researcher examines the subsequent tensions.

6. Structure of the Thesis through the Chapters

The thesis is structured as follows. Firstly, in the introductory chapter, I explain the fields that the study is situated within. Then I give a brief background to the study, for the reader to get an understanding of the field and the environment where the study took place. I explain why those sites were important to the study. Then, I present briefly existing knowledge on the concepts that I focus on in the post-industrial heritage of the urban waterways, and identify gaps in the knowledge, which lead me to identify the main research problem. The aims, objectives and main question of the study are outlined, followed by the significance of the study to the relevant academic fields and the contribution to knowledge. Finally, I present the limitations, which underpin my understandings of how the study could be enhanced, and the scope widened.

Secondly, the Literature Review chapter critically engages the conceptualisation of the activated and contested livescape and examines the existing scholarly knowledge mainly in the fields of critical heritage studies, urban geography, and expands on the fields of anthropology, political theory and sociology that have studied the urban landscape, its development and the effect on its localities. The chapter examines literature on place making processes with a particular focus on the urban post-industrial waterways and waterfronts, and the understanding and relation of the heritage environment via AHD. The role of memory and monumentality in the urban landscape is juxtaposed with theories of publicness and the cultural space in cities as part of the place making process. The heterogeneous and problematized concept of local communities is examined from the point of view of transiency, in form of marginalisation, experienced deprivation and exclusion from decision-making processes related to engagements with the heritage landscape. Thus, concepts of liminality, knowledge, AHD and the everyday life are studied against the notion that heritage is processual and live and it is understood through activation in the life realm of the everyday. Additionally, existing literature explores tangible and intangible heritages in the urban landscape and the way they are interweaved with the vitality of

materials, craft and theories of more-than-representational space, as underpinning the processual nature of heritage. Finally, the literature review chapter concludes with a discussion on issues identified in the post-industrial heritage landscape and the local communities' engagement with it, issues that have not been sufficiently covered by the existing studies.

The literature review is followed by the Methodology and Methods chapter, which presents and analyses the philosophical and theoretical underpinnings of the methods used for data collection and subsequent analysis. Firstly, the study's design, philosophy, epistemology and methodology of research are justified and explained. More specifically, there follows a discussion of the philosophical paradigm, an introduction to the study's conceptual framework and approach, research type, and the principles of the study. This is where the positionality of the researcher is explained and discussed. Secondly, the research strategy is analysed *vis-à-vis* the explanation of the case study in relation to the community heritage project, CanalCraft, followed by a presentation of the data collection methods. The participatory action research approach and ethnography, auto-ethnography, and interviews as data collection methods are discussed in this section. The next section presents the timeline and sampling strategy, including explanations about the selection of places, activities and the sampling groups. Analysis of data through methods and techniques is then explained, with an emphasis on the main method of thematic analysis. Finally, the limitations of the methods are discussed, followed by a conclusion about the overall evaluation of the methodology of the study. The Methods chapter includes extracts of the Portfolio of the thesis, which consisted of a body of work that highlights the outcomes of the practice led study. The Portfolio is an integral part of the thesis, and significant because it illustrates the concept of the activated and contested livescape; the livescape becomes alive through the Portfolio. Moreover, this is a practice led study, thus, the body of work was produced during the time of data collection and fieldwork. The Portfolio as the practical part of the thesis stands alone, whereas the chapters form the explanation of the practice and the step-by-step development of the study, theoretically, methodologically and empirically. As the study examines participation of transient communities with the post-industrial waterways and aims to examine engagement with heritage assets and cultural organisations in the urban waterways, the portfolio is evidence of the data collected and shows how it was disseminated; in the form of objects (boats), craft (boat-building and boat-handling), celebratory events, and an exhibition. Furthermore, the Portfolio is specifically curated to include photographic evidence of fieldwork from ethnographic and auto-ethnographic

observations, workshops, visits, and archival material collected during the study. The portfolio also includes material from the exhibition and short films created to mark the end of CanalCraft, the community heritage project.

In Chapter IV, the Case Study, the Results and Analysis are presented together as they were both based on the data, the evidence collected via the methods of case study and the interviews. This approach has the rationale of enabling the reader to follow the case study's structure and description and seamlessly connect it with the results, through quotes and imagery from the Portfolio. This approach also enables the reader to link sequentially the case study with the results and analysis to achieve a better understanding of the unravelling of the livescape through words, themes and illustrations. As the analytical approach is thematic, diagrams and specific examples from the signposted Portfolio illustrate the themes, categories and subcategories or patterns. Thus, firstly, the case study introduces the context in which the study took place - the specific heritage landscape and the locality. The context reminds the reader of the landscape and at the same time, provides a platform on which to introduce the themes of the analysis and appreciate how they link to the conceptual formation of the livescape. The chapter continues with a discussion of CanalCraft, the community heritage project on which the case study was based on. The activities and events are described as a series of observations and the interviews depict the situations in which they were conducted. The tensions concerning the unpacking of the concept of the livescape are placed in thematic categories and subcategories, illustrated by examples from data (extracts from meetings, videos and photo diaries, other fieldnotes and illustrations from the online Portfolio). At this stage, the livescape 'becomes alive', and the reader is able to follow the tensions through the activations, along with insights and interpretations of the data and the analysis. Images and examples from the online Portfolio follow the themes of the presentation. The combined case study, analysis and results chapter, concludes with a discussion and summation of the case study, interviews and the results of the analysis. The explanation of how I arrived at the conceptualisation of the livescape is supported by each tension and images from the online Portfolio. The chapter concludes with comments and suggestions for further discussion.

In the Concluding chapter (Chapter V) I integrate the most significant elements of the study, the conceptualisation of the activated livescape. I suggest the ways the livescape, activated by local communities who experience transiency, through their changing regenerated locality and their potential lack of

opportunities for engagement, reveals the tensions that have a significant effect in engagement with local heritage, and these identified tensions influence the heritage process. I specifically relate it to the original research question of the study, along with additional questions that I presented complementing the main research question. I present the insights that the study revealed through answering the questions I began the thesis with. Additionally, I present a brief summary of the livescape as a model of engagement, and I discuss its theoretical, methodological and empirical significance to the fields of critical heritage studies and human geography. I finally suggest that the livescape could be applicable to other environments, beyond the heritage field. These I discuss along with recommendations for further study on heritage participation for more inclusive heritage futures.

Chapter II Literature Review

1. Introduction

1.1 The livescape – a situated notion within knowledge

The historic landscape is not only a place where heritage exists and is practiced (Hackney, 2017:194), but it is also an environment where tensions appear when the landscape is activated. In this study of the activation of the heritage landscape and the effects of such activation on the heritage process, I examine participation in and involvement with heritage of the local communities who experience the post-industrial urban and inland waterways of Glasgow as a heritage environment. The historic urban post-industrial landscape is a place in transit, as it undergoes changes that affect the locality, thus, I begin by examining the existing literature, through the notion of *livescape* – a possible alternative mode of engagement with heritage localities.

The notion of livescape is conceptualised, in this study, as the transient, activated and contested heritage landscape which is then understood and developed through the exploration of the tensions which produce it. In this research, transiency, sense of familiarity with and ownership of place, and inequalities in knowledge formation, are recognised and identified tensions in the heritage landscape, and are discussed through a consideration of the existing literature.

This study of the livescape is situated within the fields of human geography and critical heritage studies, although it also, relatedly, draws on cultural and political studies and specifically theories of the everyday, liminality, vitality, and neo-materialism. In this literature review, I will also discuss how the livescape, as a conceptualisation, relates to, but differs from, theories of place-making (Pierce et al., 2010; Martin, 2003; Anderson and Gale, 1992), and of the affectual altered urban place (Thrift, 2004). Theoretical consideration concerns the ways in which the conception of activated livescape departs from the notion of *lived space* (Lefebvre, 1991:362) understood as the experienced space that comes about through the process of the production of space. The concept of the livescape also relates to considerations concerning the way knowledge is formed and acquired and hierarchies of knowledge, and through doing so, it provides the basis for heritage theories that concern the notion of AHD (Smith, 2006) and how these influence engagement in both the transient place and the heritage process.

Given the above, in focusing on the research's central question concerning the ways in which local communities engage with local heritage and how these engagements then inform the heritage process, I will begin with a discussion of the relevant existing literature with respect to the conceptualisation of livescape and the notions and theories that underpin it.

1.2 Structure of chapter

In this chapter I consider the existing relevant literature on *the place* (the heritage landscape- the locality) as a transient environment with specific respect to the urban space (landscape) as shaped by the place-making process and critical heritage studies' consideration of the binary relationship of nature/culture. In doing so, I discuss transiency through the role of memory and monumentality and those of urban space's publicness (Varna, 2010) and *familiarity*, and how these relationships are juxtaposed with the cultural space (Low, 2003). Furthermore, I examine literature on the notion of *local community*, as transient, again within the framework of the place-making process, liminality (in-betweenness) and change in the locality. I then examine the notion of *knowledge* in the heritage environment, the effect of AHD, inequalities in how knowledge is formed, and how these impact on agency for transient communities in the locality. I also examine literature on the *processual nature of heritage* and how this emerges through activations within everyday life in the transient post-industrial heritage landscape.

Further, I review the literature on notions of heritage in relation to the heritage landscape and its binary expressions as tangible/intangible and natural/cultural. The more-than-representational space, the vitality of materials, and notion of liminality of a place, as they characterise the sense of in-betweenness in the regenerated environment, and the ways in which the in-betweenness and transiency affect heritage's processual nature.

Finally, I discuss the notion of transiency, as covered in the relevant literature, in two respects. Firstly, transiency as the experience of the altered regenerated urban heritage space when this is combined with exclusion from direct decision-making – and the implications this has for emotions of belonging, familiarity, and a sense of ownership of place. Secondly, transiency as experienced through individual and collective experiences of mobility (through displacement, social and spatial mobility due to life circumstances) (Bulmer

and Solomos, 2017), leading to perceptions of marginalisation and of exclusion from direct engagement (Gray, 2018).

2. The livescape

Places and landscapes are transient and processual (Thrift and Crang, 2000; Lorimer, 2005; Muller, 2015; Lefebvre, 1991) and previous studies have analysed the role of transient heritage places and landscapes in the heritage process (Groote and Haartsen, 2006; Harvey, 2015; McDowell, 2008; Nardi, 2014). The term *landscape* is understood in this research to be the geographical locality that consists of human and non-human elements actions and interactions, collectively and as relational ontologies (Grauer, 2019). The transient locality containing interactions and tensions deriving from interactions revealing the activated and contested livescape, which is this study's contribution.

Figure 1: The activated and contested livescape as framed in this research

2.1 Developing from the lived space

Post-industrial urban heritage landscapes have been formed through place-making processes (Hölzer, 2008; Vallerani and Visentin, 2018), adapting a homogenous perspective towards heritage, as places acquire specific characteristics and uses, resulting in the creation of abstract spaces (Lefebvre, 1991: 362), space devised by expertise knowledge. With respect to Lefebvre's triad relating to the production of space – the perceived space, the conceived space and the lived space -, Lefebvre's conception of the lived space, the representational space, is understood as an unfinished processual entity, which emerges through daily experience (Smith, 2016).

Thus, in the literature, place is understood as the amalgamation of tangible and intangible entities and activities (objects), and as Lefebvre (1991: 83) presents it the Thing that becomes an absolute. The absolute is susceptible to the formation and application of knowledge hierarchies, knowledges that are formed through official institutions such as universities, and this absolute fails to account for or incorporate the realities as to the elements of place that do not align with the conceived plan for that place. Hegemonic realities as to attitudes to knowledge creation and ownership, lead to distinct tensions with respect to the heritage landscape. Furthermore, according to Lefebvre, hierarchies within the lived space are implied by the word user (*usager*) which has negative connotations, implying that the place occupier is somehow *allowed* or even *has been given permission* to be there. Through my examination of communities' participation in the heritage landscape, I align this PhD research with and I support Lefebvre's lived space and his critiques as to the concept of the user (place occupier as part of the locality), as these are reflected in transient communities' experience of place within the framework of place-making urban planning, which is based on 'abstractions' (Lefebvre, 1991:93), on designed spaces. The user or occupier/participant in the activation of the heritage landscape, experiences the landscape, objects, activities and interactions as part of the place, by exposing the tensions in these experiences, through aiming to reveal the natural environment of the place, '[t]he more a space partakes of nature, the less it enters into the social relations of production' (1991: 83). Thus, considering transiency in the landscape by viewing it holistically, eliminates characterisation and thus directional making of a place.

In the production of space, social forces, economic and linguistic, tangible and intangible entities, are in place across the whole of the life realm (Lefebvre, 1991: 82). Lefebvre claims that production of space also implies strategic planning, such as city strategic plans on place-making (Rosenstein, 2011). Given this understanding, the realities are of a multiscale space where forces of making (production of a place) range from the global to the local. The cultural strategies of cities, such as Glasgow (Judd and Fainstein, 1999; Mooney, 2004), that aspire to metropolitan status, incorporate a focus on the improvement of their post-industrial abandoned spaces. In such processes, the preservation of a conception as to non-homogenous place presents challenges and causes tension, as, according to Lefebvre, places of interaction remind him of 'flaky mille-feuille pastry' rather than beautified homogenous spaces.

Lefebvre's lived space provides a foundation for the conceptualisation of the livescape in this literature review, underpinning transiency that exists with respect to engagements with the heritage place; transiency that arises through acknowledgement that a place is not one thing, but interactions and everyday experiences, at the same time exposed to strategies that alter perceptions, thus non-fixed but transitioning. The experience of a place is generated through the memory of doing, as Lefebvre argues, a becoming entity.

2.2 The made place as transient locality

In this literature review I focus on the definition, by Cresswell (2004: 39) and Friedmann (2010: 153) of the urban built space as one that is defined by the social activity in it, and thus its transiency. Social activity aligns with the activation of heritage, the heritage practice, as described in the research's case study in Chapter IV. Social activity is connected with opportunities to use the urban space, and in this research I am particularly concerned about the use of blue spaces. Blue spaces, like cultural urban spaces, made places, embed plurality, with complex experiences and opportunities for being there and occupying. In understanding a locality, its occupiers and their adaptation to changes induced by place-making processes, the 'self-defined neighbourhoods of urban life' (Friedmann, 2010:161) follow rather than lead the process of place-making (De Liu and Lin, 2011; Mooney, 2004; Button and Pearce, 1989; Holzer, 2008; Varna, 2016). On the other hand, Hutton's study of cultural economy and its effect on urban life suggests that '[t]he cultural economy reflects (and embodies) the extraordinarily nuanced relationships between diverse fields of human enterprise and the constituent elements of the city: space, landscape, identity, meaning, labour, connectivity, and social relations, and lifestyles' (Hutton 2016: 325). These differing perspectives on the meaning of a place and lifestyle

underpin the complexities of engagement with the heritage space as a phenomenon central to the creation of sense of belonging in a place, as understood in terms of 'territorialized politics of belonging; (Trudeau, 2006: 421). Whether a place is one of livelihood, leisure or both, the place is the life realm of its locality and contains all activities, and this applies to the post-industrial places of the urban waterways.

Figure 2: Transiency in the heritage locality

The diagram above illustrates the notion of transiency as it is underpinned in this study. Thus, transiency is considered as the state in a locality when approaches to the landscape block familiarity with it, such as being on a boat is an exclusive activity. Transiency is observed when anthropocentric attitudes towards the liminal landscape prevail, such as dismissive behaviour towards wildlife in the waterways for the sake of new buildings. Changes to the landscape with new buildings that sometimes alienate local communities connote transiency, such as the alteration of Glasgow's skyline on the river Clyde's waterfront with the appearance of icon buildings that cost millions of pounds to build. Prevailing knowledge for the landscape coming from the top down means that due to transiency decision-making is reserved for the authorities and the powerful. The four characteristics of transiency, as it is framed in this study, determine it as a tension in the activated livescape. The transient landscape is non static but ever-becoming, however activation (participation) in the locality is affected and it's influenced by structures of authority.

Figure 3: Locality

Locality in this diagram is depicted as the space that includes the whole landscape, including the communities that occupy it, and the activities that take place in it. The landscape consists of human and non-human elements, thus, matter, plants, objects, wildlife, are all parts of the locality. The same way, the amalgamation of all elements of the landscape create an ever-changing whole, locality is not an end-entity but an entity in transit. Transiency characterises the actions interacting within the human and non-human realm that forms the everyday life; the activity of the living realm. Everyday life coexists with memory in the locality, however, it is separate from monumentality: memory is not always shared, nor present, thus monuments in the locality do not share a homogenous meaning. Place-making affects the locality by making it transient, creating spaces that are end-entities for specific purposes; it is connected with AHD and power structures in the urban environment, blocking engagement with space. Whereas transiency in the locality also occurs by everyday life and its interactions within it, making it an ever-changing place, shaped by the life realm.

2.3 The cultural city as transient

Culture has played an important role in the alteration of the city landscape of Glasgow and the existing literature has extensively covered the city's place-making process, including, specifically, the Clyde waterfront and the only remaining functioning canal in the city, the Forth and Clyde canal (FCC). The scholarship mainly focuses on issues caused by the alteration of the landscape and transiency, with respect to community cohesion, and agency (Cadell and King, 2008; Breen and Ridby, 1996; Carter, 2017; Firth, 2016; Gillick and Ivett, 2018). Glasgow was designated the European City of Culture for 1990, which had the effect of placing cultural planning at the forefront of city planning and place-making for over three decades (Ghelfi, 2017; Miles, 2007). This is the root of the prevailing dynamic that creating an attractive city meant that some cultures that predominate in the city were affected by the process. Miles (2007: 76) discusses the ways in which the characteristic ways of life of city dwellers were in danger of disappearing, through having been impacted by the application of 'symbolic capital'. The transient locality emerges in previous studies through the conflicts of plurality and its position and agency in the urban environment. The real and the illusional (understood in terms of the symbolic, representational, or lifestyle) with respect to urban living are revisited here, as underpinning the livescape's framing of tensions that are the result of cultural strategies, '[i]n demographically multicultural societies and politics, conflicts over values and lifestyles, ways of being and ways of knowing, are unavoidable' (Sandercock 2006:47–48 as quoted in Miles, 2007: 142).

In Glasgow, the heritage landscape of the two urban waterways, the river Clyde and the FCC, both exemplars of transient places, have been central to political decisions about the alteration of the urban landscape, as has been manifested through the process of cultural planning and development (Hutton, 2002; Ghelfi, 2017; Paxton et al., 2000; Berry et al., 2013; Punter, 2011). Event-based and experience-centred (De Shule, 2008) cultural tourism took over urban planning: '[t]he proliferation of new buildings and sites are designed to produce (or reproduce) cultural signifiers as a means of attracting visitors' (Hutton, 2016: 341). These buildings, such as the new Riverside Museum, were designed alongside public spaces around them. However, the public spaces around the river have become restricted as new building works, for example residential, claim public space by restricting access. Thus, access to the river is restricted and controlled, and as Varna (2016) and Haeffner et al. (2017) argue, barriers to accessing blue places in cities affect quality of life and create inequalities in experiencing the urban fabric.

Furthermore, transiency emerges when experience with respect to the cultural economy (Pine and Gilmore, 1998: 97) interferes with opportunities in the locality to experience the place to gain local knowledge, through familiarity and consequently a sense of belonging. In that respect, what emerges in the literature relates to distinctions between the different types of community and different kinds of experiencing of places in gaining local knowledge and familiarity. Locality's identity is obscure in the urban landscape, due to transiency, as argued earlier, and also the landscape's changes in appearance, which happen due to political decisions and through the codification of the landscape (Trudeau, 2006: 437). The codes assigned to the landscape that determine how it is socially understood, may cause alienation – depending on the identity of the coder. Thus, transiency in this research is underpinned in the literature as this: although change is a characteristic of localities, '[t]he order is civil, the structure is centred, and the identity (Feuchtwang's 'interiority') is constantly being made and remade, because neighbourhood places are dynamic, and every snapshot is nothing more than a moment in the flow of life' (Friedmann, 2010: 162). The heritage locality, therefore, contains all the elements that constitute the ever-changing experience of a place, which are connected to the historicity of the 'flow of life'.

2.4 Heritage transient landscapes and places

Lowenthal argues that through the way in which heritage discourse views historic landscape, with the dominant understanding being one which separates nature from culture, 'no aspect of nature is unimpacted by human agency, no artefact devoid of environmental impress. Yet we have traditionally dealt quite differently with these two kinds of legacy' (Lowenthal, 2005: 81). Pallasmaa (2007: 17) argues that 'we do not only exist in a spatial and material reality, we also inhabit cultural, mental and temporal realities', which implies that a place is a multi-scalar entity and is understood through a recognition of both its physical characteristics and its immaterial ones. Where places are understood empirically, the body (as being) is understood in terms of being in the world rather than as a self-contained entity (Merleau-Ponty, 1962; Heidegger, 1971). Thus, with respect to an approach focusing on the phenomenological experience, the barriers between the environment and the body are dissolved. Merleau-Ponty on *being there* states ' [t]he body, is the vehicle of being in the world and having a body is, for a living creature, to be involved in a definite environment' (1962: 82).

While critical heritage theory discourse has firmly rejected the dichotomy of natural/cultural with respect to the historic environment and heritage places (Harrison, 2015) it is clear that in dominant and hegemonic approaches (Berg, 2004) to the place-making framework, this dichotomy remains, with the natural environment on one side, and that which humans have impacted still being viewed as separate entities. However, the UNESCO Convention of 2002 (UNESCO, 2002) declared the cultural and natural aspects of landscape to be one inseparable entity.

The main premise of the concept of the livescape in this research is that the heritage landscape is transient, due to its natural environment but also because of ongoing processes (Ingold, 2012) through which human and non-human factors are in operation within and on the location (Bennett, 2010).

In 2011, UNESCO approved the Historic Urban Landscape Approach (HULA), which aspired to address the impact of authorised discourses on heritage as based on the ontological binaries of natural/cultural, tangible/intangible, and took into consideration other elements such as the places' value to communities, the impact of heritage on the environment, cultural diversity, and the local economy (Rogers, 2017; Onesti, 2015; Ginzarly et al, 2019). Harrison (2014: 24), suggests that this formal dissolution of the binary assumption about the landscape releases 'a sense of how heritage could be oriented toward composing "common worlds" or "common futures," while maintaining a sensitivity to the ways in which each domain of heritage relates to a particular mode of existence'. This research is founded upon the processual characteristic of heritage landscapes and places, as transient places, in how they are viewed and experienced.

However, tension is then created as to the way places are viewed in place-making. Developing Harrison's position on heritage futures, Rogers', with respect to HULA's understanding of urban habitation and consequently of heritage processes, points to how this understanding impacts on the theorisation of this research's concept of the activated livescape – as an acceptance of decay as part of the life realm and vitality, within historic environments, commenting on, 'the various ways in which the HULA methodology and tools can support the messy, living nature of historic cities: recognizing and mapping of living, messy "real world" heritage; valuing its complexity and understanding its vulnerabilities; integrating it into a wider operationalized framework of city conservation and development' (Rogers, 2017).

The HULA suggestions of heritage process sparked scholarly responses (Bandarin and Van Oers eds., 2014; Erkan, 2018) that questioned the ways that the new paradigm of thinking about the landscape would be

operable in the life realm of the everyday of cities. The challenge suggests that although HULA promotes empowerment in heritage localities via cultural activities, in order to enhance pluralism within the place, '[m]anagement of living cultural heritage requires an integrated and multidimensional approach' (Erkan, 2018: 347). In other words, despite efforts for inclusion, cultural activity as part of place-making may impede the kinds of complex modes of engagement that are appropriate with respect to transient localities, thus a wider and more complex approach to the place is needed to embrace its processual nature.

In heritage urban places, the nature/culture binary still characterises attitudes to heritage environments (Lowenthal, 2005: 86), which affects engagement with them. Leitão (2017) argues that this stance is hard to address, as it underlies a network of powers within the heritage sector, which is institutionalised, given that the World Heritage Convention hasn't resolved the problems associated with different attitudes towards 'mixed sites' (:195). Thus, the literature suggests that a heritage environment, a place, is characterised by the institutions that operate in it, and which institutions have the power to implement their approach to engagement in the locality, according to that characterisation.

Ginzarly et al. (2019: 27) consider the appropriateness of a values based approach with respect to the implementation of HUL as intending to consider urban heritage holistically, with a focus on the locality's unique characteristics and the need for agency, when at the same time, identifying academic discourse as problematic in the implementation of theoretical suggestions (2019:27). This discussion underpins the conceptualisation of the livescape as recognising knowledge as coming from a top-down direction in the heritage place, rather than acknowledging that knowledge has the potential to be created through the everyday life realm and interactions in it.

2.4.1 Memory and monument in a transient heritage landscape.

Considering that the transient heritage landscape is approached as homogenous by the institutions that operate in it, this has a specific impact with regard to understandings of places of monumentality by its locality.

The institutionalised approach is challenged from the point of view that such localities are not homogenous with respect to their transiency, which transiency is connected with identity formation based on memories ,

'most of us are convinced of our identities: we have personality, memories and recollections' (Varela et al., 1993:4).

Memory, as discussed in a range of studies (Bachelard, 1958; Crinson, 2005; McDowell, 2008; Trieb ed., 2009; Finn, 2015), works as one of the receptors of experience. We collect memories by interacting with the landscape and with others (Bachelard, 1958), which makes the process unique and contextual. Given this, memory is not static or fixed, therefore, heritage, which is processual (Smith, 2006), can be understood as the 'desire to represent memory through the marking of *place*' (McDowell et al., 2008: 38), and '[j]ust like heritage, the practice of memory-work takes place somewhere' (Buciek and Jull, 2008: 111). Heritage's fluidity implies relations with historicity, rather than merely history and that makes a heritage landscape a complex place and impacts in its perception by the locality '[s]paces become memorable in two ways: through formal structures with special coherence or power, and through events that take place rooted in a location... It is the duality of these sources that sometimes makes the designation of "historic buildings or places puzzling"' (Lyndon and Thieb, 2009:63).

The built environment is *mnemonic* (Lyndon and Thieb, 2009) and given this, we are defined and evolve through the environment in which we dwell (Bachelard, 1958). Thus, a place of memory is transient and generated by activation, which in the regenerated urban space occurs through place-making processes (Martin, 2003).

2.4.2 Place-making and monumentality

Place-making processes which contribute to transiency tend to approach the heritage place and monumentality from a homogenous stance, and examples of this are the prevailing modes of memory-based urban place-making in post-industrial landscapes. Crinson (2005: xi) observes that in an effort to preserve the past through monumentality, place-making processes apply similar methods such as 'the "villaging" of city centres to evoke lost or mythical forms of the public life, historic buildings that are little more than the carcasses of former functions[...]' to urban developments, but without the reality of the everyday life realm, which lacks the patina of nostalgia and instead presents a raw image of the place. Crinson adds that 'the paradox of this is that it works in a context where deprivation has increasingly become peripheralised in the post-industrial city, while in other parts of the world has increased as never before'. This notion of

representation through monumentality poses questions as to the authenticity of memory, and whom it is that memory represents, and transiency emerges through this questioning.

Monumentality in place-making with respect to the built environment emerges through the preservation of significant buildings or when 'the monument joints the everyday (street life)' (Crisson, 2005: xvii). Memory can be 're-enacted' (McDowell, 2008: 41) by people who do not actually possess a living memory of an event, situation or act. Thus, according to previous studies, monuments are formed notions of shared memory, which become the dominant and recognised collective memory, relating to the notion of re-enactment through cultural events due to place-making. Shared memories, understood in this way, inform the dominant trajectory as to how a place is characterised, through mnemonic 'hegemonies' imposed by collectives and institutions, and this helps to explain discrepancies with the localities, as such – non-homogeneous engagement; 'sites of memory and power are often constructed in public spaces' (McDowell, 2008: 45). Therefore, according to literature, the heritage environment is often understood and experienced through place-making processes of power that are perceived to possess knowledge. In the transient heritage landscape, knowledge is contested through sense of familiarity with the locality and opportunities for engagement and interaction (Berg, 2004).

2.4.3 Knowledge, agency and heritage practice in the transient place.

Sense of familiarity with a place is recognised, in the locality, as (local) knowledge (Smith 2006). When local communities in Castleford applied local knowledge and skills to embrace 'change' and through doing so altered their place (Smith, 2006: 252). Smith also points out, in the same discussion of that Castleford community, that the meaning of heritage from below is informed by universal concepts, connected with the life realm of communities, such as family and friends.

The concept of 'regulated heritage behaviour' (Smith, 2006:79) underpins the argument of this study concerning the tension of transiency with relation to where the dominant paradigm of knowledge, and where knowledge derives from, and how democratic decision making in the urban environment that affects the heritage practice, is. That, if knowledge as part of the heritage practice is scripted by the discourses of authorised heritage, then interactions in the transient, heritage place are controlled by such dominant discourses (Harrison et al., 2020).

2.4.4 Heritage process, AHD and the transient heritage place.

The literature relevant to heritage processes in the urban environment suggest that interactions within the transient heritage place tend to be regulated. Smith's study of heritage uses (2006) underpins this suggestion and defines AHD as the dominant knowledge-based paradigms that set the regulations for what constitutes heritage and how it should be safeguarded.

AHD impacts on place-making processes (Zhu, 2018); it influences interpretations of activities, and it forms the basis on which monuments, of any scale, are recognised and preserved – according to AHD categorisation and regulation systems, as underpinned by multi-national heritage organisations and conventions, such as UNESCO and ICOMS (Harrison, 2013: 5). According to Smith, made places of heritage environments become 'scripted', specifically characterised as monuments, and thus they are experienced through defined regulations by heritage institutions (Smith, 2006: 79)

AHD influences not only institutional conceptions as to the nature of heritage, as focused on 'users' (Crooke 2011), but also affects local communities' attitudes to what constitutes heritage, constructing its meaning (Smith 2006:256). Furthermore, it affects understandings of heritage participation, given that this is linked to being part of a group collectively activating the heritage environment (Holmes 2003). Thus, given Smith's conception of the term AHD, knowledge relates to scalar participations and involvements in the heritage landscape, which suggests that heritage participation is conditional (2006:83). Relating to the contestations that are associated with the heritage landscape, Smith's conception of 'dissonant heritage' (2006:80) is one which informs whether places are regarded as heritage or not, and consequently how this affects behaviour. Central to all these considerations is the influence of AHD on the way the transient locality, community, human and non-human elements interact in the heritage process and activate the heritage environment.

Figure 4: Heritage as it is framed in the activated heritage livescape

This diagram shows the way the notion of heritage is framed in this research. Heritage is connected with Participation to the landscape in order to activate it, such as the craft of boating. It's also connected to locality, such as the historic waterway. Heritage for this research is non-binary, thus it's natural and cultural, tangible and intangible, memory and experience, and uninherited. The waterways are an example of this notion as they are a natural environment but they are manmade (the canal); they are tangible due to features such as bridges, but also intangible because bridges need skill to operate them; historic waterways depend on memory to be monumental, but they also depend on experience by the people who live near them everyday. Finally, heritage doesn't need to be inherited, as its meaning can be transferable through different localities, the same way the canal reminded participants in the boat-handling activities of the waterways back to their countries of origin. AHD and dominant knowledge dominate the locality in the urban regenerated place, however, as heritage is a process, like the landscape is in, it is non static, but it alters through the everyday life.

2.4.4 Post-industrial transient landscapes: wastelands or heritage?

The same concept of dissonant heritage applies to mundane places. These places, which are outside the AHD framework, yet of everyday importance to communities, may be considered as 'not heritage'. Given this, '[t]he danger is that those elements excluded from official heritage narratives are thereafter denied any place in social memory' (Atkinson, 2008: 384). In the case of the post-industrial heritage landscape in Glasgow, which are places perceived as declining and decayed- transient- the dominant knowledge paradigms of the AHD are connected to place-making processes of renewal (Bury, 2009). As Desilvey (2017:12) argues, 'the focus of scholarship, for the most part, remains resolutely fixed on the destructive aspects of the decay process and on identifying strategies for protection and remediation'. The issue for the heritage process remains whether such landscapes are perceived as heritage, when issues concerning what is tangible and intangible heritage remains tied into the AHD and knowledge that derives from the top down. On the intangibility of heritage, Smith and Akagawa (2009: 6) state that heritage as a notion is recognised and acknowledged through 'a particular set of cultural or social values, which are themselves *intangible*'. The role of AHD in the place-making process, through a heritagization process, contributes to the characterisation of transiency, as cultural and social values are not homogeneous and places do not have the same importance in the local community 'as they promote solidarity within a certain group by separating it from others' (Poria and Ashworth, 2009: 524).

2.4.5 Transiency, locality and the notion of local community

Locality in this research embeds transiency, which is supported in previous studies of the opportunities for social interactions in the urban environment. It has been argued that the community of a locality, like its place, is not a homogenous and set entity, but a collection of perplexing combinations and unstable components that work together to create it (Bauman, 2001, Moser et al., 2002, Crook, 2010, Hackney, 2017). In the conceptualisation of the contested heritage livescape, and specifically regarding considerations as to the changeability of the locality, part of the cultural city, communities expose transiency, reflecting fluid cultural realities, such as multiculturalism and marginalisation (Buciek and Juul, 2008; McDowell, 2008; Crooke, 2007; Watson and Waterton, 2010; Midland and Grahn, 2012; Krauss, 2008; Collins, 2018, Ng, 2018). The notions of changeability and diversity in communities, primarily as discussed by Bauman, are central here, reflecting both

transiency and a sense of familiarity as developed through interactions. Belonging to a locality is a complex matter, '[t]here is a price to be paid for the privilege of "being in a community" – and it is inoffensive or even invisible only as long as the community stays in the dream' (Bauman, 2001: 4).

I consider identification of locality, as a notion, core to this research, and literature supports that identifying a local community is a complex matter. Transiency emerges as the community element in a locality provides a narrative for place-making processes. Mee Kam Ng argues that a community that is related to a place is subject to many external forces, particularly the stakeholders that are interested in developing the place, 'how places are characterised, represented or perceived may have real consequences on people's perceptions of, and practices of space' (Ng, 2018 :2).

Thus, transiency arises between the place as community maker, and the community as a place-maker; between the perception of the place through practice, and consequently the formation of knowledge, and the practice of activity which the place directs (Lefebvre, 1968). Thus, transiency is underpinned in the literature through examinations of both the altered place experience and the mobilised community. Additionally, this is implied by the different communities in a place having a variety of interests, 'place frames', examined as clusters of collective mobilisation for a common cause (Martin, 2003: 747). In this research, this element is manifested through the activation of the waterways by boaters, such as the FCCS's ongoing campaign for a navigable canal.

According to Martin (2003), neighbourhoods are arbitrary collectives and their collectivity is derived through their struggle for agency, therefore, place framing focuses on revealing alliances that serve a purpose or a campaign, and which do not necessarily share other bonding elements. Bauman discusses the notion of belonging to the usability of a place (relevance, comfort, ease), which affects communities' functions on both a group and individual level (2001:5), which emphasises transiency through the experience of place as activation.

Therefore, belonging, understood as a sense of security in a place, is related to a local community's perception of the locality, what they know about it, and how individuals feel within it. Bauman criticises the lack of resources and provision of services with respect to less privileged communities, as this deprives them of a sense of safety, 'in a world dominated by *do-it-yourself* approaches to community, safety is related with struggles for urban space, a sense of belonging' (2001:112), and I would add, knowledge about it.

Concurrently, the perception of locality, knowledge and the sense of place, is changeable and affected by external and internal factors, which in their turn, affect the decisions of individuals as to whether to become part of a collective or a group: 'Distinctiveness means: the division into "us" and "them"...there are no "betwixt and between" cases left, it is crystal clear who is "one of us" and who is not' (Bauman, 2001: 12).

Therefore, the literature supports that transiency emerges in the locality when within community groups knowledge and senses of belonging conflict with unconventional practices: reflecting the fact that 'orthodoxy [is] articulated in response to an alleged transgression' (Trudeau, 2006: 434), which suggests the meanings of place.

2.4.6 Familiarity and belonging in the transient place.

Transiency in the unfinished and always changing heritage landscape is evident through the existence of cultural clusters, serving to embed issues of inequality and injustice in the sharing of the city (Collins, 2018; Rosenstein, 2011). Previous studies on the concept of engagement with place have investigated urban placeness and openness and familiarity (publicness) (Lefebvre, 1968, Kofman and Lebas, 1996). A consideration of these concepts in relation to Glasgow is undertaken by McPherson and Flinn (2007) who examined community interactions with cultural life. They explain that when communities come together to share in cultural life, this enhances the community's relationships, partnerships and networks. Local government seeks to empower communities with respect to taking ownership of their locality and the building of social capital through partnerships, a process in which the cultural sector plays a pivotal role. It does so by raising aspirations, which in their turn, lead to increased educational attainment (:8).

Varna and Tiesdall's discussion on publicness of place, analyses 'meta dimensions' (meaning, ownership, control, civility, physical configuration, and animation) (2014: 581). The meta dimensions underpin the theorisation of the livescape as a carrier of tensions that reflect these dimensions, the transiency, where publicness is the opportunity to be familiar with the environment (in this case blue spaces), as considered in terms of activation, knowledge, agency, and belonging.

2.4.7 Marginalisation and transiency in the locality

Therefore, Collins suggests that the concept of community is multifaceted and understood through a collection of factors that characterise the place 'communities can be divided in their perception and experience of

neighbourhood culture and change' (Collins, 2018: 11). The struggle for agency and participation in the decision-making processes is connected to transiency in relation to the heritage process.

Transiency in the locality is experienced through marginalisation, and, with respect to heritage practice, is connected to the politics of visibility (Byrne, 2009), and linked to heritage institutions' efforts to improve their visibility within local communities (McDowell, 2008).

Mowat (2015) argues that marginalisation has two facets, the sensed and the recognised, which are linked to inclusion/exclusion and thus transiency presented as the struggle for agency, 'it is important to recognise that marginalisation is more than a state: it encompasses feelings about that state. To be marginalised is to have a sense that one does not belong and, in so doing, to feel that one is neither a valued member of a community and able to make a valuable contribution within that community nor able to access the range of services and/or opportunities open to others. In effect, to feel, and be, excluded' (2015:457). I relate this point to the desire of communities in the locations of this research, who have experienced forced and prolonged dislocation, to contribute to the host community.

2.4.8 Communities in the locality in transit

Transiency, in terms of mobility, does not always reflect deprivation, and this is covered in literature on the cultural city and the new global class (Florida, 2003; Bauman, 2001). However, in this research, transiency in communities that experience mobilisation is examined by accepting that there is deprivation from services in the locality, 'the communal principal of sharing cannot be accepted' as localities become progressively exclusive (Bauman, 2001: 59).

This is a focal point of the research, as the literature discusses the complexity of transiency in the locality of made urban places in relation to the conceptualisation of the livescape and transiency as tension in the heritage landscape. Bauman argues for the global (transient) that are those who possess the privilege of traveling widely across the globe, and as such, they are not tied to the one place (compared to the displaced communities that reside in the same locality under place-making processes). The place is also important for this group, however, as despite their non-local sensibilities and possession of the privilege to be able to travel to anywhere in the world, they also need a place to belong to, as safety/familiarity is a universal value (2001: 113). Therefore, previous studies reveal a gap in literature where there is a need for examination of the

complexity of transiency in the urban locality, by looking closely to the concept of 'local community' through nuanced study.

Ehrkamp and Leitner (2006) analyse the issue of safety (in terms of inclusion, provision and agency) in relation to the global elite, affecting their perception of space, which manifests in 'a burglar-free and stranger-proof "safe environment". "Community" stands for isolation, separation, protective walls and guarded gates' (Bodnar, 2015:2095). Place-making processes as part of urban renewal involve privatisation of public space, which affects the sense of a place in the locality, '[t]he triad of private management, public ownership and public access has become the new recipe and norm for public space regeneration closely followed by the model of privately owned public space' (Bodnar 2015: 2095). Thus, transiency is experienced by the restrictions of use of the urban environment, and this includes the heritage locality, phenomena that I have observed, for example, in the regenerated waterfront of the river Clyde.

Therefore, the argument put forward in this PhD study, with respect to the rights to public space and the agencies that manage the control of it and access to it, is supported by Bauman's analysis of place-making processes, specifically the point that, in the renewed urban environment, the dominant mentality of the community can be understood not as a platform of shared resources, but rather as 'charged with the oppression of individual autonomy' (Bauman, 2001:62), which manifests as demands for 'more space'.

Thus, public space has become widely politicised and contested (Harvey, 2012). Urban design that promoted gated communities or defensible architecture went hand in hand with urban policies of cleansing and 'policing public space to make it fit for a more select clientele' (Bodnar, 2015: 2093). This point of the community groups being perceived as a consumer rather than a producer (Bauman, 2001: 120) is important to the study as it underpins an existing mentality of groups in relation to inclusion and visibility and underpins the conceptualisation of transiency in relation to knowledge formation and familiarity in locality.

2.4.9 Knowledge and agency in the transient locality and the everyday realm.

The heterogeneous nature of communities occupying places of heritage determine understandings of heritage and affect its process (Smith and Akagawa, 2009). In contrast, the heritagization process (Poria and Ashworth, 2009: 523) which speaks to the trajectory of recognition, categorisation and protection in relation to the historic environment, applies a one-size-fits-all perspective (Zhu, 2018). This neglecting of nuanced

community interactions and elements can induce tension, as cultural and social values are not homogeneous and places do not have the same meaning in the local community (Poria and Ashworth, 2009: 524).

Furthermore, authorised heritages, tend to be anchored in the senses and their materiality so as to be justified as valuable, and this place-making process tends to neglect the everyday realm, the familiar and the local knowledge that derive from everyday interactions. Thus, heritage acquires a recognised shape, 'discernible and therefore knowable' (Kearney, 2008: 210).

The heritage landscape contains the practice of the everyday that establishes familiar connections and interactions with the heritage environment, even if those practices are not recognised as authorised heritages. Byrne suggests to rather place the emphasis on the intangibility of the place rather than its recognised intangible heritage and in that way the focus shifts to the study of 'the politics of visibility' (Byrne, 2009: 249).

AHD usually exhibits inflexibility in accommodating the nuances of locality and community (Smith, 2006: 80).

AHD values, at least in theory, the flexibility of community's heterogeneity. However, community 'will be renegotiated so that it fits the purpose for which it is being used' (Crook, 2010: 17). This form of renegotiation is utilised by the place-making process, as homogeneity in the heritage landscape could induce feelings of comfort for local communities who regularly participate in heritage (Atkinson, 2008: 391). In some situations, authority adapts to incorporate the mundane and the fluidity of the unexpected input from what locality has to offer (Atkinson, 2008:392). Grydehoj (2011: 87) argues that heritage derives from 'the complex webs of cultural history contextualising them', thus suggesting that not all proclaimed heritage places are accepted as such by the local communities, as localities are not homogenous with respect to their nature and practices. In the heritage landscape, authorised discourses held by those deemed to have heritage expertise, the 'heritage promoters' (Grydehoj, 2011: 87), unravel through discrepancies that are foregrounded by the way communities, and the locality as a whole, actually engage with heritage. That 'heritage is a cultural practice' (Stevenson, 2013:11) in the life realm and the landscapes we experience, suggests that heritage is recognised as a cultural activity. As such, this connects to urban place-making processes and the cultural city's strategies. What we perceive as space is a cultural practice (Hayles, 1996: 413) and any community practice recognised (authorised) as cultural or not, is heritage practice (including unvalued or undervalued practices). Thus, the contested heritage livescape is situated in the gaps between monumentality, knowledge, everyday life realm,

the place and how heritage is or is not recognised, and how it is understood, by and through communities' practices, but also through interactions with the non-human and material elements in the locality.

2.4.10 Interactions and sense of belonging in the transient place

Hall's (2012) study of Walworth Road in London suggests that materials within a transient environment, such as a street in the city, can carry the life realm forward through everyday, ordinary interaction. Hall states, '[l]ocal places, then, are about finding and fixing coordinates of familiarity to navigate everyday life' (:100). This references the available space, where gathering, eating and even disagreement occur. Sennett, in the *Craftsman* (2008), examined workshops where tools, skill and creators communicate in processes other than those which end in a finished product (Lefebvre's 'Thing'). Sennett argues that '[w]orkshops present and past have glued people together through work rituals, whether these are a shared cup of tea or the urban parade; through mentoring, and through face to face sharing of information' (2008:73).

Hall and Sennett both describe activated landscapes similar to the ones examined by this research, as emerging in the interactions between different elements, with materials and the activities becoming, re-imagining and re-creating space through knowledge generation and transmission and sense of ownership. This research connects this notion of *the workshop* with the notion of the intangibility of heritage, heritage as a process, which this research further links with the work of Jane Bennett (2010), as focusing on the liveliness of materials and their agency with respect to creating change in the transient place of the activated landscape. Bennett's work is discussed, below, in Sections 2.4.12 and 2.4.13 of this chapter.

In understanding the place and the landscape, it is important to recognise that all entities involved in their ecological environment are altered and shaped by the matter and the motions in it (Thrift, 2004).

2.4.11 The taskscape and materiality

Thus, the heritage landscape embodies the affectual relationships that activities and materials in 'correspondence' (Ingold, 2002) occupy which implies its incompleteness and its transiency, a notion supported by previous studies.

Smith, for example, from a heritage studies point of view, argues that 'how that past is understood validates or not a sense of place' (2006: 80). As such there is diversity with respect to any sense of belonging and feelings

of ownership for a place in the everyday life realm. Additional to the human element in the life realm, the non-human and the more-than-representational considerations (Lorimel, 2005) in the heritage landscape contribute to the complexity of the realm where decision making powers operate. Ingold argues for interactions, with respect to the realm of everyday encounters and 'meshwork' (Ingold, 2012: 435), leading to 'a focus on the active materials that compose the lifeworld' (Ingold, 2012: 429). This argument holds for the heritage landscape: as, in it, we witness the making of each other, of materials, and of the ones who occupy it, and space. Ingold considers the nature of materials and their role in contemporary urban places, recognising that materials cannot be categorised because their meaning changes according to what they were or are involved in, '[t]o understand materials is to be able to tell their histories' (Ingold, 2012: 434). This notion is also connected to the generation of knowledge in an environment, such as a workshop: what and how and who uses the tools, performs the craft and the previous experiences they have, determines how the knowledge will be generated. Thus, previous studies support the consideration of human and non-human affectual impact on the heritage landscape, as being transient in terms of meaning because it is bound to the activities and interactions that take place within it. When Ingold and Lorimel support transiency of the landscape, concrete categorisation, and consequently homogeneous characterisation of a place through place-making, become arbitrary and connote hegemonic attitudes to monumentality (Harrison, 2013).

Furthermore, Ingold (2000, 2007, 2012) has examined transiency of landscapes, as underpinned by the role of 'making'. The ongoing, always unfinished, transformation as to any state of place is acknowledged by Ingold's 'taskscape' (2000), situating this within contexts of anthropology, human activity and nature interacting in the one environment: 'the landscape is never complete [...] it is perpetually under construction' (2007:7).

Departing from the notions of in-between states with respect to natural and cultural landscapes and how combined approaches hold out potential for nuanced modalities of heritage, Harrison proposes the 'dialogical model in which heritage is seen as emerging from the relationship between people, objects, places and practices' (Harrison, 2013: 4). Carter et al. (2011) argue that objects are powerful means towards building an understanding of a place '[they] are understood as minor "actants" in the city yet microcosms that contain the whole city and are witnesses to the forces, wills, relations, subjectivities and power that make it up' (:7).

In the urban life realm, the *city*, as Stevenson describes it, has been discussed in parallel with *nature*, and studies other than Lefebvre's have suggested that they are both manifestations of the same realm, with

different representations (Ingold, 2011; Frisby, 2007; Cronon 1996; Stevenson, 2013; Treib, 2009). These authors have argued that the environment that we act upon and inside is manifested as both the natural and the urban but have pointed out that both are places that have been shaped, altered, developed and evolved through interactions with the human element, considered as an aspect of them, not separate from them. 'This transiency, calls to embrace the "dwelling perspective", according to which the landscape is constituted as an enduring record of the lives and works of past generations who have dwelt within it [and] have left there something of themselves' (Ingold, 2011: 189).

Ingold, thus, conceptualises a 'taskscape' as a transient scape, through emphasising that the processes creating landscapes are perpetually in motion, and that a *cultural/natural landscape* is defined by the actions that have happened in it, the entanglements of the human and the non-human elements, and is always unfinished or incomplete, rather than definite and absolute. Accepting this notion in thinking about the landscape, and in particular, the heritage landscape, acknowledges that knowledge about places is not absolute, but relational, thus hierarchical knowledge which influences decision-making on how the urban space should be formed, is challenged.

2.4.12 Thinking and knowing with water in the transient heritage place of the waterways.

Ingold's studies belong to a school of thought that challenges anthropocentric attitudes to knowledge production, and this research develops from this position in order to theorise the livescape.

Activating the transient heritage landscape exposes *muted knowledges*; knowledges, like landscapes, are understood in terms of practice (Santamarina and Beltram, 2016). Graham *et al* put emphasis on the transient nature of heritage perception by the locality 'one of the most challenging issues here is to ascertain how people understand the "historic environment" or "heritage", how they value it, and how such values are shaped by official bodies such as councils and heritage organisations', as this alters according to activity, events or individual circumstances (Graham et al, 2009:3).

Considering the heritage of the post-industrial landscape of Glasgow, and particularly the historic waterways, past research suggests that the contestation emerges in the transient place, what Thrift calls 'a different model of what thinking is', taking into consideration that the natural/cultural environment where heritage is processed is composed of interactions of responsive elements (Thrift, 2004 :60).

This leads this review to a body of literature on the ontologies of vitality and neo-materialism (Haraway, 1988; Greco, 2005; Braidotti, 2019; Neimanis, 2012, 2017; Bennett, 2010) which is concerned with scientific approaches to the landscape, in terms of understanding, knowledge production, acknowledging and management, all of which also bear economic implications that affect the place (Greco, 2005:24). In this study theories of vitality, neo materialism and post humanism are considered as being of significance, as the role of human and non-human elements and the on-going development of a place are core concepts in the conceptualisation of the livescape. Unfortunately, there is no space for exploring the economic and scientific implications of engagement further in this study.

Previous studies suggesting an alternative way of thinking, *with* the place rather than *of* the place propose different approaches to understanding knowledge, which this study acknowledges as contested in the transient heritage waterscape. 'I have been wondering if I think with water rather than about it [...] if I invite water to be a collaborator or an interlocutor in how I imagine or theorize the world, might I also treat water better? Might the concepts and theories I develop also help bring water out of the mute, passive background to which it is too often relegated?' (Neimanis, 2017: 52). Both Neimanis (2017) and Thrift (2004) discuss the politics that are guided by the nature of *thinking* and by *muted knowledge*. Thus, with respect to political decisions impacting on the alteration of and agency in the heritage and transient environment, Vallerani (2018: 10), specifically speaking of post-industrial waterways, calls for a 'hydraulic humanism' and 'participating consciousness', based on the local past experiences with knowledge of the place.

The interactions between the different elements of place, the transient locality, inform the *vitality* of the landscape— 'I realised that the capacity of these bodies was not restricted to a passive "intractability" but also included the ability to make things happen' (Bennett, 2010: 5), implying the power of objects to affect change. Materiality and interactions re-create the heritage landscape collaboratively, 'an actant, never really acts alone' (Bennett, 2010 :21), as the historic environment is part of the life realm and not abstract.

Thus, these previous studies suggest that the altered and transient heritage place activates the processual notion of heritage, and at the same time challenges *ownership of knowledge* in the heritage landscape. The literature discussed here argues for a change in thinking about the transient landscape (which is not final but in flux thus are the knowledges it contains) and for the acknowledgement of the affectual rigour of the interactors in it (Berg, 2004; Neimanis, 2012), suggesting that knowledge construction, regulation and

consequently ownership, implicate the activity and the agency of the heritage process. If we acknowledge that things in the heritage landscape, other than human, have power to affect what we know about the place, then imposing anthropocentric knowledges to shape urban landscapes' future, questions hegemonic attitudes towards urban planning.

2.4.13 Vitality in the transient heritage place.

Bennett (2010: 2) takes the argument further when she argues for '[t]he active role of non-human material in public life' and she introduces the *politically active role of matter* in the life realm. The political implications are that the power of materials is affectual to activity in the landscape and therefore such thinking suggests that humans can't be *ontologically central* in the world, as the 'vitality of matter' that humans consist of, come from frictions in the landscape (Bennett, 2010: :11). In fact, the activities of humans and non-humans engaging within an environment are part of that environment/locality, and the locality is part of the activity. An exemplar of this is the locality of a workshop where Sennett describes knowledge by using sharp tools 'in craftwork identification has a sharp point' (Sennett, 2008: 221). There is a cyclical or symbiotic relationship between knowledge and heritage in the transient place, a perpetual state of flux (Ingold, 2000; 2012), which excludes absolutism in knowledge, and consequently hegemonic attitudes in the place.

Thus, it is understood that the heritage process provides a platform and space for interactions, in the heritage locality, and this process 'is dissonant' (Smith, 2006: 82). Bennett argues that the political capacity of materials is based on the human inability to fully understand and control the world. With reference to this research study's landscape, the waterscape, the water as element opens deliberations about authorised/unauthorised knowledge. Knowledge, previous studies suggest, in transiency, is perceived as 'stable' and 'real' (Harvey, 2015), even though it derives from 'a temporary constellation of connectivity' (Harvey, 2015: 589). The post-industrial heritage of the waterways that this research examines is live matter, fluid and in an ever-changing state. Waterscapes, like all natural environments, are unpredictable, affectual and unsettling landscapes (Neimanis, 2012; Keating et al., 2012) and at the same time through human bodily functions, activity and needs, they are connected in a myriad of ways to the physical world – through sewages, drainage systems, rain, fish, vegetation living in rivers and canals (Neimanis, 2012: 54).

Ingold describes the transiency of the landscape as a 'mesh' (Ingold, 2012) of active and radiant matter, and as such casts doubt on authoritative knowledge and agency, outside of everyday interactions, and instead Ingold wonders if the way to *learn is by doing* (Ingold, 2007:3). I agree with Ingold's statement, and I based this research on this premise: to engage with heritage one needs to know it and to know it is by doing it.

Here Ingold's comments have an affinity with the thoughts of Smith when she explores the notion that all heritage is intangible, 'the idea of heritage not so much as a "thing", but as a cultural and social process' engaged with the present (2006:2). This review suggests that heritage is intangible and transient and thus *unknowable* and consequently, *un-ownable*.

At this point, this study connects previous research into the concept of *un-ownability* (of the heritage place) with those on the *publicness* of urban space. Varna and Tiesdall's (2010: 581) 'meta dimensions' problematise the role of AHD in place-making. In the instance of urban and post-industrial heritage landscape, there is tangible and intangible matter that generates belonging, doing so in ways that are distanced from authoritative and hierarchical understandings. Heritage's intangibility and locality's transiency entail those vulnerable aspects that could actually matter deeply to people, such as their familiarity or complex emotional (and often unknown) relationships that pertain to what is understood as 'the fluvial sense of place' (Vallerani and Vinsentin, 2018:10).

Being and experiencing familiarity as a continuum of publicness in the landscape, is not homogenous and is affected by empirical knowledge and preconceived ideas, through hegemonic attitudes, of what is recognisable as familiar, as our engagement with the world is always situated as taking place from a point of view, and it is connected to power. Thus, this literature review has shown that it is impossible to exhaust the description of any place or any object. In this sense experience is always unfinished, inherently incomplete and ambiguous (Tilley, 2006:27). Incomplete experiences and transiency of the heritage landscape's locality carry a sense of incompleteness and in-betweenness.

2.4.14 Transient landscapes of liminality.

Urban fluvial and transient environments bear a sense of liminality with respect to the in-betweenness of their existence, which extends to affectual ontological conditions of dwelling and safety (Vallerani, 2018; Wylie, 2007; Gillick and Ivett, 2018). As the literature suggests, the heritage waterways, in their *matter* and

transiency are dissonant, with emerged *political* power through their interactions, however their localities have been developed within the cultural *strategic landscapes* of cities.

As mentioned previously in the literature on the cultural city, situated between the arbitrary dichotomy of natural and cultural urban environments, the liminal places of the waterways, occupy and contain heritage values that are highly prioritised with respect to the current trend of urban regeneration (Kinder, 2015; Vallerani and Vinsentin, 2018).

Liminal places embed transiency, and they are understood as being places of uncertainty and existing in-between the familiar and the unfamiliar. These localities are important to explore, given that liminality, as this study will argue, is an in-between (sometimes precarious) state, characteristic of the environments of the waterways. From an analytical standpoint therefore, liminality, as it has been examined in previous studies, presents an interesting element for analysis as not just being in-between nature and urban in its fabric, but in addition manifesting elements of anxiety in its uncanniness. Downey, Kinane and Parker (2016), through the collection of essays they edited, which apply interdisciplinary approaches to examination, investigate the ubiquitous notion of liminality and how it is applicable regarding many different cultural manifestations. This study supports the statement of Downey *et al* that liminality is concerned with socio-political change (2016), that by 'occupying the liminal threshold allows for generative possibilities of new ideas, forms and states of being' (Miller, 2017:2).

Liminality in the transient heritage landscape, such as in urban and inland waterways, implies that the place occupants exist in a state of recurrent change. It is transient, as the uses of the landscape and its perception by the locality are in process – and this notion relates to familiarity of the place. Being there and experiencing in the heritage place links to *proximity*, which similarly contains a sense of uncertainty and insecurity. The liminal state of *co-existing with water* poses a tension of knowledge in relation to place-making; water connotes danger if one knows little about how to *be with it*. The perception of a locality's inhabitants about the waterways as locality (blue spaces) alter and adjust, and they are linked to transiency, and, as mentioned earlier, issues concerning access to services and resources (Vallerani, 2018; Wylie, 2007; Gillick and Ivett, 2018). The pluralities that communities face in contemporary cities, with ethnicity, gender, sexuality and economic alterations to society dominating the cultural landscape, also create a liminal environment; Downey *et al* optimistically suggest that 'liminality, becomes not a source of alienation but a communally shared

experience' (Downey et al., 2016: 8), and in this study I examine the collective role of liminality and its effect on the locality.

In this view, the notion of liminality poses a state of being that could be interpreted as a space where new actions could take place. One could point out here that liminality and the breaking down of borders could possibly pose issues that involve alienation and fear, rather than having a positive impact, with respect to urban living. Nevertheless, the political dimensions of liminality, if applied to the areas of Glasgow around the waterways that exist in and around the city, present an interesting context within which individual agency could be examined: 'to speak of space was thus to speak of how space was occupied- and by whom-and the ways in which space in turn affected and determined the behaviour of those occupied it, passed through it, and interacted with it' (Downey et al., 2016:10). One could observe here that the fading of boundaries and breaking down of structure in societal situations, due to new developments such as migration and climate change, have emphasised the idea of the very schema of urban contemporary communities: collectively fragmented 'in the perpetual in-between' (Downey et al., 2016:13)

With reference to the body of literature that examines the philosophical dimensions of the transient heritage landscape, as liminal and incomplete, and its relationship with knowledge which invokes agency, I will juxtapose previous studies on the everyday life and familiarity of a place, forming dissonance (Smith, 2006).

Figure 5: Liminality in relation to the transient locality

Liminality as it is underpinned in this research, is the notion of in-betweenness in the ever-changing environment of the post-industrial waterways through place-making processes. This diagram puts together all the elements that together characterise the locality as liminal.

2.4.15 *The heritage livescape and the transiency of the everyday realm*

In the literature on *the everyday* (De Certeau, 1984; Thompson, 2013; Hall, 2012; Bennett, 2005; Courpasson, 2017; Inglis, 2005; Ronneberger, 2008; Highmore, 2002), the in-betweenness of a place is revealed by everyday rituals, thus, in the post-industrial urban transient landscape, the locality's identity derives from its activation in the everyday realm. De Certeau, analysing everyday life rituals that are divided between the time of producing and the time of recreation, points out the transiency of the heritage locality that obscures the two. '[T]he dividing line no longer falls between work and leisure. These two areas of activity flow together', as culture became a tactic for economic growth in the urban environment, the locality's use of the place passes between cultural production to consumption continuously through activating the place. The heritage process (Smith, 2006) masks a production process with robust components, 'fictions of surprise ('the event'), of truth ('information') or communication ('promotion')' (De Certeau, 1984: 29).

Thus, in the cultural city, even leisure activities provide a structured existential reality for the individual. Place-making in urban renewal generates a cultural ontological landscape where all activity is regulated by the forces of *performance*, creating contestation in the landscape that is related to engagement (Smith, 2006). In this study, there is insufficient space to further explore the notion of performance in participation (of heritage). Rather, participation will be examined as an activation tool. De Certeau calls for the process of participation in activity through the expression of individuality, by avoiding authorised direction, such as 'poaching' or using 'illicit' methods to escape agency.

There is relevant literature on alternative ways of engaging with the heritage landscape within the everyday.

With reference to the concept of *perspective*, understood as the point of view of the agency that can see everything, city dwellers are the *walkers* according to De Certeau and they define their own lexicon via the performative act of walking, as they become the *writers* of a *text*, 'an urban text they write without being able to read it' (1988:93). De Certeau implies that the practices of the everyday cannot be seen, as they are invisible and undetected and continues by exploring the notion of *passing by*, a *placeless* and *purposeless* activity. This point is focal to this study, which seeks to examine the ways the transient place of the urban waterways is experienced in the everyday realm, rather than through the mechanisms of cultural production.

Thus, according to De Certeau's study, *passing by* represents the places that are not there. This non-place situation is an urban phenomenon, as it disrupts, is a rupture of the certain place of work, leisure and creation of place-making that dominates urban living. De Certeau argues that the non-significant space, the unseen, and the practices that underpin it, appears over time, but is not *apparent* as an event. The boundaries of individual *language* of expression break down in the gaps of everyday practice, between the placeless and the *purposed* activities.

De Certeau's analysis of the possibilities of *urban language* determining space, is important to this research as it applies to issues concerning behaviour within urban planned routes, as extended to encompass water routes. De Certeau, in discussing the significance of politically charged objects and activities with respect to defining spaces by increasing both the space and the meanings it holds, refers to the significance of an object from film: 'Charlie Chaplin multiplies the possibilities of his cane: he does other things with the same thing and he goes beyond the limits that the determinants of the object set on its utilization' (:98). In the same way, the walker transforms each spatial signifier into something else.

De Certeau's notion of dissonance through actions of the everyday, and interactions with materials in the transient urban landscape is central to the analysis of the city inhabitants' behaviour, which relates to this research study's articulation of the available capacities for performative changes. Possible margins and gaps available for activity and activism in the urban cultural landscape, as the place is 'lived', ' "subjectivity" is already linked to the absences that structures its existence and makes it "be there" ' (De Certeau, 1988 :109).

De Certeau's analysis of the place that gets rejected by the *made place* signifies the urge to observe what is beneath the surface of the cultural urban environment, specifically with respect to the approach through which regeneration and the new service economy has made it transient by altering objects, buildings and localities in which urban communities live.

In another study of everyday life, David Courpasson (2017), examines the theory of the everyday from the perspective of the working place. In this research, and with the cultural waterways landscape in focus, even charitable activity depends on leisure and the commodification of the waterways through place-making. As in De Certeau, Courpasson also observes that the borders between leisure and work environments have been blurred; employment in the tourist industry, with heritage at the forefront of this, creates gaps – in the form of *absent spaces*.

In everyday activity, according to Courpasson, lies the truth of the existence of the city dweller '[t]he study of everyday life started from the premise that understanding people's real lives involves analysing their experiences in their *natural* context that is to say, where they accomplish things and deal with the hard matter(s) of actual existence' (Courpasson, 2017: 844). The transient environment that urban renewal established through place-making and through the cultural economy strategies, the absent spaces, obscure the observation of the everyday life, as interactions and their locality became the *new natural* context.

2.4.16 Activation, engagement, and the transient, post-industrial heritage landscape

A body of literature exists which covers a range of studies that incorporate work in architecture, art and archaeology, and that body of work examines participation and engagement of local communities in relation to sense of ownership in the transient, social space (Fine, 2010; Flinn, 2011; Jackson, 2011; Leeson, 2018; Gillick and Ivett, 2018; Grauer, 2019). Activation of the heritage landscape is interacting and engaging and creates links between human and non-human elements. An exemplar of this interaction, as mentioned in section 2.4.13, is the setting of a workshop (Sennett, 2008), with human and non-human elements and actions and part of the everyday life. Participation in the workshop is a collective activity in the locality and the activity grants the locality ownership, as during the activation (participation) where participants, objects, places and skills interact in the place.

The transient heritage environment has shifted from an urban landscape of production of goods to an environment of service provision (Hutton, 2016; Harvey, 2012), and scholars such as Bauman (2001) and Sennett(2008) have examined activation in the transient urban places, where processes of place-making take place. The argument is that in these alteration processes of the urban landscape and the attendant strategic change of the urban fabric, so the development of work and production modes also change, including processes of alienation with respect to the *craft mentality* of earlier models of society based on manual labour. In the industrial period, where *craft mentality* was dominant, approval and *control* by the wider community environment worked as a mechanism of regulation (Bauman, 2001:26). Community gatherings, such as festivals, carnivals and fayres, were part of everyday life at a time when industrial urban places provided the livelihoods of localities. In the post-industrial transient and heritage environment celebratory events acquire a visitor attraction character (Baillie et al., 2010; Liu and Lin, 2011), are part of the place-making process, as they assign character to the place through its activation, and they are regulated by institutions with decision making

powers. Thus, the transition from the community of craftsmanship of the industrial past to the regulated service industries and offices, led to a more 'engaged' model of regulation and control in the post-industrial heritage landscape. Transiency occurred when the 'natural understanding' within a workshop's parameters based on craftsmanship was replaced by one-size-fits-all regulatory habits (Bauman, 2001: 34).

Studies have suggested that this paradigm shift in terms of engaging with the everyday life affects the celebratory culture in the heritage post-industrial environment. In the transient place, mechanisation and the organised production of events, freed from the ties of close community control, have resulted in the creation of a routine (Lefebvre, 2014; De Certeau, 1984) as part of the everyday life, which leads to the politicisation of the disruption of that routine, by acts of non-compliance (Courpasson, 2017).

3. What the conceptualisation of the livescape contributes to literature

This review of the relevant existing literature suggests that the heritage landscape and its locality is identified as transient, due to its binary characterisation as natural/cultural, tangible /intangible, and liminal.

Furthermore, literature suggests that transiency in the heritage place occurs when hegemonic attitudes involved with urban regeneration lead anthropocentric understandings of the life realm, by characterising, organising and regulating heritage environments in cities. In previous studies, transiency is linked to knowledge formation and its hierarchies that holds the decision making in the renewed urban heritage environment, and it has been conceptualised through this literature review by the way it weaves through *locality* and *place-making*, and transiency being the common element affecting the heritage place.

This PhD research, developing from these notions of transiency, situates the tensions that derive from the engagement that takes place in the locality, and which conceptualise the notion of the activated and contested heritage livescape. Knowledge, and particularly AHD, as tension in the activated livescape, generates hierarchies that influence engagement with heritage, and these hierarchies are represented by authorised discourses (Smith, 2006; Harrison, 2013; Santamarina and Beltran, 2016). Authorised knowledge is a driving force of strategic decisions that lead to place-making 'scaling knowledge being produced in specific places' (Berg, 2004: 554) and thus, knowledge generation relates to the geographic context. Although considerations of national geography prevail in the heritagization of a place and in place-making processes (Johnson, 1995),

this literature review has focused on studies of engagement with heritage in the *transient urban place*, as shaped by local knowledge (Santamarina and Beltran, 2009).

Transiency works as a catalyst with respect to local heritage practice in relation to knowledge, because, either it is blended or unnoticed in the practice of the everyday life, or it has no direct relevance to the *historicity of the place* for the communities who live in it (Grydehøj, 2010), such as migrant communities. Thus, further research is needed to examine participation in the urban heritage space through the activated livescape, by alternative activations to those of AHD and place-making processes. This will contribute to knowledge on marginalisation in the heritage urban landscape, specifically with respect to sense of ownership of knowledge and consequently empowerment, which leads to feelings of belonging and agency in the locality.

Transiency, as tension, was covered in this literature review from two points of view: through communities in transit and through the transient landscape that place-making creates. With respect to place-making and the sense for belonging, transiency and the hierarchical way knowledge is applied within the heritage space are not only related to the 'exotic Other', but they also relate to the notion of 'heritage from below' (Robertson, 2012). Drawn by Robertson's place identity analysis of 'the landscape of activity' (ibid.: 2), going back to Ingold's taskscape, therefore, the study of the activated livescape could fill gaps in the study of spatial justice in the heritage and urban environment.

Hoflehner and Zimmermann (2018), in their examination of community participation, specifically suggest that diverse modes of participation, such as Urban Labs, can contribute to resolving the tensions that communities face in a regenerated and transient urban environment, and that such tensions shape the way communities perceive themselves (:219-220).

Conversely, transiency also depicts itself as privilege, with respect to that section of community which has the means to extensively travel and thus be global. The 'global elite' and their 'practices', indirectly contribute to the tense environment. Bauman, in discussing the 'new' social body, refers to them as the 'cosmopolitans' and the 'culturalists', the members of communities who belong to the educated and well-travelled elite, and suggests that, often, this community holds the power to influence policy through influencing what is considered authorised knowledge (Bauman, 2001 :61). This research on the activated livescape contributes theoretically through its conceptualisation of the locality in the heritage landscape.

Thus, the tension of what is known relates to *familiarity*, originates from transiency, as variability with respect to the local community factor is considered in the regenerated urban environment - in this study, the post-industrial transient place. The transient place of the place-making process connotes *un-familiarity*, as it has been presented in the literature (Mooney, 2004; Muatt, 2015; Busiek and Juul, 2008; Diamond, 2010), in the form of alienation and exclusion from engagement.

The familiarity that derives from being and participating in the everyday life challenges hierarchical ontologies of the heritage landscape, as being outside the mundanity of life, as moving into a specialised dominion of *heritage* (Zhu, 2018). The literature supports this heritage practice, through the notion of the altered regenerated urban place, which manifests via place-making processes and via the established and authorised heritage discourse outlets, such as museums and cultural organisations safeguarding heritage (Smith, 2006; Crooke, 2010, 2011). Here, notions of monumentality and memory in the heritage urban environment, and the role of the locality, enter the discussion, as post-industrial heritage landscapes are large-scale monuments in need of preservation and care. Thus, place-making processes based on the heritagization of neighbourhoods and taking place in spaces familiar to local communities, transform familiarity of places by making them culturally attractive (Pacione, 2009: 156; Hutton, 2016: 331). Thus, the concept of the activated livescape contributes to an existing gap in literature by providing a model of engagement and participation in heritage that exposes barriers to familiarity, and knowledge generation.

Finally, the triptych of tensions: knowledge, transiency, and familiarity in the urban heritage environment, expose the deficit of contemporary authorised knowledge as 'not a knowledge itself, but the unthought, tacit assumption of all leading-to-knowledge thinking' (Bauman, 2001: 124).

4. Conclusion

In this research study I investigate the participation of local communities that occupy the environment of the post-industrial cultural landscape in and around Glasgow, focusing on the heritage assets of those environments, and the ways this engagement informs the heritage process. In this review of the relevant existing literature, I have presented theorisation with respect to the contested and activated livescape, as a place in a transient state, ever changing and incomplete.

I first discussed the theorisation concerning notions of transiency in the heritage landscape, as shaped by place-making – a process of preserving and utilising memory and monumentality in the landscape. I discussed discourses on the culture/nature binary paradigm with respect to heritage landscapes, and how this binary affects understandings of urban heritage. Furthermore, I discussed the literature concerning the way localities and their communities develop through empirically engaging with the historicity of a place, in terms of activities and materiality – using the example of Ingold’s taskscape. I also discussed the transient heritage environment through theories of vitality of materials and neo-materialistic approaches to knowledge and agency – focusing on what makes a place. I also examined literature that focused on the tensions with respect to the changing environment of the post-industrial space, and on experiences of mobilisation (migration and multiculturalism). Developing from Lefebvre’s (1991) lived space, as opposed to “abstract” and “perceived” space, I emphasised the importance of this conceptualisation as providing the foundation for the examination of the environment studied, specifically, as to the dynamics that create space.

Through the review I presented previous studies that argued how alternative approaches to knowledge affect the ways in which those in the locality feel about the spaces they occupy and their sense of familiarity with the transient place. I discussed dominant approaches to heritage in terms of the AHD and I presented examples from the literature with respect to how AHD has influenced the locality of heritage landscapes by underpinning place-making processes that alter the landscape. In the literature, processes of place-making are understood as mechanisms for regenerating public spaces that have been left derelict and abandoned (wasteland), where attitudes and understandings towards *waste* and what is considered *unsafe* affect decisions with respect to place-making in the heritage landscape.

Scholarship on theories of everyday life in cities discusses the duality of purposeful working life when compared to just *being* in the urban heritage space. Furthermore, local community’s heterogeneity, juxtaposed with the change from craft (as task) based society, has affected understandings of community and place. Liminality in the heritage urban place is experienced through complex, heterogeneous localities, whereas AHD is the dominant communicator of heritage for the changing heritage landscape, shaping engagement and understanding. The literature suggests that this stems from knowledge of the heritage landscape being regulated in terms of the AHD guidelines which pertain to place-making processes.

The concepts above, as brought out through this review of the literature, underpin the tensions that form the theorisation of the activated livescape, a landscape in transit.

This study on the notion of the livescape, was based on a theoretical framework that supports notions of cultural place-making and its effect on values in the locality, as taking place through the place-making process. The relevant literature informing this was selected from previous European and American studies, taking place within a specific geographic paradigm, over the last thirty years.

This research study's contribution to the theoretical discourse is the livescape as a mode of engagement with the heritage landscape, which is developed through the process that leads to the conceptualisation of the activated livescape.

Following on from this literature review, I proceed to discuss my specific study of transient local communities' participation with the post-industrial heritage in Glasgow, focusing on heritage assets and specifically two heritage landscapes-monuments, the river Clyde and the Forth and Clyde canal. Methodologically, I approach the study qualitatively, through a case study based on craft activities relating to the heritage of the two waterways, as a means of activation of the heritage landscape.

Chapter III Methodology and Methods

1. Introduction

With this research project I set out to plan, design and implement primary research into public engagement with the heritage of two post-industrial waterways in and around Glasgow. I was concerned more specifically to identify whether, and, if so, how, local communities engage with historic waterways of their locality. Further, I sought to analyse whether and how such engagement informed heritage process.

The research was based around two areas of activity: firstly, an ethnographic and auto-ethnographic case study embedded within a community heritage project based on the canal in and around Glasgow, that involved engagements with community groups in the locality, and secondly, collection of qualitative data through interviews with heritage and cultural organisations based on an urban river.

Leading on from this research I developed of a model of engagement with heritage that could potentially have applications beyond the scope of the case study.

The heritage activities of the case study, and the resultant model of engagement were based on the notion of activation of the heritage through active participation research in this case by being on and around the water, employing traditional craft.

In the study, which took place between October 2019 and February 2020, I focused on communities' participation and involvement with local post-industrial maritime heritage, and I explored how such participation informs heritage practices and development. Through this study I aimed to examine communities' participation with respect to a focus on heritage assets, that were both tangible (boats) and intangible (boating), in a transient environment. The study focuses on heritage situated in the everyday life realm (Hall, 2012), and thus, I proceeded with the study on the basis that both tangible and intangible heritage are intrinsic parts of the everyday (Smith and Akagawa, 2009). Furthermore, as in this study I examine the activation of the heritage landscape, I considered the activation of the heritage landscape occurring by both human and non-human elements, and that there are ways in which this activation contributes to the understanding of the use of social space and its publicness (Varna, 2016). Specifically, the examination focused on the heritage of the urban and inland post-industrial waterways, as the heritage landscape, a social space part of the everyday life realm (Inglis, 2005) of a transient locality.

This chapter has two main sections. The first main section explains the inquiry through the livescape, and discusses the ontology, epistemology and philosophical paradigm of the study. The second main section sets out the research process engaged in for the activated livescape, discusses the approach to the study, the strategy conceived and utilised for this, and the methods of collecting data. Further, this chapter presents the case study, including outlining the contexts of the case study, the sampling strategy and the data collection methods, as well as discussing the researcher's positionality in and to the case study. The study was based on a constructivist understanding as to the creation or generation of knowledge. This section also discusses the analytical methods utilised in the research, with an emphasis on the role of local knowledge in the inquiry.

2. The inquiry through the livescape

I based the study on an exploration and examination of the activated and contested heritage *livescape*. The livescape is a holistic conception of a heritage environment that encompasses its human and non-human elements, and the interactions between them, which take place in the realm of everyday life. The activated livescape is identified through *tensions* that are uncovered in the heritage environment. The contestation occurs in the locality of the live heritage environment, a transient place. I examined the contestation by drawing on a number of key concepts which I identify as common recurrences in the heritage locality: liminality, transiency, familiarity and agency. Liminality in the livescape presents as contestation through the altered urban environment, place-making processes, the impact of cultural city strategies, and binary understandings of the environment as cultural/natural (Harrison, 2013).

Liminality induces transiency (as it is mapped in Figure 5, in Chapter II, Section 2.4.14), which is examined, in the livescape as the local community, in two ways: transiency from the mobilisation of communities through forced migration or necessity, and transience as the experience of the transient urban space and the impact this has on communities. In some cases, these two forms of transiency overlap, with respect to both individuals and groups. Based on the presumption that there are under-represented, marginalised and voiceless community groups in the locality (these groups are considered to be transient), I observed and identified possible barriers that contribute to a lack of or non- engagement with the heritage environment. Another contested notion was knowledge, taking into consideration local knowledge and knowledge through activation (Lefebvre, 1991), which are juxtaposed to hierarchical knowledge, as emerging through and represented by authorised discourses (in the case of the heritage environment, the AHD (Smith, 2006)). Familiarity is examined through the notion of 'publicness' (Varna, 2010), the place-making process of altering space, the possibilities for engaging directly with the heritage environment, and the sense of ownership for the place. Furthermore, familiarity induces knowledge, and by following these contested notions through and across the examination, I observed the struggle for agency in the heritage place, through the activation. Agency in the livescape affects engagement with the heritage environment and allows for possibilities for participation in the post-industrial landscape.

2.1 Ontology and Epistemology of the livescape

2.1.1 *Ontology*

My starting point of this inquiry is the ontological assumption that heritage is a real thing. This assumption means that through this research I understand heritage to be part of the everyday life realm, which is life in the locality. My position assumes that heritage, being part of everyday life, is embedded in the locality and is shaped by the landscape. At the same time, the landscape, which is also embedded in the locality, is shaped, in its turn, by the heritage. I then proceed from the assumption that both heritage and its locality are part of the everyday life realm and that they are an always ongoing process (always unfinished or incomplete) and not fixed and definite entities. As such, I do not view heritage as something detached from the life of its locality and as if it were a finished product. On the contrary, ontologically, through the study, I regard heritage and its locality as processes that emerge through activation and contestation. Activating the heritage landscape entails employing actions and activities that involve groups of elements in the landscape, both tangible and intangible, and both human and non-human, as they interact with one another. It is these interactions which uncover contestations. As such, ontologically, the study assumes that the heritage process is predominately informed by authorised and hegemonic institutions and structures that influence what heritage is and how it should be practiced. However, the study also recognises heritage as being practiced by actions inside of everyday life, and that it is these actions which challenge and uncover, problematize, interactions and relations within the heritage locality. Thus, it is, that the activation of the heritage locality provokes contention, which informs the heritage process.

This means that I understand heritage as experienced and understood through activation of the heritage environment, which is embedded in the everyday life realm. Engagement with the everyday life realm encompasses hegemonic attitudes towards the ownership of the heritage locality. Given this, in this study, ownership of the locality, as reflected by hierarchical attitudes in the everyday realm operating in the development of the urban landscape, is ontologically challenged. I assume that the development of the locality and the heritage landscape, as dominated by hierarchical approaches such as place-making practices, affect the heritage process. Local authorities and urban regeneration projects, as promoted by the government and development agencies in charge of the planning of city networks, contribute to place-making. Hierarchical

attitudes (through official decision-making) in the locality and the alterations of the landscape provoke transiency. Thus, ontologically, I understand and acknowledge transiency, with respect to this study, in the sense of the transient heritage landscape and the transiency which local communities experience due to difficulty in accessing services and due to marginalisation. I view transiency not only as a reflection of deprivation, but as existing through the experience of occupying a transient locality. Therefore, ontologically, the study assumes the heritage transient locality to be a liminal place; a place in process and in-between states. The belief, here, is that the heritage locality and its monumentality are contested, and that this contestation has its basis in the liminality of the engagement with heritage. Importantly, in the study, I assume the liminality of the heritage landscape and the vitality of all elements in its locality. I do not view materials as inactive props that are accessories to anthropocentric attitudes to landscape. Ontologically, the study is founded upon the belief that non-human elements in the heritage landscape have a similar power with respect to activation to that possessed by the humans within the same landscape (Bennet, 2010). Materials and actions interact and are interwoven, enabling the emergence of the processual heritage landscape (transient). Therefore, hierarchical and anthropocentric attitudes to localities problematize the practice of heritage and its process.

2.1.2 Epistemology

Drawing from the ontological position outlined above, I approach the creation of knowledge as founded on understandings that knowledge is created in the everyday life and is connected to experiences of the life realm and, in this study, the experience of the landscape. As such, knowledge, like the locality, is not static, one directional, hierarchical, or created as an end-result. Furthermore, knowledge does not derive empirically, as having fixed parameters. On the contrary, knowledge is constructed through interactions that, in this study, occur between all the elements that constitute the heritage landscape. As the heritage landscape and the everyday realm have human and non-human elements, both tangible and intangible, that interact and create relationships and entanglements, these interactions are infinite, and knowledge production, like heritage, is a process that has no end and knowledge itself is thus always incomplete, unfinished, and relational.

Furthermore, given the ontological assumption of the study, the heritage locality is shaped by heritage and heritage is shaped by the locality, so knowledge created in the locality is shaped by the everyday life and the landscape's components. Moreover, the understanding that heritage and its locality are processual is based on

the underlying understanding that the creation of knowledge is processual and has no hierarchy. Knowledge is non-directional, and this study is created by the activated locality, in a holistic manner; by all the components that constitute the activity or action within that locality. The ontological assumption of the study is that sense of ownership of the heritage locality and landscape is challenged because it is based on creation and possession of knowledge in the locality. Possession of knowledge is achieved by familiarity with the locality and the heritage environment, which is achieved by proximity and ease of access. Therefore, knowledge of a place is acquired through familiarity, which is linked to being and to activating the locality. Activation is reflected on a bodily and spatial scale, therefore knowledge in the heritage locality is created on a multi-scalar basis, without restrictions. Given this, this study assumes that knowledge is reflective and not only based on experiences of the body, as the body is restricted in understanding the heritage locality, which is an amalgamation of many elements – thus, an understanding of knowledge and its production that moves beyond anthropocentric attitudes. Having the human bodily experience as the main source of knowledge removes the vitality of materials and non-human elements in the heritage landscape that have agency that impacts activation. The assumption that the activation of the heritage locality provokes contestation that informs the heritage process, links with the assumption that contestation creates knowledge in the heritage locality by revealing problematic attitudes concerning how heritage should be practiced and how the locality should be activated. Therefore, authorised knowledge of heritage, as influencing participation and involvement with heritage in the locality, impacts negatively on the target of familiarity (Smith, 2006) with the heritage locality by placing barriers and controls, visible and invisible, in the way of interactions and activation, and consequently blocking opportunities for understanding through meaningful engagement and thus, the creation and sharing of knowledge.

This study's heritage locality is the regenerated urban post-industrial landscape that has undergone alterations for the creations of new places. These alterations are procedures that have been informed and shaped by authorised heritage knowledge, such as institutions that safeguard heritage, that does not reflect or take into account other knowledges which are embedded in the locality and that are created through interactions in the everyday, but are outside institutional control. The place-making process, therefore, creates gaps with respect to participation and reinforces the notion of liminality in the heritage locality, by blocking the sharing of knowledge. My assumption in this study is that the heritage and the regenerated locality bears liminality and

therefore transiency, as derived from these gaps in participation, through being in a changing locality. Activation reveals the gaps in engagement in the locality, by illustrating that hierarchical knowledge domination controls activation and therefore influences the creation of knowledge. Thus, the study's epistemological assumption is that transiency in the locality derives from place-making processes, which then impacts the ways in which knowledge is created and understood. Knowledge understanding, creation and sharing is linked to familiarity and a sense of ownership in the locality.

2.1.3 Methodological framework

I based the ontological and epistemological framework of this study on the notions of heritage as processual and the heritage locality as a landscape in flux. This framework speaks directly to an interpretivism paradigm of knowledge making, as then providing the methodological underpinning for the research. In interpretivism, knowledge is constructed in the life realm and is not static or an end result, an *object*. The interpretivism paradigm is evident in this study's understanding that the heritage landscape is a fluid environment where meaning is created through interactions between the elements that constitute it and processes. The regenerated post-industrial heritage landscape has undergone changes and alterations to its fabric and its social space, which have induced a sense of in-betweenness. The liminality of the heritage landscape and transiency in the locality affect the heritage process. Thus, an interpretivist understanding facilitates a broad exploration, through which the landscape is examined across different scales and intensities. Such an interpretivist understanding leaves room for movement and adaptability with respect to changes of context. Vitality in the heritage landscape is based on the understanding that knowledge deriving from the activation is not anthropocentric, hierarchical, nor based solely on corporeal experiences. At the same time, sense of ownership of the heritage locality is achieved through familiarity with the heritage locality, which is gained through proximity and knowledge of the heritage landscape. Activating the transient locality, which is dominated by authorised and hierarchical knowledge, uncovers problematic notions of participation with heritage, affecting both knowledge creation and the heritage process. This reflects the assumptions and understandings of the critical paradigm with respect to knowledge creation, facilitating critical exploration and reflection through problematizing social phenomena such as the agency of materials in the activation of the livescape. The above philosophical framework of the study guided the trajectory I followed in designing the research.

It is a main premise of the study, that heritage, the heritage landscape, and the knowledge that is created in it which influences participation, are all processual in nature. A process is something that is in continual flux, is not constant and never ceases developing, it is a 'a space of flows' (Castells, 1996: 406). Thus, the study had to be located within a philosophy of examination that reflected this premise, and this happened through the theorisation of *the activated and contested livescape* as a model of engagement. The livescape, in this study, is the heritage landscape, which is activated in order to uncover the tensions that manifest within and help create the heritage locality. Thus, activation is the catalyst that brings the landscape to life, and through which it becomes the livescape. In order to theorise the livescape, I need to set this theorisation within the paradigm that provides the foundation for the research.

2.2 A philosophy for the livescape as inquiry?

2.2.1 Constructivism and Interpretivism

The study is situated within the constructivist philosophical paradigm, and an interpretivism paradigm of knowledge production, '[i]nterpretivism argues that truth and knowledge are subjective, as well as culturally and historically situated, based on people's experiences and their understanding of them. Researchers can never be completely separate from their own values and beliefs, so these will inevitably inform the way in which they collect, interpret and analyse data' (Ryan, 2018: 8).

Interpretivism as a paradigm, according to Scotland (2012), allows myself as the researcher to blur the barriers between the role of the participant and the researcher. As I participated in the study and was not only an observer, the fellow participants became an intimate aspect of my reflections, many times influencing my thoughts through their interpretations and understanding as to meanings. I was not quite a 'participating observer', in terms of Whyte's (2012) terminology. My previous relationship with the canal boating society (including being a member of it), positioned me as directly within the study, as part of the group I was observing, thus breaking down barriers between researcher and researched. All the research participants possessed personal knowledge about the place they occupied, and I believed they were contributing to knowledge creation from a legitimate positioning within the heritage environment. This was not a place that I could occupy, entailing the need to incorporate the participants' understandings and interpretations as an aspect of my own critical reflexivity.

The dichotomy of natural and cultural landscape has been criticised in critical heritage studies (Harrison, 2015) and by other critically oriented scholarship, through making ‘use of the constructivist and sometimes the positivist perspective’ (Kühne, 2019:29). The heritage landscape in this study concerns the everyday life realm of the urban post-industrial waterways, an environment dominated by water (Gandy, 2018). This, in some respects, is a tangible environment, which could be studied within a positivist paradigm of knowledge production, as it consists of natural and scientifically measurable components – such as the water and engineering constructions (including boats and the canal itself). However, this inquiry examined the heritage locality, which encompasses both tangible and intangible elements, and the actions, interactions and entanglements that occur within it. The employment of the livescape as a method, to draw out and then consider the tensions generated by its activation, relies on a philosophical belief as to knowledge being subjective. The research took place in what was not a controlled research environment (Ryan, 2018) which could be subject to measurement as is necessary when working within a positivist paradigm – as positivism’s focal point is the ‘strictly scientific empiricist method designed to yield pure data and facts uninfluenced by human interpretation or bias’s (Saunders, 2009: 136). With respect to examining the intangibility and abstract notion of the heritage livescape, a positivist philosophical approach would have excluded important aspects such as affect, liminality and familiarity of the experienced heritage locality. The examination of the livescape therefore, calls for an interpretivist philosophy which allows for this kind of value-based research, as encompassing the ‘flux of processes, experiences and practices’ (Saunders, 2009: 136).

Furthermore, as the study of the activated heritage livescape is based on the cultivation of contestation, the study’s philosophical basis embraces the critical paradigm, as associated with critical theory (Asher, 2015). This research focus on tension and contestation was foundational for the study, given its objective of investigating and challenging the hierarchical knowledge ownership in the heritage livescape (Santamarina and Beltram, 2016; Smith, 2006). I, as the researcher, through reflexivity and the acknowledgment of my own positionality in relation to the knowledge hierarchy within the heritage environment, sought to provide an appropriate foundation for the study in terms of appropriately relevant literature.

Given the above, I drew on notions of ‘thinking with *water*’ and ‘knowability’ (Chen, MacLeod and Neimanis, 2017: 5, 8), which challenge hierarchical attitudes in knowledge production through a feminist and phenomenological critique. Setting the study within a critical theory field, supported the choice of

methodologies that expose knowledge dynamics within the live heritage landscape, including considerations of knowledge as connected with authorised institutions (heritage institutions that adapt AHD as explained in the literature review). Critical theory also examines practices that block participation and involvement with the heritage – ‘[c]ritical researchers have argued that culture has to be viewed as a domain of struggle where the production and transmission of knowledge is always a contested process’ (Kincheloe & McLaren, 2017: 288).

Although power structures in relation to meaning and knowledge production are also considerations of post-structuralism (Saunders et al., 2009: 142), the examination of the live heritage landscape concentrates on tensions-as-language for the representation of the observed phenomena. Interpretivism, post-positivism and critical theory are philosophies that underpin the observation and interpretation of phenomena that generate meaning, and they all relate to the study’s foundational research paradigm. Although the study follows the interpretivism philosophical approach, it also acknowledges the post-positivist approach (Ryan, 2015) which respects the subjectivity of the observer and acknowledges the contextual importance of the research.

2.2.2 Constructivist paradigm

The study was set within the constructivist paradigm, where truth (knowledge) derives from the parameters that influence that knowledge (as experiences), following a reflexive trajectory, whereby truth develops throughout the empirical process and through constant reflection upon that process (Charmaz, 2016). This study recognises that reflections do not happen only through me as the researcher or any of the academic community that enters the field for the purposes of observation, but rather involve the participants and their activated heritage environment. As the study problematizes hierarchical attitudes towards knowledge production, it explicitly rejects restricting the researcher’s analysis (production of knowledge) to the familiar parameters of the academic community (Hammersley, 2010).

Placing the study solely within authorised discussions in knowledge institutions based on a pre-determined model would restrict severely the efficacy of the research. Embeddedness within the realm of the everyday life of the participants was central to the study and thus my study approach developed as the project progressed, reflective of observations and interactions in the field. ‘In addition to linking critical inquiry to emancipation and transformation before inquiry, we can also emphasize developing it during the research process. An open-ended, emergent method fosters developing a critical stance’ (Charmaz, 2016: 4).

The study emphasised the importance of incorporating participants' analytical powers within considerations of the study design and the processes of analysis from the outset, thus harnessing the critical inquiry powers of the community involved. Knowledge is constructed jointly by the researched and the researcher, and this inter-subjectivity of knowledge co-production is acknowledged and drawn on in the study (Multani, 2020). According to Charmaz (2016: 3), critical inquiry begins with acknowledging issues of misalignment in the research field, such as injustice. The study examined tensions in the heritage landscape, specifically the generation of knowledge relations between the authorised heritage discourse (and the institutions that promote it) and the communities who use the landscape (Guzzini, 2013: 6).

Therefore, knowledge contributions directly from the field (interpretations) also contributed to the fluidity element of the study. According to Multani (2020: 8): 'No longer are the researcher and the researched separate'.

2.3 An approach for the livescape as inquiry

2.3.1 Qualitative approach and thoughts on the post-positivist paradigm

The study followed the qualitative approach to research (Denzin, 2017) for three reasons: (a) a qualitative research approach enabled me to view the study holistically and focus on flexible designs; (b) there were many variables that were hard to control in the research environments, which demanded a fluid approach, rather than rigid metricised, positivist aspects of a quantitative approach; and (c) overall the qualitative approach gave me the flexibility to adapt, change and develop the study according to participants' everyday lives and needs, as embedded in the everyday life realm (Bennett, 2015).

Firstly, in order to assess the heritage landscape, I conducted a Scoping Study in the localities of the FCC, involving community groups that had regular meetings in the areas I was interested in, that experience transiency. As the elements of participation that I was investigating (transiency, activation, familiarity) were not easily observable, it became clear early on, during the scoping study, that the research design had to enable me to be embedded in the research field (Merleau-Ponty, 2012) in order to derive data from first-hand experience and develop a closer relation with the participants and situations I needed to understand. Scoping studies are useful for testing the main study's design, and then informing adjustments and considerations with respect to sampling groups (Kim, 2011: 191). A presentation and analysis of the scoping study follows in the

Case Study chapter. Secondly, I was involved in the design, organisation and management of a community heritage project, CanalCraft, which became the basis of building the case study (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/the-case-study/>). Considerations of transiency, the results of the scoping study, and proximity to the research sites guided me in selecting participants as the sample groups (Reybold et al., 2013; Gentles et al., 2015) from within the heritage localities in focus. The case study design was informed by suggestions gathered during the scoping study, with insights recorded from participants, professionals working with local community groups and volunteers. Given this knowledge, my criteria for selecting actions for the participatory action research engaged in as central to the case study were based on practicality, availability of resources and of expertise, all of which were considerations scoped out during the scoping study.

2.3.2 Tensions in the livescape and the critical paradigm

The critically oriented field of cultural studies has a focus on questioning the underlying forces that exist within cultures in terms of power and agency (Saukko, 2003). Drawing on this field facilitates the challenging of preconceived ideas concerning culture and how culture manifests within any particular set of social contexts. This was of benefit to the research, given that the study's subject matter is primarily situated within the field of critical heritage studies, and that the study takes an explicitly critical approach in developing the livescape as model of inquiry; one which is underpinned by questions concerning nature and culture, liminality and the affectual impact of actions and materials within the heritage landscape (community and heritage). The multiple notions underlying the heritage landscape and its activation, along with the examination of transiency in a regenerated urban environment, demand such a pluralistic and procedural approach – 'multi-perspectival research aims to hold different perspectives in creative tension with one another' (Saukko, 2003: 32).

Consequently, a consideration of the blurred boundaries between knowledge acquisition through abstract and lived space (Lefebvre, 1991) are most relevant: the regenerated post-industrial landscape has become a ground where a re-imagined idea of how the city should look and feel has materialised through place-making processes, assisted by cultural strategies and in particular the role of the heritage sector (Harrison, 2013). Within these processes, the cultural city and the cultural class (Florida, 2003) have shaped attitudes towards the urban environment including through the specific ways they believe communities *ought* to experience the environment they occupy (Fainstein, 2013). Thus, the regenerated space has become a transient environment within which notions of re-invention and renewal have been the dominant force guiding and influencing

behaviours and actions. Participation in the transient space, as subject to such forces, takes specific forms that is powerfully shaped by these forces of change, consequently impacting on issue concerning knowledge and how it is created. This is because such knowledges are gained through the empirical space, through actions, interactions and embeddedness in the transient heritage environment, and specifically in the affectual and vital historic environment. More specifically, the liminality of the transient heritage space of the post-industrial waterways, and the affectual space as impacted in ways outlined by Lefebvre's critique of the lived space (Lefebvre, 1968), synthesise the empirical nature of knowledge within the field of this study.

Activation of the heritage livescape generates tensions, which are understood as forms of dissonance with respect to considerations of ownership and familiarity relating to the study's specific historic environment (Gray, 2018). Plurality in methodological approach within the livescape, allows for varied readings of observed dissonances. Thus, the contextual background of the local communities in the heritage landscapes, the locality, was examined utilising a range of different perspectives.

2.3.3 Positionality of the researcher

Considerations as to my own positionality within the study were reflected in both its design and execution. The choice as to research methods was informed by the model of reflexivity and positionality discussed by England (1994: 87), as arguing for the personal nature of fieldwork and the important role the background of the researcher plays in research processes. Collecting data is a dialectical process, a relationship between the researcher and the participants in the research, through which it is important that the voices of the participants are presented in ways that avoid replicating or creating 'patterns of domination' (England, 1994: 81). Such concerns resonate with the ontological position outlined, with respect to understanding and challenging the domination of knowledge that controls place-making processes by heritage experts and professionals who work in the locality of the historic environment.

There is a clear need, in such research processes, to consider the impact that the participants' actions have on the researcher: transient communities, in this instance, have affected my understanding, attitude and attribution of meaning with respect to places, situations and their wider contexts. Thus, the research is not static (a product) but a process (England, 1994: 85). This reflects the concept of the livescape as an ever-becoming life realm, one created by tensions within it and shaping it.

As explained in the literature review, the activated livescape exposes the liminality of both heritage and everyday life. In a similar manner, the activated livescape exposes the tensions of the in-between with respect to the researcher's world and that of the participants. With regard to concerns about appropriation and whether research can overcome the nature of what is often an unequal exercise, reflecting considerations of power and agency with respect to the researcher and the researched (England, 1994), the activated livescape model of inquiry opens up discussion on tensions that exist in the arbitrary space between heritage process and everyday life. This is the point, which England and Berg (2004) both speak to, concerning the validity of the researcher's worlds, which the livescape specifically aims to reveal 'the world between ourselves and the researched' (England, 1994: 86).

In the study, I positioned myself in multiple roles: the researcher, a member of one of the groups with whom I was conducting the research, an active volunteer, and an officer with a paid role in a publicly funded heritage community project. Thus, the researcher was also a consumer of, a practitioner with respect to, and a participant in heritage, in part through performing the same or similar acts as some of the research participants being observed within the environment of the research (England, 1994: 82).

Building close relationships with the sampling groups through inhabiting these multiple roles had varied effects and was, at times, difficult to manage (Gray, 2021: 626). The vulnerability of some of the research groups led to difficult relationship dynamics, given the need for maintaining a balance between trust and freedom of expression. On the other hand, possessing positions of control within the study, such as my position as the manager of the community heritage project, allowed for greater flexibility and adaptability for me as the researcher, without having to go through external levels of hierarchy.

I gained insights, with respect to perceptions as to possible interference with the analysis, which were noted. The possession of bias is an inevitable aspect of the everyday realm, indeed is inherent to being human, as is foregrounded by the critical paradigm framing the research. As such, I attempted to appropriately recognise, understand and acknowledge my own bias with respect to my observations of both my own and the participants' actions (Gray, 2021: 627). This point is significant, because the liminal state of the heritage locality was reflected in terms of transiency, understood as created through the changing heritage landscape and the knowledges of the communities that live in proximity to the heritage landscape. Transient landscapes, in the post-industrial space, are characterised by multiple levels of deprivation and difficulty in accessing

services (Gray, 2018). Collecting data, gained through inserting myself into these community settings, exposed me on an emotional and social level (Korstjens and Moser, 2017: 278). As someone who can afford to pay for the activities the participants had no easy access to, such as access to the river and the canal, I had to reflect on my privileges and my insights with respect to considerations of the barriers the research participants regularly faced to engagement. Given this, it was important for me to gather my evidence from a range of sources. For example, I considered the membership prices of boating clubs, the equipment someone would need to buy in order to participate that went beyond that which the clubs provided for members, the necessary time for dedicating to the activity when no wage was involved, as well as other potential barriers, such as the need of a car. I also considered the attitude of boating clubs towards membership and the capacities necessary for non-boating groups to engage with boating activities. Further, I reflected on the fact that communities that face multiple deprivation struggle to find either the time or the resources that it is necessary to dedicate for engagement in boating activities, especially when they have to depend on cars to access the water with boats (hence the need for better access to slipways). As a boater myself I have all the above barriers removed, thus I entered the study from a very privileged position.

The study delved deep into the heritage landscape of the waterways in Glasgow, observing the affect exposed by the activation of heritage when engagement took place. Across a variety of data collection methods, there were certain important considerations.

Firstly, the positionality of the researcher before, during, and after the research. Coming from a non-British, Mediterranean background, and being a female from an older demographic who didn't grow up in the UK, positioned the researcher in the field in a variety of ways: the relationship of the researcher with the heritage landscape was not one of memory, although as a historian, it bore significance as a historic monument.

Secondly, the relationship of the researcher with the community in the heritage landscape was not homogeneous; while immigrant groups viewed the researcher as an equal and close to their circumstances in being a foreigner in the UK, amongst white, local and indigenous groups, they were viewed as an outsider wanting to find out about what they knew, a listener.

Thirdly, the relationships that I, as the researcher, had with the cultural organisations which resides within the heritage landscape of the study was illustrative of the richness as to the contradictions and hidden realities in the study's field. The organisations that were dominated by white, middle class, indigenous, male members

(FCCS and CMT), where the researcher already had an established working relationship that spanned over five years prior to the research, embraced the research as an opportunity for greater exposure to wider audiences, as they trusted the researcher due to their previous collaborations. The position of the researcher with the refugee group and the women's group were based on trust and comradeship, underpinned by the fact that the researcher is a both foreign and a woman. Previous collaborations in refugee projects with local organisations, facilitated the refugee group's involvement to the study. The Women's Centre (WC) had previously collaborated with Maryhill Integration Network (MIN) in integration projects and recognised the study as another opportunity for integration. The, younger, LGBTQI Youth Scotland (YS) group already knew the researcher and there was an already established trusted relationship in place.

Fourthly, I considered the relationship between the political and social positioning that I occupied as the researcher in the heritage landscape and my pre-conceived ideas about the results of the study and concerning the study as a whole. As an educated person in an Anglo-American education system and perceived as having a middle-class life, while possessing what would be considered a 'left' political orientation, my views, as the researcher, involved certain biases with respect to the demographics of the groups involved in the study. This acknowledgment necessitated the adoption of a critical reflexivity with respect to my positionality and political orientations across the research process, in particular with respect to the discursive and analytical aspects of the study.

Moreover, as I was embedded in the study's field through membership and belonging in the cultural organisations involved in the study, the validation of the results was considered and re-assessed through discursive methods with participants assisting in the research. This approach spoke strongly to the study's aim of identifying possibilities for future engagement within the community, through the recognition of the considerable pre-existing knowledge of those within the field of the inquiry (Nind et al., 2013: 9).

I acknowledged that a particular set of values guided the research (Macfarlane, 2010), and ensured there were opportunities to reflect on and consider their appropriateness across the research process. These values were communication; transparency; collaboration; commitment; respectfulness; bravery. Transparency, as the intentions of the researcher in terms of the ownership of the study and its outcomes when shared and reflected upon. Collaboration, as participants contributed to the insights in the design, running and analysis of the study. Commitment and lack of, provided insights revealing dynamics in the research field that situated

the study more accurately. Respectfulness translated in respect for everyone's position in the livescape, regardless of status. Finally bravery is linked to participation, noting the boldness of participating groups and individuals to try activating the livescape, even stepping outside their familiar space.

These values were reflected in the methodological approach, as focused on challenging hegemonic and hierarchical attitudes towards knowledge formation in the livescape through the breaking down of barriers between authorised knowledge and the knowledge required through familiarity with the locality, as emerging from the realm of everyday life. Therefore, the values I adopted in the livescape as a method of inquiry aided in the inclusion and position of the participants as equal to my position as the researcher. Participants involved in the study were considered as knowledge bearers with respect to the locality as they were familiar with the landscape. Such an understanding is what facilitated my assessment of the gaps and barriers with respect to familiarity, as emerging through the activation of the livescape.

3. A research process for the activated livescape

An action plan for the study was established in ways that reflected the research's philosophical paradigm – as explained earlier in this chapter, in section two and framed as based on the activated heritage livescape as a method of inquiry.

3.1 Collecting data from the activated livescape

The methodology of the activated heritage livescape was that of a qualitative study (Bryman et al., 2008; Macfarlane, 2010; Astalin, 2013), which drew on critical theory (Denzin, 2017) as the main approaches to research. The study was centrally a process of participatory action research (Marshall, 2001; Bradbury and Reason, 2003), with the methods used being forms of ethnographic and auto-ethnographic fieldwork (Atkinson et al., 2001; Brunt, 2001; Cook et al., 2019; Denshire, 2014) through which I collected the majority of the data during the case study (Hays, 2003; Flyvbjerg, 2011). The further method employed, as utilised for supplementary data collection, was that of semi-structured interviews (Keats, 2009).

Figure 6: Research framework for the livescape

As discussed in sections 2.2 of this chapter, the framework of the inquiry followed the principles of the philosophical acknowledgements of the interpretivist and constructivist paradigm, where the production of knowledge is constructed through activation and interactions. The methodological approach, therefore, was based on activation of the heritage environment, which is already contested. The contestation in the heritage landscape provoked the inquiry to use qualitative methods of data collection, such as case study, visual material collection and interviews. These methods were fluid and flexible to adopt to the fluidity and changeability of the heritage locality. The result was a body of data that consisted of a variety of interactions, objects, activities, and occurrences.

3.1.1 Activating the livescape (participatory action research)

Participatory action research (PAR) (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/participation/>), as a methodology, fitted well with the study's philosophical paradigm, and thus the need to situate the participant communities and groups at the core of the study, not as subjects to merely be observed, but as direct and participatory contributors of both previous and newly created knowledges (Bradbury and Reason, 2003: 156). The Portfolio Participation section is divided between participation in this research and participation of the community groups I worked with in various activities in their everyday engagement with the heritage environment. Thus, through a series of photos I have taken throughout my engagement with the groups and individuals in various events and activities, such as festivals and open days, I have illustrated the continuing engagement of certain communities with the waterways. In the first example (<https://elenakoumpouzi.com/participation/#fccs>), photographs show an FCCS volunteer activities: a canal cruise, volunteers restoring a lifeboat, and a volunteer washing the hull of the canal boat. In the second (<https://elenakoumpouzi.com/participation/#coracle>), we see the building of a coracle by volunteers in the Clydebuilt festival (September 2019) and the trial of the coracle in the river Clyde. In the third set of images (<https://elenakoumpouzi.com/participation/#moreparticipation>), we see volunteers servicing a canal boat, a volunteer addressing a heritage walk, public participation in using traditional tools, and volunteer litter picking on the canal. These photos are exemplars of *the being there* in the heritage locality, in the everyday.

I based the research model on participation in activities in the heritage locality (Pain and Francis, 2003: 47), thus, participation in the research, with respect to both the sample groups and myself as a direct participant,

was viewed as knowledge making practices, as well as a method of uncovering knowledge dynamics in the locality (Berg, 2004).

Considerations of participatory action research as the methodology informed my planning a set of activities designed to trigger responses which I observed and recorded in diaries of my actions, such as meetings, informal conversations, informal interviews and responses, towards the direction of the contested livescape. My own participation, alongside my first-hand experience of the contexts and activities, enabled me to observe the phenomenon closely and be sympathetic to the experience of the sample groups, as it was a *shared experience* (Denshire, 2014; Wells et al., 2020).

Forms of participatory action research served the study's philosophical and political aims and objectives of challenging knowledge hegemonies in a regenerated urban heritage landscape. Wells et al. (2020: 187) discuss the differences between experts and lay knowledge in the preservation of the historic environment, arguing that emphasis must be given to local expertise, given that this will reflect the needs of those in the locality. The methods of inquiry, as sitting within a PAR framing, enabled an approach designed to reveal tensions with respect to interactions in the heritage livescape. Following, I describe the stages of the case study, the main body of the research, supported by the body of data collected during the case study and showcased in the online Portfolio, and I am going to guide the reader through the stages by referring to the corresponding links, with explanations.

3.1.2 Case study

The holistic approach to, and of, the case study (Thomas, 2019: 2), as framed by its philosophical underpinning, enabled flexibility with respect to changing parameters. This was particularly important with respect to considerations of the notion of transiency in the activated livescape. This approach has certain limitations, which can problematically lead to over-generalisations, if the built-in flexibility in the study allows for such a range of changes such that the focus shifts and the depth of inquiry is consequently compromised (Thomas, 2019: 3).

Thus, I designed the case study (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/the-case-study/>) around the activation of the livescape (activities), focusing on participation in the locality, with the intention of ensuring that the research was both sufficiently flexible and responsive, but that it also maintained sufficient focus and depth of

inquiry to achieve the desired aims and objectives. The design focused on transiency, as framed in the philosophical underpinning and the place-making processes that induce transiency in the post-industrial heritage landscape. This means that my priorities for community participation focused on groups and localities that a) have been through place-making developments and b) potential participants experience transiency and have been affected negatively, either through marginalisation or through difficulties/improbability in engaging with heritage in their locality.

The case study model of research was chosen to allow a variety of methods to be used in order to adapt to different situations and facilitate the creation of theoretical outline-building (Lauckner et al., 2012). Specifically, the purposes of the research justified a 'revelatory' single-case study, in which opportunities are created for observations of phenomena that are otherwise hard to access (Yin, 2018: 50). A participatory action research methodology was thus central to inducing the desired interactions, specifically, the traditional crafts of boat-building and boating, which then provided the platform for exploring the post-industrial waterways' environment and engagements with it. Accessing the boating environment was improbable for the community groups I was looking to research, but it was an environment very familiar to me, as someone who occupies the waterways with small boats (canal boats, kayaks, canoes, rowing boats) frequently (more details about the researcher's background is located in the Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/the-researcher/>). Therefore, for the designing of the research it was rather convenient that I had myself as a subject for observation through auto-ethnography, someone with frequent engagement with the water, and at the same time members of community in the localities with almost no opportunities for this engagement, which I could observe by setting up opportunities through the case study.

Njie and Asimira (2014: 37) argue that 'the case study is necessitated by the specificity of the case under investigation which is informed by its boundedness'. As such, the case study in this research had a set of parameters that framed a focus on the studied environment and the 'ecosystem' of the research area. Ethnographic observations were targeted to provide answers to the research questions, thus setting the 'boundedness' of the case study. Participants had to find a specific place within their everyday surroundings, but outside their habitual processes, in the form of workshops, at a specific time during their ongoing activities/engagements through their clubs but with respect to an activity with which they had no previous experience, in the form of boat building. This kind of activation, although occurring within the everyday life

setting, is specifically designed to create engagements with new experiences, so as to study the tensions this made evident. The target of the case study was to embed participants in an activity that had the potential to become part of their everyday life (the workshop). There is a sub-section about the Workshop in the online Portfolio (<https://elenakoumpouzi.com/the-workshop/>), where through pictures of workshops from CanalCraft, the activation of the livescape is illustrated.

The research engaged in ethnographic observations, which positioned myself, as the researcher, within the research as a participant, not just an observer (Fielding, in Gilbert, 2001: 148). Embedded in the environment of the study, I was able to reflect on own experiences during the activation process. Experiencing things from the same positioning as a participant, along with the other participants, breaks down barriers with respect to 'authority' of the researcher and as to the sense of being an outside observer (Fielding, in Gilbert, 2001: 148-149). Reflecting on the study's philosophical underpinnings on authority and hierarchical attitudes in the livescape, the study adopted Thomas' (2019: 9) ideas about object and subject identification during the case study's design: as the objects of study are the locality (the places and the communities) and engagement, the subjects were understood as expertise in and of the locality through the experiences and interactions of the ones who activated the landscape (cultural organisations, participating groups, individuals, agencies) which worked as 'prisms' through which the objects emerged. Thus, interactions through activation create the platform where engagement and locality can be observed and studied, and where the heritage process emerges as observable too.

Forming relations through the practice of heritage presents both opportunities for and challenges to the researcher. This concerns opportunities to study the environment in depth through participation, an immersion in and through the participatory practice in ways that facilitate the identification of gaps and barriers that would likely remain unseen or unrecognised from an external point of view. There is, however, a danger of becoming overly emotionally involved with the environment and with the other people participating in the study, in ways that might compromise the observation process. This potential issue was mitigated through re-visiting and re-evaluating the observations at various points during the study's progression, as the researcher's own feelings towards the practice became established and mature. As an observer and a participant, I had to carefully step-out of my 'boater' role outside the case study. During the case study, I felt responsible for the research and the participants, and I tried to give them more opportunities to be on the

water and with the boats, as I felt that this was a new experience for them. This practice helped me keep distant from becoming too involved with my own engagement and knowledge, and let the participants make mistakes and take decisions regardless of my thoughts. Inevitably, direct engagement with the water offers a sense of familiarity with the environment, and this is a feeling acquired by me by being able to engage. It was interesting during the case study that as the observer in the field I had to reduce the feeling of familiarity, to let the participants have the space to 'discover' the same feeling without my experiences blocking it. Thus, the design of the case study had to shift repeatedly in its implementation and to be finely tuned in order to mitigate the nuances of the activation through participation.

The philosophical underpinnings with respect to the sense of ownership and agency in the heritage locality, posed the question of multi-scalar and multi-contextual needs for the study. The concepts of place-making and urban renewal for example, which set the backdrop and dominate the environment of the study areas, contextualised the study on one hand and on the other hand posed a challenge for approaching it. For this reason, I utilised different approaches in the research, and that was intended to enable the collection of a wide range of data, so that I covered a range of different attitudes and I helped to reveal phenomena that emerged repeatedly. The design allowed the study to move from the holistic to the specific, while allowing flexibility for the issues central to the research questions to develop (Yin, 2018: 16).

The study had to derive the kind of data necessary for unpacking the notion of engagement with respect to various actors in the specific transient spaces, in order to observe phenomena as to behaviours and reactions. Ethnographic research is particularly suitable for 'disentangling and explaining interconnections' (Herbert, 2000: 557).

3.1.2.1 Selection of research sites – livescapes

The research question and aims, the scoping study, the community heritage project the case study was based on, and my previous knowledge of locations in and around Glasgow guided me in selecting the research sites (Walford, 2001; Carman and Sørensen, 2009). The sites were considered as suitable as livescapes for being activated for the purposes of the research. In the Portfolio, I set the research's framework of the notion of *locality* and in through the photographs of the localities of the two waterways that I focused on, I identify why these locations are suitable exemplars for the case study (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/locality/>). To be appropriate in terms of the research question and aims, and in order to examine participation in post-

industrial heritage in Glasgow, the sites had to have strong historic connections with the actions selected for the activation of the livescape (these actions will be outlined in section 3 of this Chapter). I consider the case study as one study taking place across more than the one location, with the same activities and actions being engaged in with respect to more than one livescape. The reason for this is that the observations had a focus on participation rather than being specifically related to the different characteristics of the sites that participation took place in. Furthermore, the heritage subject of the study, the inland and urban waterways, provided a physical continuum, as I could study two locations (the river and the canal) as representing two aspects of the one heritage subject (inland and urban waterways). My previous knowledge gained by volunteering and working with maritime organisations in and around Glasgow, provided me with insights as to appropriate localities where groups had problematic engagement with heritage. Moreover, the community heritage project had the support of the FCCS, support that provided funding and practical assistance for the duration of the study. Specifically, the organisation became the focal group that then interacted with the other groups selected for the research. Historicity of the sites of research was also important, as the sites needed to have strong historical connections to post-industrial heritage in terms of location and activity. This ensured that the research sites as livescapes, had history related to the actions employed in the activation (boating, boat maintenance, boat building).

3.1.2.2 Selecting participants to activate the livescape

Although the participating groups (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/the-case-study/>) were from under-represented communities in the heritage locality, the case study did not investigate the groups in terms of their individual characteristics, acknowledging transiency as shared contestation created through urban place-making processes. Thus, under-representation with respect to place-making processes affecting the localities was a much more important consideration for selection than, for instance, being a refugee group was. The different characteristics of each group did not dictate how the study was conducted, while nonetheless setting the parameters of a shared approach, including the style of the workshops, and informal conduct throughout. Furthermore, purposive sampling was used, which allowed me to select groups of participants from the chosen locations. This provided flexibility with respect to adapting the research to fit with groups' availability and welfare requirements (Arber, in Gilbert, 2001: 62).

This study focuses on the examination of the interactions and experiences of three groups that took part in the case study, as these are the groups that activated the livescape through a number of actions. All of the groups exemplify local communities that are deeply impacted by the changes to their locality (by living in regenerated areas, having new buildings in their neighbourhoods, experiencing certain areas as being inaccessible), but have not been and are not engaged in the decision-making process responsible for these changes. Maryhill has a high incidence of locales that fall into the lowest quintile on the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD). While Kirkintilloch is, overall, less 'deprived' according to SIMD measures, there are neighbourhoods that are amongst the lowest quintile and some of the participants came from these areas (SIMD).

The concept of transiency (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/tensions/>), as utilised in this study, draws from the relevant literature explored in the previous chapter (Chapter II), which defines transiency as the experience of the changed environment or the experience of relocation and migration, and in some cases both. Transience may also be experienced in combination with forms of deprivation and, by extension, exclusion or marginalisation. This definition is used in considering the sample groups to be transient. The migrant community in Maryhill exhibits many transient aspects, not least their migration experience and, for some, the possibility of either further onward migration or return. The Kirkintilloch group was composed primarily of young LGBTQ+ identifying people. This group is transient both in the sense that, as young adults, they are likely to move on (Scottish Government, 2020: 51), and also in the sense that the environment in which they engage is ever changing under the pressures of globalisation and specifically urban regeneration. Furthermore, representation in decision making for these groups is limited, 'urban planners are often extraordinarily unreflexive about how the built environment creates symbolic barriers to genuine participation' (Gray, 2018: 5). The scoping research revealed that these local communities usually struggle to take advantage of the services and opportunities that regeneration provides, resulting in different experiences of exclusion and marginalisation in the areas where they live and work.

3.1.2.3 Selection of actions for the activation of the livescape

The study was situated in the environment of the historic waterways in and around Glasgow, as the researcher had previous experience, in both a professional and voluntary capacity, with cultural organisations situated in these research sites. The organisations I already had knowledge of (Appendix II) were involved in boating activities, boat handling and maintenance, and two of them in boat building. Thus, the case study's actions

were boat handling, boat building, and the dissemination of information through celebratory events and exhibitions.

Craft (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/boat-building/>), as the means for activation of the heritage livescape (Lefebvre, 1991; Sennett, 2008, 2012), was employed as a method and as the movement designed to reveal agential interactions with respect to heritage (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987: 373). In this way, the choice of employing craft as an activity for examination facilitates the negotiation of the study between experts and participants. As framed by the study's philosophical underpinnings, through the way in which the fieldwork (the activated livescape) was established, there is continuous negotiation of the positions of the researcher and the researched. As such, throughout the study, knowledge was negotiated and transferred within the field of the research. It is the focus on craft, in this instance, which facilitates the interactions and reveals the activation (Ingold, 2000: 153).

3.1.3 Interviews in the livescape

I used semi-structured interviews (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/interviews/>) as a data collection method for two main reasons, firstly to reinforce the argument of the contested livescape and secondly for triangulation purposes (Latham, 2003; McLellan et al., 2003; Keats, 2009). This sub-section of the Portfolio has a collection of photographs from the environments the interviews took place. The reader can see the places where the interviews took place and at the same time acquire a sense of the places: for example, both places have workshops, however one place uses their workshop for events and community gatherings. One interview was taken after one of those events and the interviewer and myself, the researcher, attended open workshop nights and events in the organisation, before the interview was arranged.

Through the methodology of the activated livescape, the study's aim was to examine in-depth participation in local heritage, particularly, the ways local (transient) communities participated. The heritage locality is one of contestation, due to place-making processes. For the purposes of exploring that contestation through examining the locality for gaps in participation and for hegemonic attitudes concerning sense of ownership in the heritage landscape, I needed to employ a variety of data collection methods in order to cross examine the results from different sample groups.

Interviews 'take place within relations of power' (Bennett, 2014: 6), thus, utilising a method of semi-structured interviews which incorporated the sample groups in the process contributed to the examination of the tensions, by addressing the barrier between the other research participants and the researcher. The interviews provided the opportunity to the participants and the interviewees to negotiate power balances through the process of extrapolating data (Bennett, 2014; Smith and Osborn, 2021).

I used three interviews from the oral history part of the community heritage project (Appendix I), and I collected data in the form of observations during the fieldwork. I observed one of the study's participants conducting semi-structured interviews with two cultural organisations in two different localities on the river Clyde, during the study process. The oral history interviews with the members of the FCCS as part of the CanalCraft community heritage project are mentioned, with parts of them used as data to support the research's arguments. These are interviews that I conducted personally, with a questionnaire prepared and agreed by the members of the organisation. The oral history interviews served as a repository of memories from a selected group of long-standing members of the FCCS, who served since the beginning of the campaigns for free navigation, since the late 1970's. These interviews became part of the archive of the FCCS and they are accessible to researchers of the FCC.

3.2 Ethical considerations

Firstly, as a PhD researcher undertaking research under the auspices of the University of the West of Scotland, I adhered to the university's Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship (UWS, 2016).

The principles of the UWS Code of Ethics guided my study throughout, as aligning with the values that were foundational for the study, as outlined previously in Section 3.2: the principles of beneficence; non-maleficence; autonomy; justice; and truthfulness – all of which corresponded to my own philosophical paradigm as reflected in this study from the outset.

Studying communities and groups within communities' locality needs to involve certain ethical considerations. Research should aim to promote innovation and push methodological boundaries (Macdonald, 2010) and at the same time retain reliability and transparency for the communities involved (Nind et al., 2013: 3). According to Orb et al. (2001), '[t]he desire to participate in a research study depends upon a participant's willingness to share his or her experience' (:93), thus, I embedded in the research design process considerations of the ways

the participants' willingness and cooperation could be managed and maintained throughout the study. The principle of transparency, being open about expectations from participants, became my primary concern during my conduct with the participants, but also during the recruiting process and my communications with the officers who worked with the community groups. An exemplar of this is the recruitment of the women's group in Maryhill. I contacted the group via the manager and all my arrangements were through them. I had a triple role in the research: as the Heritage and Community Engagement Officer for the CanalCraft project, as a researcher through a university, and as a participant, who was observed for my involvement in the activities and the locality. As I discuss in more detail in the positionality of the researcher in section 2.3.3, the triple role has given me the opportunity to gain trust amongst the officers who managed the community groups. Activities, events, scheduled meetings, and all participation involving the groups were co-designed with the managers of the groups, in order to put the participants and their wellbeing first, without compromising their safety and sense of security.

In their study on 'participant observation and interview process', which focuses on research situations with vulnerable groups, Kang and Hwang (2021: 9) set out clearly the parameters of what qualifies as consent for participants to take part in a research project. In this research project, the participants were all adults, however the groups that they represented are considered vulnerable. I approached consent with as much transparency as possible. I introduced myself to the groups as a researcher, using the UWS's name. I also introduced myself to the groups with my role as the officer responsible for the heritage community project. Thus, the fact that I had two organisations that supported me, the university and the FCCS, helped with gaining consent from the individuals and the groups. As most of the data was sourced from photographs and videos that became part of the fieldwork diaries, all images that were published in the Portfolio were checked and approved by the organisations that represented the participants, securing their safety and acceptance to be published on line and in hard copy publications (for a digital copy of the CanalCraft Review publication, see the Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/canalcraft-film-and-publication/>).

According to Aluwihare-Samaranayake (2012), 'the researchers must put the person first before the research' (:69). I followed this guidance in the research process, and an exemplar of this is the conduct with the LGBTI+ group of young adults. Some of the participants from that group were happy to sign consent forms for the research, which stated that they were participating in an academic study. However, there were members of

the group who expressed their desire to have minimum presence in publicity although they were happy to be observed for the research purposes. This experience showed me as a researcher that approaching groups, especially vulnerable ones, is a delicate matter. It made me understand that starting a study from the outset with groups who are self-aware and have a problematic relationship with signing documents could jeopardise the research project, and the relationship of the individuals with the researcher. For this reason, I based the consent process on my open and transparent relationship with the individuals and the officers who managed the groups, maintaining a dialogue and honest relationship throughout the study, retaining a culture of openness and freedom to express desires and feelings of discomfort.

Kang and Hwang (2021) argue for five implementations in order to maintain adequate ethical standards when conducting research with vulnerable groups. These standards are based on building an honest relationship with the researcher, integrity of the researcher in every aspect of the relationship with the observed, beneficence, confidentiality and privacy, and informed consent. I would add that meaningful research that brings helpful results from the study could not be achieved without these ethical parameters. My experience with the research project has demonstrated that without a trusting relationship between participants, organisations and the researcher, based on mutual respect and understanding of desires and boundaries, research cannot produce deep insights from observations and interviews. Mutual respect builds the foundation for a successful study.

3.3 Data collecting

According to the philosophy of the study as discussed earlier in this Chapter (Section 2.2), the heritage livescape is not static and an end product but is in a constant state of becoming. Given this, I wanted to make observations of the experiences of being in the livescape, by collecting data through a range of different methods, ethnographic and auto-ethnographic fieldnotes; field diaries; reports; images and footage of videos; and interviews transcripts. This amalgamation of data 'provide audiences with vivid, empathetic accounts of "being there"' (Cook et al., 2019: 2).

3.3.1 *Ethnography and Auto-ethnography*

Reflecting the study's paradigmatic understanding of heritage being a process that continually develops through the ongoing interactions of the elements that occupy the heritage landscape, ethnographic work

serves the research by capturing the interwoven relationships and interactions that take place and expose the livescape (Herbert, 2000: 557; Atkinson et al., 2001). Being both a researcher and a participant, I engaged in such ethnographic work through fieldnotes, taken in the form of photographs and videos (Denshire, 2014; Emerson et al., 2011; Wang, 2012).

Videos provide live testimony of participation and engagement in the activation of the livescape, something which could not be fully captured using only the spoken and written word (Donoghue and Miller, 2016). In fact, the issue of language became a barrier and a tension in the field work, as for some members of the sampling groups (including myself), English is not their first language. Therefore, ethnographic work employing a range of media sources helps to reflect the different modes of interaction in the research field (Norris, 2002). Video and photo field notes do not fully have meaning unless they are complemented by notes on the context in which they were taken (Mitsuhara and Hauck, 2021: 248), thus my notes with the video and photo diaries were vital for identifying the tensions as they emerged in the field. With respect to the examination of the livescape, ethnographic work provided me access to the other research participants' understandings of the activation as it was happening. Through systematically taking notes of my impressions as to research participants reactions, and thus gaining insights into their perspectives, during the interactions I could begin to form an understanding of the livescape, the tensions as they emerged, and the forces that shaped interactions (Emerson et al., 2011: 159).

The ethnographic fieldwork revealed local knowledge through paying attention to local community perspectives, and thus contributed to gaining an understanding of local insights while, at the same time, working to balance out unequal positioning in the research between researcher and participants, all of which serve to reveal dissonance (Hamilakis and Anagnostopoulos, 2009: 66).

Observations of myself as the researcher and of my own actions within the research process, and particularly how my actions were perceived by sampling groups, provoked 'transgressive writing' (Denshire, 2014: 838) which pays particular attention to both immediate and wider contexts. An opportunity was provided, through taking this approach, to write about not only being part of the activation of the heritage landscape, but also being a foreign Mediterranean woman in a local community group, in the periphery of Glasgow, in which the dominant perspectives are those of a white, middle-class, male demographic. Auto-ethnography provided the opportunity for me, as the researcher, to take a step back from the groups I was both in and was observing, in

order to critically reflect in providing accounts as to emotions, insights and intuitions (Denshire, 2014: 834). It is important, in doing such, to consider the actions and insights of participation in terms of being multi-scalar, from the bigger picture to the granular level of self (Jones, 2016: 296).

Auto-ethnography (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/the-researcher/#autoethnography>) fits well with the study's aim of examining acquisition of knowledge. Additionally, it fits with the research being through practice and activation, as it serves to 'unpack' the researcher's positionality, with respect to the contexts of the research. It also helps to expose power relations in the field (Denshire, 2014: 838) that inform the heritage process; in this case relations of power with respect to knowledge making and recognition, both concerning relations between participants and heritage management, and also between the participants themselves.

4. Analysis through employing the activated livescape

I approached the study through a combination of inductive and deductive methods of analysis, ensuring that the conclusions and propositions that led to the development of the conceptualisation of the contested and activated heritage livescape were founded on a multi-modal understanding (Bowen, 2009; Braun and Clarke, 2019; Keats, 2009; Kiger and Varpio, 2020). I made sure there was a continuation between the philosophical paradigm of the livescape and the conclusions of the study (Gray, 2017: 37). A combination of inductive and deductive approaches to the study assisted in the validation of existing theories as to the intangibility and processual nature of heritage as well as in establishing the theorisation of the contested and activated livescape (Braun and Clarke, 2012: 58).

Indeed, the use of both deductive and inductive approaches to data analysis are apparent through considerations of the livescape as a method of inquiry. Addressing marginalisation in engagement and broadening the scope of participation through familiarity with the heritage locality, call for themes and coding headings that reflect previous theories such as those concerning the more-than-representational and the vitality of materials (Lorimer, 2005; Bennett, 2010).

4.1 A trajectory for the analysis of the livescape

The trajectory of the analysis began with the gathering of all noted material (fieldnotes, diaries, photos, videos; interview transcripts; archival material) and followed a thematic procedure with respect to the analysis, as informed by the six-phase approach (Braun and Clarke, 2012: 60). I used Braun and Clarke's

approach as guidance only, and I proceeded with five stages identified in my planning and informed by the considerations outlined in this chapter, above. Thus, the steps for the analysis of the livescape were:

- Notes were generated for every item of data, framed according to the research questions, in a process of familiarising myself with the data.
- Commonalities (or patterns) extracted from the field notes organised according to the tensions of the livescape.
- Themes (from the research question) were observed and noted to construct Commonalities.
- Overlapping of commonalities (patterns) to create pools of concepts (sub-themes).
- Sub-themes emerged within each of the themes.

Figure 7: Thematic analysis of the livescape

4.1.1 Thematic Analysis reflecting on tensions

Critically reflective thematic analysis was utilised to interpret the data. The model of the activated livescape as a method of inquiry guided the study in terms of locating relevant themes and sub-themes, in order to organise the varied data collected. Although I understand engagement to be an abstract notion and that as such, its nature and impact is not easily identified, qualified and measured, nevertheless, through thematic organisation of the data, the analysis aimed to be rigorous (Braun and Clarke, 2012: 57). This was achieved by following the progression from the philosophical underpinning of the study to the results. Looking for common themes across the data posed some problems, given a consideration of the concept of commonality and whether this is understood as an aspect relating to everyday life or an aspect relating to a one-off event; for example commonalities that surfaced with respect to observing a weekly gathering of the groups, or over lunch, when compared to commonalities with respect to behaviour during a festival. These, in contexts of the livescape, in which human and non-human elements are considered as part of the engagement process. Therefore, commonalities were clustered according to their relation to the human and non-human elements of the livescape.

Although grounded theory was not used as an analysis technique, the analysis borrowed principles from it as a theory building tool (thematic analysis), which clusters commonalities into themes (Lauckner et al., 2012). The analysis sought to describe emerging tensions and then themes as connected by tensions. Therefore, the analysis followed two strategic directions, reflectivity and positionality of the researcher which establishes the cultural perspective of the study to which the analysis then refers back for validity, and systematically answering the sub-questions to the main research questions and re-examining them in relation to the theoretical propositions established at the beginning of the study (Yin, 2018: 168).

I devised a framework for the analysis based on themes, guided by the theoretical framework for the research, as supported by the discussions of the literature review chapter. The conceptualisation of the activated heritage livescape guided the research through the theories that underpin it: knowledge; familiarity; liminality; ownership; transiency; agency; ; the everyday; proximity; vitality.

Within this strategic analysis, an attention to critical reflexivity aided in considering different possible interpretations of the data, thus ensuring rigour.

For triangulation of the results, the analysis depended on the technique of pattern matching (Yin, 2018: 178), using memos and the visual notes to analyse behaviours and opinions.

All data was analysed for its relevance to the research question and aims of the research. The results were analysed in terms of the research's theoretical propositions and through doing so arranged in commonalities.

The study's questions determined the framework of analysis. Data was collected throughout the time of research and all material was then categorised, as discussed by Yin (2018: 131; LeCompte, 2000: 148). I explored 'interconnections' (Herbert, 2000: 557) that support the triangulation of patterns and speak to the frequent appearance of phenomena – and then placed these in themes as relating to the research questions, in order to find connections.

Being critically reflexive with respect to the analysis reflects the ethical principles on which the study is founded. Theoretically, the study has supported the argument that socio-political positions construct the cultural landscape, thus in a case study, where examination through participation and ethnography/ auto-ethnography form part of the data, the analyser and interpreter are part of the building of knowledge (Finlay, 2002: 532).

Acknowledging the reality of and influence through one's position in society, through processes of critical self-reflection, does not imply rigidity in evaluation. This study's theoretical framework supports the notion of becoming, rather than the existence of static, concrete realities concerning the heritage environment.

Therefore, as Marshall argues, '[p]art of inquiring is making judgements about when to be focused and directed and when to be open, receptive' (2001: 433).

With respect to the conceptualisation of the activated livescape as a method of inquiry, the study's analysis was based on three concepts and the relationships between them, which served to identify the tensions within the heritage landscape. These concepts are: Locality; Heritage; and Participation. (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/>)

4.1.2 Commonalities in the livescape

A systematic and in-depth reading of all the data led to the development of a system of commonalities (patterns) in the activated heritage livescape.

Research notes were gathered, reread and arranged into mind maps, with visual signs/symbols attached for ease of recognition and thus to facilitate the locating of patterns. Patterns were then established, and this process was informed by comparing the research notes with both those from discussions with the participants and my own reflexivity notes. Figures were created with the commonalities in ways that spoke to the conceptualisation of the livescape.

‘Themes both emerged and had been pre-established and the next stage of the process involved a clustering of patterns within the themes’ (Smith & Osborn, 2021: 19).

Avoiding the issues concerning commonality, the themed clusters were juxtaposed and formed into sub-divisions of clusters, or sub-themes. Connections between the themes and sub-divisions become Figures that are examined for tensions. A spine of tensions deriving from the themes, provided the backbone for the analysis, with all other themes branching out (Figure 7, Chapter III, Section 4.1).

The final stage involved writing up this analysis so as to illustrate the similarities and differences in behaviour and interactions between participants and participants and researcher, thus creating a narrative that answered the research question, and supported the livescape as a model of engagement.

Figure 8: Thematic analysis example

4.1.3 The Portfolio

The creation of the Portfolio was the tool that collated all the outcomes of the case study, which were the data of images and footage collected during the workshops, the celebratory events, and the festivals. I consider the on-line Portfolio as the main part of the thesis, as the tangible outcomes of the case study could not be accessed and experienced live, due to the Covid-19 pandemic restrictions. Furthermore, by the time the pandemic restrictions had eased and the examination of the thesis was planned, the boats with their oars had been donated to community groups: two boats were given to a carnival organisation based on the FCC and one boat was donated to a children's cancer charity on Loch Venachar, to be used for short trips. Nevertheless, the Portfolio is now an on-line resource for everyone to connect with the research project and to get familiar with the livescape.

The Portfolio was divided in four sections, to reflect the main aspects of the study, and the research journey I underwent in order to create the livescape as an engagement model and inquiry method. The sections of the research journey are:

1. The Research, which includes the-sub sections of the Scoping Study and the Case Study in which I demonstrate through visual material the heritage project CanalCraft the study was based on. In this section all the activities are presented, such as boat-building, boat-handling and the celebratory events, and in another sub-section, the Interviews.
2. The Researcher is the section that includes my previous experience and expertise which led to me leading the research. In this section I explain my previous involvement with the cultural organisations I worked with during the study, underpinned by visual images. This section also includes the autoethnographic work that took place during the research.
3. The Livescape is the third main section and here I have discussed three aspects of the environment I studied: Locality, Heritage, and Participation. Presenting these sub sections was important as they became the themes on which I based the analysis of collected data. Another sub-section ins Tensions, which includes the diagram I created of the Livescape as activation and the tensions that appear from the activation. Each tension is presented in four sub sections, each one demonstrating the tension with text and visual material: 1. *The locality of the heritage landscape is ever changing*, 2. *The ever-changing heritage landscape blocks opportunities to get familiar with 'being there' in everyday life*, 3.

Knowledge of a place begins when there is familiarity with the locality. Knowledge belongs to all and all should have equal opportunities to be familiar with their locality, 4. Knowing a place, its past and present, and being familiar with it, makes us feel like it belongs to us and feel responsible for its future and 5. Taking part in the locality's everyday life by the practice of craft such as boat-building in a place where the craft is part of its history breaks the routine of the everyday life that is under the power of the authorities that control knowledge. .

4. The Film and the Publication is the final section, and it is the moving image documentation I have created with footage from the entire CanalCraft project. In the film the viewer can see the different elements of the project and the affect it had on the participants and the organisations involved. I felt that the film needed to be presented separately from the other sections as it encapsulates the essence of the research project. The Publication is the digital version of the CanalCraft Review booklet that was produced at the end of the community heritage project.

By following the different sections of the Portfolio, along with the written part of the thesis, the reader will be able to follow the resonance behind the research and be view the livescape coming to life through the visual data and the films that have been created by using the data. Signposting to the Portfolio sections and sub-sections throughout this thesis guides the reader through the different themes' explanations of the analysis, assisted by the visual materials of the data.

Figure 9: The Online Portfolio

The online Portfolio is the visual part of the thesis. This diagram facilitates the reader in following the different parts. The Portfolio was curated into five main sections: The Research, The Livescape, The Researcher, CanalCraft Film & Publication, and Acknowledgments. Throughout Chapters III, and IV, there are references to specific places in the Portfolio, for the reader to follow and this complements the argument in the thesis with the images and films deriving from the research. The online Portfolio is an online exhibition of the results of the research, as well as a showcase of the community heritage project the case study of the research was based on CanalCraft.

Chapter IV The Case Study

This chapter presents the data that supports the theorisation of the livescape. In doing so, firstly, I explain the case study by placing it in context and practically describing it. Secondly, I refer to my methods of collecting data and the literature review that guided the formation of the research question. I proceed with presenting the results by introducing the patterns, themes, and sub-categories derived from the data that also correspond with the concepts of the livescape that emerged from the literature review. The analysis and interpretation of the results is completed with a discussion on the theory of the livescape. Finally, I conclude the chapter with possibilities for further study and opportunities for the case study to be repeated in other contexts.

1. Examining the livescape in a case study

1.1 The case study in context

The case study concentrated on areas around the river Clyde, Glasgow's Riverside and the south bank at Govan, and the Forth and Clyde Canal (FCC), particularly the northern areas of the canal in and around Glasgow (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/locality/>). These post-industrial heritage landscapes were familiar to me from previous professional and volunteering engagements. Thus, the case study design was derived from a scoping study (Arksey and O'Malley, 2005) that included consultation sessions and a seminar (see Appendix II, Scoping Study Report) comprised of local heritage presentations by individuals, projects, community groups, and cultural organisations from the areas of focus. The case study was part of a larger, publicly funded community heritage project, CanalCraft. I have presented the research in the online portfolio, where I have used visual material from CanalCraft and the case study in order to guide the reader through the research project. The four main sections are divided to sub-sections including all the stages of the research project, information on the researcher, the scoping study, the activities, the interviews, the livescape as the model of engagement, the tensions, the concepts of locality, participation and heritage, and the film from CanaCraft and images from the co-produced exhibition. The case study can be found in the Portfolio; <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/the-case-study/>

The scoping study exposed that the tensions identified in the literature review needed further investigation and identification. Observations in the geographic areas of the study focusing on use of the landscape revealed

that the different levels of possible involvement with it have been broken or blockaded by, principally, a lack of engagement with the place and due to issues of transiency in the locality. Actively using heritage landscapes in order to preserve them challenges the locality to recognise significant elements in the experience of them, which identifies the place and the meaning of it as a public space (Varna and Tiesdall, 2014), and, through familiarity, a sense of ownership and agency. Therefore, transiency in the locality as identified through this study is twofold: the experience of a changing environment (human and non-human), and the mobility of the communities that use the place due to migration and lack or deprivation of opportunities to access resources and the heritage assets where they live.

Local communities (under The Scoping Study in the online Portfolio, I explain about the community groups I consulted and the areas where the study took place) who occupy the localities along the river and the canal are expected to adapt to new cultural planning through place-making processes that have placed heritage at the forefront of regeneration (OECD, 2002). The new built environment (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/locality/>), with its focus on inspirational cultural buildings, such as the Riverside Museum, managed by the expertise of heritage (AHD) that favours monumentality (Smith, 2006) appears to challenge certain communities' struggle for visibility and voice, despite the efforts from heritage institutions (Crooke, 2010). Prior to the study, I held a position as a museum officer at the Tall Ship, Clyde Maritime Trust, and that position facilitated observations that led to the realisations of gaps in engagement related to transiency. That included gaps in engagement by members of the local community who, despite apparent access to the regenerated areas and new buildings, felt that they didn't belong or that the new places had relevance to their everyday life (Talen, 2000; Jones, 2017; Ng, 2018; Gray, 2018), (for images of Speirs Wharf development with gates separating the heritage buildings in the locality, see Portfolio <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/research/#spiers>). A sense of familiarity and ownership, and knowledge hierarchies affecting agency (Crook, 2010) in the heritage of the place, were two key factors that were identified through the scoping study (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/scoping-study/>).

1.1.1 The groups

The case study involved the participation of six organisations (plus three youth groups during the Scoping Study stage). These were: a canal boating society that hosted the case study and provided background support, identified in the study as FCCS; a refugee integration organisation based in Maryhill, north Glasgow,

which provided two groups (MIN); a women's group in the same area which provides shelter and skills; a group of young LGBTQ+ adults based in Kirkintilloch; a heritage organisation based on the north bank of the river Clyde, which is a museum ship with a workshop, The Tall Ship at the Riverside; and GalGael, a community organisation based in Govan, on the south side of the river, which promotes wellbeing through boat building and woodworking.

Some of the organisations that took part in the case study (Portfolio <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/the-case-study/>) were involved with campaigning. The canal boating society, FCCS, has over forty years history of campaigning, initially to open and currently to keep open the canal to navigation. The refugee integration organisation is involved in campaigning for the rights and wellbeing of refugees and asylum seekers and their work is dedicated to the integration of New Scots in the local community. The Kirkintilloch participants were organised through an established local LGBTQ+ youth group, and they were involved in supporting young adults in issues related to diversity. The Tall Ship museum started in the 1990s as a community project helping unemployed men to acquire new skills. Today, the organisation, through a boat-building workshop, provides opportunities for disadvantaged and marginalised community members to learn new skills, and promotes community-led projects that provide skills and new opportunities for employment. Finally, the organisation on the south bank of the river, GalGael, had originally started as a campaign venture for taking ownership of public spaces, which were being taken away by big urban infrastructure projects such as motorways (GalGael Charter, 2017). Today, the organisation still campaigns for publicness in the urban environment and provides opportunities through boat building and woodworking workshops to local communities affected by unemployment and mental health issues related to deprivation. The promotional literature of GalGael states that 'we quickly realised we could achieve many of our social, cultural and ecological aims by involving the community in building boats. For us boats are both a metaphor for transformation – as we journey from one place to another – and tools for achieving our purpose' (GalGael Charter, 2017).

All the above organisations suited the study's Participatory Action Research collaborative approach (Bradbury, 2019), as they hope to achieve justice for social space and the publicness of the urban waterways (Appendix I) I related the campaigning work of these organisations directly to the concept of the activated livescape, in that it presents an assemblage of objects and human and non-human activity in the heritage environment

(Bennett, 2010) which defines the contested engagement with heritage.1.1.2 Place-making and local communities in the heritage livescape.

During the scoping study and analysing these cultural organisations, their projects, and the communities they serve, I identified gaps with regard to communities' understanding of heritage as a notion and engagement with local heritage (Bell et al., 2017). The FCCS encouraged local communities to go on their boats and experience the canal through cruises. In the past, they had run boat-handling school trips. In the case of GalGael, local communities have been encouraged to engage with getting familiar with the water, boat building, woodworking, and engineering skills, thereby generating knowledge about and familiarity with the water, which is a dominant feature of the locality. While The Tall Ship predominately engages communities as a visitors' attraction, they also run volunteering projects including boat building and boat maintenance, but have had very limited activity for getting communities in the water. The women's group and LGBTQ+ youth group had not engaged with similar activities before, though the refugee group had previous experience with woodworking activities through gardening.

During the time planning the case study and through the scoping study, I was aware of the topography of the river and canal system which identifies the liminality of the waterways (Andrews and Roberts, 2012). Being aware of Ng's study (Clark and Wise, 2018) which looked at embodied experiences in urban space, I was interested in their argument that our sense of a place is impacted by how it is framed including through competing or jarring discourses, and their study echoes my observations in Glasgow's urban waterways at the time. Ng's study gives an example of how collective partnerships and community initiatives could persuade redevelopment agencies to change plans and instead allow local initiatives with direct interest to a place (sense of community, understanding, attachment, ownership) to take over conservation and activate a strategic plan of social activity: a fuller understanding of place as outlined through people's active participation in the space. Thus, I applied the principal of activation, acquiring knowledge - a sense of place and understanding through active participation in a liminal space (Keating et al., 2012) - to the case study through a set of activities. In the formation of the case study I also borrowed from Lorimer's (2005) arguments of the more-than-representational space of cultivated city allotments, the element of understanding the liminal by activating it and that by activating it one can observe the tensions that develop, and that concept helped me to form the core of the case study design.

Another study that underpinned activation for me was Höflehner and Zimmermann (Clark and Wise, 2018) who studied the role of transdisciplinary approaches in establishing a comprehensive and inclusive arena for the governance of local community assets, including heritage, arguing that the activation of the heritage environment in the locality was important in order for all the actors to understand and have a sense of belonging to the place they occupy.

During the scoping study it became apparent that specialised management of resources and assets, such as the canal that runs through neighbourhoods and backyards in and around Glasgow, unintentionally fails to grasp concerns in the locality, especially from marginalised groups that are not familiar with voicing their views (Talen, 2000). Fear and uncertainty deriving, for example, from overgrown vegetation or unfamiliarity with use of the water, induces alienation at the expense of connectivity (Downey et al., 2016). These views were voiced to me during the scoping study when, for example, a women's centre located next to the FCC was approached and during an informal discussion about the neighbourhood.

The study is informed by the notion that sensory levels of engagement with the environment, landscape features and heritage that are animate, present possibilities for a deeper understanding of the topography of the river Clyde and its canal. Through this research, I contest that even though such notions feature in current thinking about place-making, it does not adequately create these new spaces for considering the contested environment. I developed the activated heritage environment in this study into the concept of the contested livescape, as the platform where the landscape is lived and worked and becoming through tensions (Lorimer, 2005). Unpacking these tensions, through the activities in the case study, I exposed the limitations of knowledge and consequently the misalignment in agency, publicness, and ultimately sense of belonging of public space (Varna and Tiesdell, 2010). In this way, I reflected on the main question of the research, the examination of the participation of transient local communities with the local heritage environment and how this engagement informs the heritage process and adds to the understanding of interactions between heritage elements in the everyday realm.

1.2 Literature on livescape and the research question.

My starting point of the research was to unravel the features of engagement with the waterways and to examine the way(s) this engagement affects the heritage process. In the words of Byrne (2009: 243), '[w]hat

worries me is that the term 'heritage practice' could too easily be substituted [...] by the word 'monumental'. I share Byrne's concerns about the hierarchical approach to intangible heritage led primarily by the cultural institutions that dominate agency in the localities of the research focus. Monumentality, which both the river Clyde and the FCC have as a common characteristic, is connected with heritage management and is a matter reserved for the specialists (Crooke, 2010; Smith, 2006; Harrison, 2013). In parallel, considering the tangible heritage of the two waterways (bridges, towpaths, boats, museums) that are under the care of professionals, there is little space left for the agency of the marginalised and transient parts of the community (Crooke, 2010). Unpacking the notion of the heritage process through the activation of the waterscapes in the case study, the aim is to open up nuanced opportunities for activities that contribute to the everyday understanding of the historic environment, and of how these understandings are weaved in the locality such that they establish a presence through action. Thus, the alternative opportunities for engagement with the heritage waterways that I was aiming to find, are presented as the activated livescape, a model for engagement that reveals the tension that develops between the authorised part of the practice and the struggle for ownership, a heritage landscape created and understood through tensions.

The plan for the case study design that I had in mind was informed by considerations that had emerged in previous studies and followed a trajectory of planned events and informal discussions before establishing a method of enquiry suitable for answering the research question. As mentioned earlier, I had over five years' experience in the geographical areas of the case study, as a professional and a volunteer, and I had observed that heritage practices for the transient parts of the locality are driven by heritage institutions, heritage professionals' expectations and targets, local strategic plans for development of tourism, and local micro and macro political directions, which makes them difficult to identify and hard to observe (Pierce et al., 2011: 57). These dynamics of the heritage processes, the tensions in the 'relational place-framing' (Martin, 2003), constitute another viewpoint for studying the heritage environment. Thus, through the study I also looked at how one can detect these dynamics by the tensions that are created in the live heritage environment that has gone through the place-making process. Examining the heritage-process triptych of knowledge, transiency, familiarity as experienced by the transient locality, discloses opportunities for reassessing notions of hierarchy, agency, and a sense of ownership which dominate the renewed urban heritage environment. Reassessing

these notions led me to the conceptualisation of the livescape as an alternative engagement with heritage and model of inquiry.

Thus, led by the literature and the conceptualisation of the livescape, I formed the study's question to examine how transient communities get involved with post-industrial maritime heritage and the ways in which this participation informs the heritage process. The case study followed a Participatory Action Research approach, and data was collected through ethnographical and auto-ethnographical observations in mainly two localities, Maryhill and Kirkintilloch, in and around Glasgow. The study also involved three interviews with The Tall Ship and GalGael. Lastly, I gathered data from fieldwork during meetings and informal conversations, and I also drew from materials generated by an oral history project, video and photographic footage, and archival material. The activation of the livescape in the case study, as I have mentioned, took place with boat building and boating activities, two celebratory events, and three interviews of the organisations on the river Clyde.

My objectives for the case study were, firstly, to examine transient communities' participation and involvement within the post-industrial cultural landscape in Glasgow, focusing on heritage assets. Transient communities in this study are identified as individuals or groups who have been affected by forced mobilisation, immigration, deprivation and difficulty accessing services, underrepresentation, and have been affected by the change of local environment due to place-making processes in the locality; secondly, to identify possibilities for the same communities to activate the heritage landscape, by boat building, using and celebrating boats and boating in their locality, and through aspects of further participation, such as boat maintenance and sustaining a boating culture on the canal and the river.

As explained in Chapter III, I collected data through a case study based at locations around the Forth and Clyde canal and the river Clyde, between October 2018 and February 2020. The boat-building workshops had the duration of two weeks each; boat building in Maryhill between 1st and 12th April, and in Kirkintilloch between 12th and 23rd August 2019. Boat-handling activities took place on 3rd June and 20th August 2019. The first celebratory event took place in Maryhill on 21st June 2019 and the second event in Kirkintilloch on 26th October 2019. Also included and presented at the events was earlier data collected from the scoping study, during May 2018, which led to the formation of the case study design.

The first two interviews (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/interviews/>) I included in the case study took place at The Tall Ship on 18th December 2019, and the third interview at GalGael on 13th February 2020. During

the case study, as the researcher I produced field notes from a series of activities and events that the participant groups took part in – activities that were craft-based, boat building and boat handling, and two celebratory events based around the canal. I collected observations from three informal interviews with two community heritage organisations at the river Clyde: The Tall Ship and GalGael. At The Tall Ship, the (Clyde Maritime Trust) the interview was arranged beforehand and was based on a questionnaire developed to inform of the organisation’s relationship with the boat-building workshop and the role of volunteers. My aim was to uncover attitudes, feelings, and gaps in the engagement with the boating culture in the present time, and the role of the museum in sustaining it. I developed the questions with the help of one of the boat builders from the Kirkintilloch LGBTQ+ group, who also conducted the interviews. The interviewees were the manager of the workshop and one of the volunteers. Arrangements were easier as I had known The Tall Ship staff and volunteers for many years due to my previous work there, and I had developed a familiarity with the place and the people there.

At GalGael, the interview was not arranged beforehand because, although the organisation was not new to me as I knew them from the Clydebuilt Festival and the Anchor and Sail project (see Chapter 1, section 2.2), I had never visited them before during events. I arranged the interview impromptu, during a social night, after myself and the interviewer (the same person who conducted the interviews at The Tall Ship) participated in a couple of community gatherings at GalGael’s premises.

Through the case study presented in the following sections, I argue that these collected activities represent the heritage process as the activated livescape.

1.2.1 A Case Study out of CanalCraft project

The study was derived from a larger community heritage project entitled CanalCraft (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/canalcraft-a-case-study/>). This larger project featured various community engagement activities undertaken primarily with marginalised groups. From within this larger project, specific activities, such as boat handling, boat building, and celebratory events, were identified for in-depth study and data collection. To do so for all the activities of CanalCraft would have been beyond the scope of this doctoral study. I undertook a dual role within CanalCraft; as a participatory researcher I led the CanalCraft project on behalf of the FCCS, and this afforded me the opportunity for auto-ethnographical data collection.

The activities described took place between 1st April 2019 and 26th October 2019, and on a couple of occasions they occurred simultaneously, either on the same day or at the same time.

These hands-on workshops involved participants fully taking responsibility and control of the building of the boats.

‘Everybody is focused on the tasks given by B (lead boat builder). The pieces are all laid out and everybody has a specific job to do. A and D are sanding, M and L are measuring some rods, and K uses the plane’

(Fieldnotes, Boat building, Maryhill, Day 2)

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/boat-building/#boat1>)

The young participants took ownership of how the new boat would look like, despite comments from other boaters who did not approve of the colours. There was an act of dissonance (Smith, 2006) in the heritage landscape.

‘I came back to the boathouse to find the participants covered in paint and laughing. They gave up trying to apply the paint in an ordered way and they decided to ‘go rogue’. Apart from the designs they drew, they are now splashing the paint on the boat and make marks on it with their hands, ‘as a signature’, ‘we were here and we built this!’ they said to me’

(Fieldnotes, Boat building, Kirkintilloch, Day 7)

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/boat-building/#boat3>)

The painting of the boat projected the young people’s understanding of familiarity with the heritage landscape. They built something that they can activate the landscape with, and they made their own mark with it, following no one’s rules.

‘This is not a boat! Boats do not carry these colours, so this is not a boat!’

(Fieldnotes, Member 1 of Seagull Trust, Boat building, Kirkintilloch, Day 10).

The same group took ownership of their safety in activation, according to the new knowledge about buoyancy they acquired by building the boats:

'We all helped to get the boat in the water. I said I will be going in with F and C. We are all very excited. This is the moment of truth. Finally, the boat is in. "It floats!" everybody shouted'

(Fieldnotes, Boat building, Kirkintilloch, Day 4)

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/boat-building/#boat3>)

The same self-support was observed with the group in Maryhill. They took responsibility to check the boat out in the canal. Although one member had previous knowledge of boats in their country of origin, it was their first time on the water with a boat in a canal.

'To check for leaks, A sat on the boat in the water for 10 minutes. 'No leak', they announced and we all took it in turns to get in and row it. At the end we all ended up in it!'

(Fieldnotes, Boat building, Maryhill, Day 7)

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/boat-building/#boat1>)

The participants took ownership of the boats' presentation to the rest of the community through the celebratory events. Presenting the results of their newly acquired knowledge meant that they were now part of the place they occupy. Now they know what it takes to set up a workshop, build boats, and row them in the locality. Being in charge of the activities transforms the knowledge into familiarity and a sense of ownership for the place, because they feel they contribute a reason for the community to celebrate.

'I'm here tonight because of the boats, yes, I was one of those who built them, and I was on the boat cruise as well, so I've been with them all along, so tonight is the celebration of achievements and I'm looking forward for more to come'

(Participant 1, Celebratory Event 1, Maryhill)

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/celebratory-events/>)

Data suggests that there was an effect on the young people's group through the exhibition that they set up in the local heritage centre about their workshop. These data extracts suggest the emergence of the livescape in the heritage environment. Activation occurred with the boat building and boating, creating the alternative opportunities to engage with the canal, water, tools, boats, in a direct way. This is significant, because the

interaction of the marginalised groups with the local heritage occurred with the help of the cultural organisations in the locality, demonstrating local knowledge and expertise, creating new knowledge that is generated by being familiar with the local environment. As the young people's group was aided by the heritage centre's curators in setting up the exhibition, the young people shared their experience and new knowledge with the curators who have never built a boat before nor been on the canal (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/celebratory-events/#exhibition>).

'Today F and S set up the CanalCraft exhibition at the Town Hall Heritage Centre, with the help of the two curators. They selected objects from the boat-building workshop that were significant to the job and they also put the rainbow flag in one of the display boxes, along with the objects. They carried the boat into the building and up the stairs. It was hard to believe a boat in that space but it fits well'

(Fieldnotes, Celebratory Event 2, Kirkintilloch, Setting up the exhibition).

1.2.2 The role of the researcher in CanalCraft.

My position of Heritage and Community Engagement Officer with CanalCraft provided a set of research duties that allowed me to have oversight of the activities, events, and selection of groups such that they could also participate in the case study. My community heritage duties were to organise and conduct oral history interviews (parts of which I analysed as archival material in the study) (Appendix I), organise and design workshops, liaise with organisations, assist with event organisation, facilitate community engagement and connections between groups, identify groups and assist the FCCS in accessing new members. My duty was also to manage an assistant and volunteers, and create and promote a digital archive for FCCS.

The CanalCraft project's assistant took an active part in the study as a participant. Their dual role was to document and facilitate the activities, and therefore they contributed to the data collection by documenting events, producing photographs and images that became part of the study data as noted in its description.

1.3 Data collection for the case study for the livescape.

Ethnographic and auto-ethnographic data was collected within the dates of the activities stated (Emerson et al., 2011; Brunt, 2001; Denshire, 2014). Forms of hard data collected consisted of: fieldnotes from meetings;

informal conversations with participants and key people involved in the case study, such as officers from the groups and boaters; my own diary in the role of engagement officer in the community heritage project between October 2018 to February 2020 (Bennett, 2015), various forms of interview questionnaires and transcripts (Hays, 2003), reports (ibid.), promotional leaflets and booklets (ibid.). My personal diary was collected in digital visual form, which consisted of 149 minutes of videos and 1,528 photographs, and formed part of the observational ethnographic notes (Bohnsack, 2009; Knoblauch and Schnettler, 2012).

Additionally, there is supplementary data that was collected throughout the duration of the community heritage project, such as that associated with events, conferences, meetings, festivals, documents and ephemera material collected within and around the study's timescale (2017–2019). Some of this data consists of ethnographical observations, however in this study it will be used as secondary data for providing further context. Supporting material consisted of notes from meetings (26), notes from oral history interviews (11), marine organisations' journals (5), one film (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/canalcraft-film-and-publication/>), notes from seminars (6), notes from informal conversations and meetings (48), an interview, archival material from EDLC and FCCS (55), reports of CHO to FCCS (6), published reports in the areas of study (3), promotional booklets and leaflets from organisations and groups in the locality of the study (37), reports of social media ratings of the heritage project and numbers reached (2). Thus, the case study has followed Schoch's (2020) case study plan, where I built a database of the data collected to supplement the Portfolio which is the main outcome of the study.

1.4 Activation of the livescape – Case Study Description with examples from the data.

1.4.1 Boat handling

The two boat-handling activities described here occurred, firstly, on 3rd June 2019 jointly with participants from the women's centre and the refugee integration organisation; and, secondly, on 22nd August 2019 solely with participants from the refugee integration organisation. Both cruises started from Rochill Bridge in Maryhill, where the groups of participants met the boat, and travelled on the Glasgow side of the canal. The first cruise sailed up to the Maryhill Locks and the second one sailed up to Applecross Basin and Port Dundas. Both cruises ended back at the Rochill Bridge in Maryhill. This section of the canal was selected because it passed through areas that have been altered through regeneration. I planned to observe the ways participants reacted to the area viewed from the water.

'I've never seen these parts before and I've lived here all my life. It all looks different from the water! There is so much green and so much wildlife. Look, look [shouting at the rest of the group], this is the back of the building we live in!'

(Participant 1, Boat handling, 3rd June).

Additionally, this is an interesting part of the canal to navigate, with features that pose challenges for boaters (Portfolio, Cruise 1, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/boat-handling/#cruise1>).

'One crew member is at the front with the groups and they are chatting to them about the canal, the boats, the society and the buildings and wild life we are seeing from the boat. They are also answering questions the groups have. Many questions! Now, they are encouraging participants to take turns to navigate the boat'

(Fieldnotes, Boat handling, 3rd June).

In order to do that navigation, the participants had to take turns and be with the volunteers at the back of the boat, chatting with them about navigation techniques, the water conditions, the canal features that cause concern, and the other vessels, animals, and users of the waterway.

'The boat builds momentum and it takes a few seconds to correct its course. However, one gets a good feel of the waterway from navigating the boat because one needs to be

aware of the water conditions, the curves and the sides of the canal'

(Member 2, FCCS, Boat handling, 22nd August).

As the participants ventured to navigate the boat, I observed the way they learned under instruction to avoid obstacles, recognise currents, and adapt to the canal's features.

'It is quite a stressful activity but it is reassuring that the boat master is next to the tiller to correct mistakes'

(Participant 1, Boat handling, 22nd August).

During the cruises, I took part in all activities alongside the participants, but as an existing member of the FCCS, I was familiar with the navigation protocol and methods, and was able to answer some questions about the canal and the boats. (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/the-researcher/>)

There were 10 participants and 3 members of crew.

The boat used for this cruise was the smallest the organisation has, accommodating up to 25 passengers and crew, but which is the most suitable for training as it has a tiller (hand-steered rudder) and so was specifically chosen for this activity.

'I have confidence in using the canal now!'

(Participant 4, Boat handling, 22nd August).

'I nearly crashed the boat [laughing]...it was fun'

(Participant 2, Boat handling, 3rd June).

Although this boat is not as spacious as their larger vessel, the tiller facilitates participants having a chance to navigate and so is a popular boat of the Society because visitors can more directly interact with the canal, giving them a sense of control over the waterway.

'It was absolutely great using the tiller. A little bit scary, but also absolutely great. I think I'm good at it'

(Participant 8, when asked about the boat)

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/boat-handling/#cruise1>)

The activation of the heritage livescape took place on the canal (both a monument and a landscape) by using the tiller (an integral part of the canal boat) in order to navigate the boat down the water. Tillers are a direct way to control a boat, and it is easy to learn as compared to other methods of navigation (Canal and River Trust, 2022). Thus, the tiller's significance here is the vitality (political power) that it holds through its ease of application: most participants can use it, even with no previous experience. It simultaneously reveals and generates the tensions in the livescape: transiency, knowledge, familiarity and sense of ownership of the heritage landscape. The majority of the participants had never been on a boat before and none had been on a canal boat. Everybody chatted with each other excitedly. Transiency is revealed because participants come from community groups who, although they occupy the canal's locality, have limited to no opportunities to be on a canal boat and navigate it (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/tensions/>).

'First time on a barge and first time on the canal. This trip has fulfilled a long-awaited wish for me'

(Participant 3, Boat handling, 3rd June).

This method of engagement opened up tensions. In this example the livescape is uncovering all the elements of the heritage landscape referred to in the literature review: the canal as a place of nature but also as a place where boats move suggests the liminality of the local landscape.

'At first I thought it was a railway that passed in there. Then one day I saw the top of a boat! When I asked, people said it is a canal!'

(Member 2, MIN, Informal conversation).

Furthermore, transiency is implied by participants' lack of opportunities to know their locality (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/boat-handling/#cruise2>). The FCC, since the Millennium Link (Appendix I), has been developed to serve local communities through the towpath. Data suggested that participants in the case study walk on the towpath in their everyday life, but they do not have the same access to boats.

'In order for the canal boats to travel with passengers, they legally need to have a boatmaster on board and two crewmembers. The canal boating society is a charity and provides the service free; however, groups that use the boats for cruises are asked to pay for the petrol fee. The fee is standard for a two hour cruise, which is not affordable

for most groups unless there is a grant involved'

(Fieldnotes, Informal conversation with crewmembers, Boat handling, 22nd August).

A lack of opportunities to access the boats and travel by water impacts knowledge of the locality. Place-making processes in the area where the cruise took place have altered the place, and being on the canal is another way to inspect those changes in the locality.

'You see different things when on the boat. You pay more attention when on the boat'

(Participant 7, Boat handling, 3rd June).

'Participants are saying that they noticed that some areas of the city are visible from the water but not from the road or the towpath'

(Fieldnotes, Boat handling, 3rd June).

'The participants are noticing the building work that is happening in the area and it is more visible from the canal. They discussed between them the changes that are occurring as they are seeing them. "Oh, they are digging everything up! You can't see that from the road!"'

(Participant 4, Boat handling, 22nd August)

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/boat-handling/#cruise2>).

1.4.2 Boat building

During the boat-building activity, two boats would be built by participants from the refugee organisation, and one by participants from the LGBTQ+ youth group. The groups built three small boats (skiffs) and a pair of oars for each boat. Each boat took approximately one week to build and another week for treatment with waterproofing resin and painting. In total, this element of the project involved approximately 160 hours of work between 17 participants.

The boat-building activity used the services of two professional boat builders. The leading boat builder, who I knew from previous projects, was responsible for the organisation of the workshops, to provide the tools and train participants in using them, to supervise the activities, create a safe and friendly environment and observe health and safety conditions and rules during the workshops.

‘At first I thought we will have a problem because not everybody’s English is good. But eventually boat building became the language’

(Boat builder 1, Boat building, Maryhill).

As the organiser of the activities, I was responsible for finding premises to host the boat-building workshops for the duration of the activities. A boat-building workshop needs a stable environment rather than a mobile one, as work, materials, and equipment need to be set up and left overnight, often with glue and epoxy drying. Participants learned new skills and became confident in using complicated methods and materials of woodworking. During boat building, they learned about floatation, buoyancy, and the science of building a boat.

Transiency was a factor affecting the organisation of the workshops.

‘If I had to plan the [Anchor and Sail] project again, I’d make the activities shorter, so that participants can follow through the building of the boats. Coming from marginalised communities and facing the impact of deprivation presents barriers for participants to stick with the task until the end. Yes, smaller projects are better so people can see the end result’

(Participant 3, Seminar, Scoping study, Riverside Museum).

Bigger boat-building projects involving volunteers require a much longer time, possibly years, not only because the scale of the vessel itself requires a longer build time, but also because (a) participants find it difficult to commit to regular attendance; (b) amongst transient groups of participants, other priorities such as job seeking create obstacles; (c) boat-building groups in traditional projects have to use timber that is worked from scratch and consequently every step takes longer and is more complex. The groups in this study used kits, which contained pre-cut designs of small boats and could be assembled using traditional tools and techniques, to build skiffs. The design had to be adapted as there were some flaws, and so the participants learned the principles of boat building from scratch in only a week. Boat-building projects with a duration of a week have a greater possibility to succeed and keep the participants focused as compared to longer builds, and the participants have a better chance of seeing the results of their efforts from project start to finish (Anchor and Sail, 2018). The groups learned about tools and how to use them in a boat-building workshop. Parallel to boat

building, the group learned about the history of boats and particularly about canal boats, as many of the famous puffer boats of the industrial period were built in Maryhill.

In Kirkintilloch, I had previously worked with the local LGBTQ+ youth group on other projects, so I knew them and the group felt comfortable with me as a researcher, as one member of my family was a previous member of the group.

The group was resistant to publicity such that two participants didn't want to be seen in photos or video footage for fear of being 'outed'. I mitigated this by following the university's ethics guidance on consent for image taking and with the participants' permission on how they wanted to appear in images from the workshops. One participant didn't own a mobile phone and they didn't have access to the internet so they couldn't be contacted easily. There was a participant from the Prince's Trust who had some issues with group work and mixing with others. The group composition changed over the period of the two-week workshop as some participants did not want to stay for the painting and others joined later. This group had multiple needs in terms of conduct that had to be observed, thus as the researcher I followed close advice from the youth worker on how to conduct the workshop so the group would feel safe and comfortable. Working with marginalised groups needs to happen on their terms and not on terms dictated by the researcher (Herr and Anderson, 2014). The Participatory Action Research case study approach facilitated the necessary flexibility for working with such groups. In completing these activities, the researcher could empower the participants to guide them.

The boathouse, that was the location for the workshop, was built on the site of a historic repair yard in the area (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/heritage/#kirkintilloch>).. The charity volunteers in charge of the boathouse, who were of an older demographic, offered the boathouse to the group for the duration of the workshops. They observed the work that was happening and sometimes commented on it.

'These oars are very skilfully made. Well done'

(Member1, Seagull Trust, supervising the work, Boat building, Kirkintilloch).

FCCS holds extensive knowledge of the canal and boats and they were happy to share that knowledge with the young adults. This interaction of the two groups uncovered the tension of heterogeneity in the locality, as one group holds knowledge about the place and the other has limited knowledge. The difference is in the

opportunities presented to the groups for engagement with the heritage environment (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/boat-building/#boat3>).

1.4.3 Celebratory events

Two celebratory events were organised to mark the outcomes of the activities. The events aimed to bring the participants and their communities together, and at the same time to take the outcomes of the activities back into the community. The events had entertainment as their core activity and the opportunity for the attendants to share food. Integration was also an aim as groups had not been together before in organised activities. As the activities organiser, both myself and the FCCS committee were responsible for the management and delivery of the events and the coordination of the different groups in organising the food, music, singing, dance, and activities that happened during the events. Participants were responsible for organising the presentation of the event, and the young adults in the second event were responsible for the exhibition, which was co-curated with the curators of the Kirkintilloch Heritage Centre.

The first event occurred on 21st June 2019 in the afternoon at The Engine Works building in Maryhill, a redeveloped industrial building that is now a multi-function venue, and the second event occurred at the end of the case study (see online Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/celebratory-events/>).

The first event was a joint celebration between the participant groups and a local women's drumming collective. The Scottish Refugee Council funded the event and arranged marketing and media, as it formed part of the Scottish Refugee Festival 2019. All groups involved in the Maryhill-based activities were invited to celebrate the achievements, and they took responsibility for the presentations and entertainment. The aim of the event was to help integrate all of the people involved in the process and bring the groups together to interact with the rest of the community, other organisations in the area, and local stakeholders. There were approximately 200 participants, including community organisations, representatives from the local heritage sector, and local residents who had heard about the heritage project. The two boats that the groups had been produced were displayed at the venue. There were introductory talks by the participants, the officers of the organisations involved, and the researcher, welcoming everybody and introducing the outcomes of the heritage project (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/celebratory-events/>)

‘New Scots love taking part in new activities, and these two boats that the participants from MIN produced and will be used by the communities of Glasgow, are a contribution from New Scots to their host community’
(Officer 1, MIN, Celebratory event 1, Maryhill).

The events integrated the community groups, which were heterogeneous but characterised the locality. At the first event, the FCCS is a group dominated by an older, middle class, and white demographic, whereas the women’s group has a mixed demographic of predominately members who experience difficulty accessing services, and MIN serve communities that experience migration.

Over 70 certificates were given by the FCCS to participants for their achievements. These certificates represented the knowledge acquired during the boat-handling and boat-building activities, and the new local knowledge the groups generated by engagement with the heritage of the FFC. This activation through the events suggested that the livescape uncovers tensions in the heritage environment, which can be detected through activation.

‘I had not a clue about how to build boats. The skills from boat building will stay for the rest of our lives’
(Member 2, MIN, Celebratory event 1, Maryhill).

Next to the boats, there were multi-ethnic dance performances from the refugee organisation’s dance group, who consider these performances as an integral part of their integration in the city of Glasgow and the local community they too inhabit.

The second celebratory event occurred on the morning of 26th October in Kirkintilloch (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/celebratory-events/#celeb2>). The five-hour event took place over three venues. Firstly, an exhibition designed with materials from the community heritage project (photographs, the films, and the boat) in Kirkintilloch Heritage Centre, curated in collaboration with the Centre’s curators and two of the young boat builders. Secondly, in the Town Hall, where the main event took place, there was a celebration of achievements with music performances and talks by the organisers, participants, and representatives of the organisations that provided an opportunity for participants to share some of their experiences and reflections with the audience. Thirdly, lunch in the Church Hall next to the Town Hall, cooked by a volunteer from the

Maryhill women's group. Approximately 70 people participated in the whole event, including the film screenings with one film made with images and footage from the boat-building workshops in Kirkintilloch (see Portfolio). Over 40 certificates were presented by the FCCS to the participants of the activities.

'You would have noticed from the film and the photos that some of us at the workshop won't show our faces. This is because we don't feel safe or secure doing so. Building the boats and being in the workshop felt that we belonged and contributed. Felt included'

(Participant 2, Talk, Celebratory event 2)

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/celebratory-events/#celeb2>)

'Boat building and then trying our boat on the water meant that we established who we are. We collectively created something and it's on the canal'

(Member 3, LGBTI+ YS, Celebratory event 2, Kirkintilloch).

The celebratory events brought the groups together in the locations where they work, showcasing the activation achievements and disseminating outcomes at the heart of the community. However, during the organisation of the events, gaps in engagement became apparent. An exemplar is how place-making processes presented barriers to securing the building for the celebrations. In Maryhill, the redeveloped, privately run, old workshop (Engine Works) aspires to attract corporate events. In Kirkintilloch, the redeveloped Town Hall's catering is run by a private provider, whose prices are prohibitive for transient community groups to have lunch in the same building as their event. This transiency could only be revealed by activating the heritage environment.

1.4.4 Sharing food as activation of the livescape

The experience of sharing food at lunchtime as a feature of all the workshops was an unexpected new activation method. The observed activity implied that the heritage livescape can be activated in the everyday realm with a mundane activity such as lunch. During lunch, the participants generated further knowledge through unexpected realisations about the place.

'This is such a nice spot. I never noticed the canal before. Now I notice that it is full of garbage'

(Participant 3, Boat building, during lunch on the pontoon outside the Boathouse,

Kirkintilloch)

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/canalcraft-a-case-study/#lunch>)

'I went to school just there [pointing at the secondary school on the opposite bank to the pontoon]. I never thought about the canal then. The canal means nothing to the kids at school. It's just somewhere to throw rubbish' (Participant 4, Boat building, during lunch on the pontoon outside the Boathouse, Kirkintilloch).

'This is a nice building. I never noticed it before. The porter said to me that it is Victorian'

(Participant 5, Boat building, Maryhill).

'It's so nice here next to the water. I don't know how this thing is called [pointing at the pontoon] but you can sit next to the water on it'

(Participant 2, Boat building, during lunch on the pontoon outside the Boathouse, Kirkintilloch).

The plan was to ask participants to cook a shared meal for everybody to enjoy together during the celebratory events. This idea originally emerged during the scoping study, from a volunteer at the women's group who works at the centre's café and grew up in the locality, and remembered food sharing in the streets of Maryhill. She thought that local communities would benefit from a food gathering that would be free or affordable for all to enjoy, and to enjoy the heritage place at the same time.

'The problem is that most food they serve now in community events [festivals] next to the canal is dear, isn't it? You can't buy food from festival stalls now, it's dear'

(Member 1, Consultation session, Scoping Study, Women's Centre, Maryhill).

This idea did not materialise as it was difficult to organise food prepared outside an organised kitchen and to arrange people doing the cooking under appropriate food preparation and hygiene conditions. Sharing the experience of food became another activation of the livescape, which was an unexpected outcome of the study.

1.4.5 Interviews on two workshops – livescapes

Three interviews took place between December 2019 and February 2020, at the Clyde Maritime Trust and GalGael, on the north and south banks of the river Clyde respectively. The aim of the interviews were (a) to use another method of data collection for triangulation purposes, (b) to collect data from the cultural organisations at the river, (c) to define transient communities that engage with the boat-building and boating participation in heritage organisations, (d) to understand the ways in which the two organisations consider their workshops, participants, their work, and boat building and boating as activities for heritage engagement. Unstructured interviewing presented a way of getting information directly from the sources outside organised activities.

Originally, the plan was to have four interviews. Two with officers of the two community heritage organisations, that have boat building and boating at the core of their activities, and two with volunteers who work with those organisations.

One of the participants from the Kirkintilloch boat-building activity, a young adult, conducted the interviews, with the researcher present supervising them and taking fieldnotes. The researcher trained the interviewer in interview skills; to form questions to guide conversation, building rapport with the interviewee, gaining trust of the interviewee, and in ways to conduct an interview for optimal recordings (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/interviews/#interviewer>).

As the researcher, I prepared the questions (Appendix IV) guided by the objectives of the study and the research question. In particular, the interviews were exploring community participation with live heritage (the river) and identifying the relevant community groups, recognising the intangible heritage assets in the specific environment, and detecting agency in the post-industrial environment. Thus, the questions aimed to explore the activated livescape of the river Clyde and how it affected the heritage process.

The first interviews occurred on 18th December 2019 at the offices of the CMT at the Riverside in Glasgow and were subsequently transcribed.

The researcher's previous connections with the CMT helped in organising and securing the interview and in achieving a comfortable atmosphere during it.

At CMT, both the leader of the CMT's workshop, and one of the volunteers, who has served the Trust for almost 20 years, were interviewed (Appendix IV).

The third interview occurred in the evening on 13th February 2020 at the premises of GalGael in Govan, and produced 24-25 minutes of recordings as well as 12 photos. The interview was subsequently transcribed.

I and the interviewer visited GalGael twice before the interview took place, in order to familiarise ourselves with the organisation, feel comfortable with the space, meet suitable interviewees, and get to know the organisation first hand. We took part in an event where they shared food with volunteers, officers, and participants of the wood workshop. We also participated in the wood workshop where they met the volunteers (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/interviews/#interview3>). Unfortunately, it was not possible to find a volunteer to interview. One volunteer who wanted to talk decided that they felt too anxious. As the principles of the study have the participants' wellbeing and comfort as priority, I decided to interview an officer and omit interviewing the volunteer. There were some notes taken from the interactions at the workshop, which helped in the analysis.

It was decided that interviewing the officer, who had been a volunteer and now worked for the organisation, was sufficient for the study's purpose. The interviewee answered all the questions and they added their comments and views on the future of the Clyde and the communities' future around the river.

I shadowed the interview and I intervened when there was need for clarification or extra questions during the introduction of a new theme (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/interviews/>). The interviews worked as a continuation of the seminar that took place at the Riverside Museum during the scoping study, before the case study took place. The interviews exposed gaps in engagement with the livescape of the river Clyde. CMT and The Tall Ship museum are guided by AHD principles (Robbins et al., 2021) and, therefore, is how engagement with the museum is structured. However, the interviews wanted to uncover potential alternative participation with the livescape. The questions focused on the role of the museum's workshop, which hosts boat-building activities. In GalGael, taking the boats in the river, gatherings and sharing food, and being in the workshop, are all activations of the livescape.

Thus, the activation of the livescape through the two workshops suggested that (a) transient communities that volunteer at the regenerated site of the museum and around the river are heterogeneous; (b) there is

knowledge generation outside the AHD parameters, exposed through the workshop and volunteering expertise; (c) handling boats in the river brings about a sense of ownership and publicness of a social space during the heritage process.

1.5 Areas of further investigation.

There were certain limitations in the execution of the case study. Some of these limitations were mitigated.

The first limitation was the nature of the groups. Working with refugees and asylum seekers was going to raise some concerns for political reasons. The researcher in the past had come across some animosity in the local community of Glasgow North when working in a project with the Scottish Refugee Council. Fortunately, there was full support from the canal boating organisation's committee who were ready to mitigate any issues arising, a fact that set the tone of the project on friendship, integration, and support.

Another consideration was the collaboration between the young adults of the LGBTQ+ group and the canal boating society. The latter, predominately with members of an older demographic and unfamiliar with current diversity issues, could be a potential obstacle in the realisation of the case study.

There were issues concerning the participation of vulnerable groups, such as the refugee groups, that the researcher was initially unaware of. For example, travel expenses, lunches, and childcare provisions had to be covered by the organiser of the activities, as the organisation did not have the funds. The grant from the community heritage project covered those expenses.

Finding suitable places for boat-building workshops was another limitation. Despite the fact that the researcher was aware from discussions with locals that there are many empty post-industrial spaces in Maryhill and Kirkintilloch, it was difficult to find a space available for a community group to use without a charge. Local authorities and statutory organisations do not have such a provision, therefore, without the grant from the community heritage project, it would have been impossible to secure a space.

'Boats need to be used and not rot away in a store room. They give joy'

(Boatbuilder 1, Boat building, Maryhill).

This data extract shows another tension in the livescape. The future of the finished boats is a community consideration for boat-building projects, because wooden boats are difficult to store and they need dedicated

people to use them frequently. We had originally discussed that the boats would go with the organisations that were to build them, however that was not possible because of the lack of space and expertise. In order to keep and use boats, community groups need to have a boat enthusiast who could take people on the water. Furthermore, boating is a skill and knowledge that the organisations who participated in the boat building did not have. Therefore, it was hard for the groups to keep their boats for future use.

In order to happen, activities, celebratory events, and heritage projects require expertise, time, and dedicated organisation. The organisations that participated in the case study are all dedicated to the wellbeing and service of specific communities and do not have the capacity, time nor expertise to fundraise, organise, and manage heritage projects too. That amount of work would take them away from their core aims and priorities. In the light of this, the researcher had to alter the way the activities were organised in order to facilitate the timing and objectives of the participating organisations.

Furthermore, as the case study presented opportunities for participants' direct engagement in heritage activities, it entailed the involvement of statutory bodies and exposed the extent to which heritage engagement is influenced by AHD and the structures that support authorised heritage activity.

A further limitation was the short period of time within which the case study had to be conducted. This limitation was directed by the essential feature of the research (PhD thesis research) and the community heritage project the case study was based on, which was only designed for one year. This limited time period forced the study to happen within strict parameters, which impacted findings and the relationships between the participants and the researcher. There is further research potential in using the same case study structure in other livescapes, such as working and education spaces.

1.6 Concluding the case study.

The case study was designed to reflect the aims of the research; to examine participation and involvement with heritage, and to identify new possibilities for participation and activation of the heritage environment of the waterways. It focused on four places in Glasgow where there is rich post-industrial heritage based on the waterways in and around Glasgow.

The case study involved six community organisations, based in the areas of focus, who have campaigning at the core of their activities. These organisations campaign and work towards securing the rights and wellbeing

of disadvantaged groups in their locality, groups who experience transiency through the altered urban environment and experience of migration or marginalisation.

The case study was based on planned activities that activated the livescape: boating on the canal, with the experience of navigating a canal boat using the tiller; boat building small craft and learning a traditional craft; participating and learning to work collectively in a workshop, sharing tools and food in creating an object that you then use to travel on the waterway. Indeed, sharing food and creating new relationships that reaffirm integration and generate new knowledge is an important aspect of the heritage process that the case study explored.

Finally, the process of finding suitable places to host boat building in the present, in the areas next to the waterways that are also of historical importance for boat building during the industrial era, was itself informative. It relates to how, overall, preconceived ideas of what heritage is and how it is practiced create barriers in engagement by the transient communities in the location of heritage and expose tensions in the contested livescape.

These tensions will be analysed further in the results section below.

2. The Livescape emerging

2.1 Research aims and questions for the examination of the livescape.

In this study, I focused on examining the experiences of local groups and transient communities' participation with the heritage of their local Forth and Clyde canal and river Clyde, in a changing urban environment, and the ways in which this experience informs the heritage process. As explained earlier, originally, the study began by examining participation with the local heritage assets of the local waterways in the backdrop of place-making processes in and around Glasgow, where the case study was based. However, during this initial investigation I observed that the historic waterways were the platform of a set of tensions – such as familiarity with the heritage place, transiency, sense of ownership, and unequal knowledge – and that noticing these tensions precipitated a model of participation based on the activation of the heritage assets. The activation that I observed, as explained in the case study, was the building of three boats, the handling of canal boats during two cruises, and the dissemination of these activations in the form of two celebratory events. I supplemented the activation with three interviews, conducted at the livescape of the river Clyde, in two areas

on the north and the south bank. During the study, I encountered the different presentations of the waterways: the physical characteristics as constructed landscape features; a natural habitat for various species; water corridors that people travel on, and where cargo was transported and boats were built; and, more recently, places of leisure and visitor attractions, with wellbeing expressed as new residential developments. These presentations are intertwined, with the past and present, and they were apparent during the planned activities of the study.

In this section, I present the commonalities as they appeared in the data. Developing from these common patterns, the themes emerged. Finally, from the themes, sub-themes were brought to the fore, and all these categories were analysed as the tensions in the livescape. The conceptualisation of the activated livescape was formed in the literature review and discussed above in the case study, as building up to the research question. I will proceed by explaining what each tension entails, supporting it with extracts from the data. Each tension is presented with the insights gained, exposing the livescape as a method of inquiry and a method of engagement with the heritage landscape. In the last section, I summarised the results and the way their analysis guided me to the argumentation for the theorisation of the livescape.

2.2 The commonalities, themes, and sub-themes of the livescape.

Following the lead of the main question of the study, the results formed two understandings. One is the activated heritage livescape, as conceptualised in chapter two, through the review of the literature and previous studies. The livescape is underpinned by notions of transiency (Clark, 2009; Diamond, 2010; Mowat, 2015), everyday life (Inglis, 2005; Ronneberger, 2008; Thompson, 2013), and liminality (Keating et al., 2012; La Shure, 2005; Miller, 2017) in the backdrop of place-making processes (Cresswell, 2004; Pendlebury and Porfyriou, 2017) that change the environment that communities engage with (Perkin, 2010; Dempsey, 2010; Della Torre, 2015; Zhang and Han, 2022). The other understanding is that the consolidation of the contestation, tensions, and dissonance (Smith, 2006) observed in the field equate to notions of hierarchies of knowledge (Harrison, 2013; Berg, 2004; Neimanis, 2012) and how they impact engagement; community's familiarity with the local place (Iveson, 1998; Varna and Tiesdell, 2010; Varna, 2016) and engagement with the heritage landscape through craft activation (Sennett, 2008; O'Kelly, 2009; Fine, 2010). These notions form the main body of tensions constructing the livescape.

According to Braun and Clark (2012), commonalities in data could be misleading if they do not identify as relevant to the research question. Thus, I interpreted the research question broadly in determining what data to collect.

In the analysis of the case study, I organised the *themes*, *sub-themes*, and *commonalities* of the study as shown in figure 7 (Chapter III, Section 4.1).

Figure 10: Case study analysis structure

In figure 10 I illustrate the case study analysis structure: the themes of locality, local heritage, and participation derive from the research question. In the locality theme, the analysis was based on the identification of the way the place was perceived by the communities who occupy it. Locality of the canal and the river is characterised by the tangible and intangible elements such as pontoons, cutting of branches to clear navigation routes, vegetation in the water that obstructs navigation, boaters and the wildlife. These elements were organised into sub-themes for the analysis purpose, thus, for example, the barrier sub-theme of preservation includes the cutting of branches by the boaters who try to clear navigation routes on the canal. The sub-themes direct the analysis of the data towards the commonalities, which are the concepts that repeatedly appear through the results of the study. Thus, familiarity and knowledge are commonalities because the cutting of the branches on the canal demand deep understanding of the environment of the waterway and skills in boating in order to cut tree branches with chainsaws and stir a boat close to the banks to do it.

Data revealed a sense of in-betweenness in the way participants felt about the place they live and work in the locality, and the canal and the river (Nicholson-Smith, 1991). The AHD and the agencies that lead place making, generate a sense of in-betweenness for the communities who are exposed to it through activation (Smith 2006), such as walking the canal tow path. The theme of locality, emerging from patterns as mentioned above, is split into subthemes, which unpack the ever-changing landscape (Ingold, 2000), the heritage landscape (binaries of tangible/intangible and natural/cultural), and the transiency in locality (Clark, 2009) by generating meaning. The theme excludes broader understandings of uncertainty in the regenerated urban space based on exchange values (Ashworth et al., 2013).

Therefore, what follows is the presentation of each theme, and how it helps interpretation of the data. This is then developed in an analysis of the sub-themes that emerge through the tensions in the data to an understanding of the livescape.

This use of patterns, themes, and sub-themes allowed me some flexibility in concentrating on what the data revealed and organising the evidence's transformation into meaningful insights, by employing different methods (Gray, 2017) such as ethnographic fieldnotes, imagery based diaries (photos and videos), and oral history interviews, in different ways and of varied intensity, according to the study's questions and results (Braun and Clark, 2012).

2.2.1 Post-industrial waterways as localities

2.2.1.1 In-betweenness in the heritage environment reflects the tension in the binaries of nature/culture, tangible/intangible, and memory/experience.

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/tensions/>)

Binary approaches to the heritage environment, in this instance the canal and the river, are expressed by patterns of natural and cultural presentations in the locality. The canal is a waterway that used to serve the locality in the past; today it is also experienced as a natural environment. This relationship is tensional, as the natural appearance of the canal, which is now developed and presented as a place for wellbeing (Scottish Canals), is not safer than before its development, when it was considered as unsafe by hierarchical agencies (Canal and River Trust 2017).

This is manifested through the data when one of the boat handling participants talked about the nest of swans by the tow path. Swans are feared by canal users, in and out of the water, as when they have a full nest they become aggressive towards walkers and boaters.

‘Just by the Lock 21, there was a nest, by the other side of the path... That could do you some damage’

(Participant 1, Boat handling, June 3rd).

The canal’s locality is shared by human and non-human elements, which are in tensional state.. Wildlife coexists in close proximity with people; for example, both the swans and people use the towpath. The coexistence shapes the locality and its liminality, which is apparent in the inanimate elements that constitute the locality of the waterway,

‘We are all enjoying listening to the rain falling on the boat and we looked outside the windows. With Gipsy [the boat], we are close to the water. Everybody is noticing the things that float on the water, the wildlife, and the plants. They are also listening to the instructions about safety’

(Fieldnotes, Boat handling, June 3rd).

The activities of being on the boat, steering it, watching the water and the tow path whilst on the water, and participating in safety procedures on being on a boat, create the waterway and its locality, according to the study.

The liminality, the in-betweeness, of the locality of the waterway presents, through the activation of being on the boat, as a cultural (boat handling) and a natural space (ecological surroundings), and at the same time underpins the tangibility and intangibility of the interactions that take place in the heritage environment. The heritage environment is manifested as liminal once again because in this case, the heritage does not derive from memory, which creates monumentality. In this example, the heritage of the waterway does not derive from its historic value but from what it represents for the memory, even if the memory is not connected to the place.

‘The women are saying that back home [Nigeria] many people live near the water and they use rivers to go to places, and when they do that they sing. M started singing and

the other two women followed her. The women from the local group are just chatting away; I think they feel a bit worried because they are on the boat'

(Fieldnotes, Boat handling, 3rd June).

Thus, being in boats around and on the canal and river opens up the challenges and points out the symbiotic reality of the locality (Harrison, 2015). (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/boat-handling/>).

The canal has been re-established and opened to navigation having gone through various levels of regeneration since the Millennium Link project in 2001, based on its physical characteristics and historic value as a monument (Appendix I). The monumentality of the canal is bound up with the memories and experiences of the participants on the boats, both when they notice the wildlife as they daily use the canal (towpath) and their own memories of other, sometimes far away, places. In the place-making process, the canal's monumentality is understood differently by local communities according to their personal experiences and relationship to place (Byrne, 2009).

2.2.1.2 The heritage process of activation of the locality exists in-between the everyday and the familiar.

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/boat-building/#lunch>)

In-between spaces such as the waterways reveal the tensions in the locality (Smith, 2016). When the locality is activated, used by the communities that occupy it, and there is interaction between the natural environment , the objects of the everyday that people use, and the waterways, the engagement underpins a connection (familiarity) that is part of the heritage process,

'I never noticed the canal before. It was just there, water, where we chucked rubbish in on the way home from school'

(Participant 1, Boat building, Kirkintilloch).

The high school mentioned here is next to the canal and children walk on the towpath routinely, which is when they would throw litter in the water. According to the participant, they do not perceive the canal as a monument to be preserved but as another feature of the landscape, such as a road. They throw objects (rubbish) in as an act of familiarity, even if this is perceived as a negative mode of engagement.

‘Canal for me means water. If you jump in it, you die’

(Member 1, Youth Club, Consultation session, Scoping Study, Milton).

Thus, jumping in the canal, which is another form of activation (engagement) and perceived as a negative form of engagement, is another act of the everyday life in the locality, and it represents the familiarity of the locality with the place.

The canal has been considered as an unsafe place in the locality, as has been suggested via the scoping study and then by the case study data. Familiarity and engagement through the water entails danger and this is embedded in the understanding and sense of place in the locality (Portfolio,

<https://elenakoumpouzi.com/heritage/>).

‘We all know someone here who either died or had an accident in the canal. This is why locals want it filled in’

(Member 2, Women’s Centre, Consultation session, Scoping study, Maryhill).

Boat handling is a pattern observed in the theme of locality, that develops in the sub-themes of knowledge and everyday life, and transforms in the tension of transiency and knowledge in the locality; the heritage landscape.

‘One of the most rewarding things was the trips that we did with school primary children. Because we introduced them to all sorts of things and taught them about water safety, and they had a policeman who came and talked to them about vandalism, and that was very important, because when we first joined the society, every time we left the boat we had to put large sheets of plywood over the windows because you would come down to the boats and find the windows had been broken by people throwing stones. And after all those school trips, we didn't seem to have that problem, so we stopped putting plywood over the windows’

(FCCS Member 2, Interview extract).

This example from the data illustrates how different modes of activation of the waterway reveals alternative modes of familiarity. Engaging with the canal by smashing the canal boats’ windows, and engaging through

boat-handling sessions through school trips are two different modes of activating the waterway in the everyday life of the locality.

Not everyone can go on canal boat trips unless they go on a free school trip or they have a car to get to the free canal cruises that are available. Patterns of deprivation, marginalisation, and barriers to engaging with the locality suggest unawareness of the place, in the heritage process. Engagement through activities eliminates unknowability by transferring knowledge (for example, learning to steer a boat). The act of knowledge sharing amongst the locality through boats transforms the attitudes on the locality by inducing awareness and familiarisation, and this activation leads to a sense of ownership of the place and agency. Canal boats' windows stopped being smashed as people felt familiar with the boats and understood their value during the school trips.

2.2.1.3 Transiency affects liminality in the locality. The familiar and unfamiliar sense of place is liminal.

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/tensions/>)

Transiency is conceptualised in this study as embedded in the liminality of the locality, and this reflects on the in-betweenness of familiar and the unfamiliar, the mundane and the significant. The significant actions of the heritage process have been determined by the agencies that hold decision making powers in locality, and the insignificant (jumping in the canal) is an activation that derives from both familiarity (feeling confident to jump in) and unfamiliarity (unaware of the dangers due to lack of knowledge about the canal structure). I observed that local communities' perception of the canal and engagement with it through activities promotes belonging, but at the same time contains a sense of threat and danger. Walking on a frozen canal or swimming in it could be perceived as a heritage activation practice, as swimming and using boats are related activities. Heritage acquires a positive meaning, however, when the ability to engage with the heritage asset (here the canal) has a negative effect (danger, death) which at the same time generates a sense of belonging in the locality.

'Finding the local sewage hole with the pool of sewage water and swim in it in the summer. It was hundreds of us. We were poor so no money for swimming in a swimming pool. The other day, boys found dead in the canal, they were trying to cross the canal when drunk' (Member 5, Women's Centre, Consultation session, Scoping

study, Maryhill).

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/scoping-study>)

The liminal state of familiarity /un-familiarity with the waterway determines the mode of engagement and the understanding of the place. I have observed that for many of the local people the canal has dark connotations, of people they knew who lost their lives on purpose or by accident. Visiting a monument (The Tall Ship) in a controlled way guided by the AHD, although providing a sense of safety (embarking a ship and being on the Clyde), does not provide the same in-depth engagement as when communities use their own activation (swimming in the canal on a hot day), even if it is a negative one (danger). One gets a better sense of the monument and its characteristics when one directly engages with it, by knowledge sharing. Thus, for example, jumping in the river Clyde to swim without knowledge of the river's environment will provide knowledge of the environment, if one survives, however, engaging with the river through a boat one has built offers opportunities for understanding the dangers of the place. Familiarity is connected to distance and opportunity to be in the place in order to interact with it (activation),

'There was no reason for me to come down to the Clyde. What for? The Clyde is too far from Kirkintilloch and I'd prefer to go to the city centre instead'

(Participant 1, informal conversation,, Boat building, Kirkintilloch).

Distance affects the opportunities for engagement with the waterways, which directly affects familiarity with the place. Accessing heritage places and assets, such as the river Clyde and The Tall Ship, combats alienation of the place. Proximity to the water provides opportunities for unorganised and intuitive engagement, especially amongst transient communities (Haeffner et al., 2017).

'If this Society ceases to exist, and I'm worried that if we don't get younger people involved it will eventually, then I'm afraid about the future of the canal. We are the ones that know the canal well and we safeguard that it remains open, through campaigning, through the boats and by always being alert to issues. Sometimes people with authority have no clue of the practical issues that could cause damage'

(Fieldnotes, FCCS Member4, Informal conversation).

During fieldwork, I experienced concerns over the authorities' agency to apply knowledge (AHD) in the regenerated place, during the interviews with canal boaters (Appendix I and Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/tensions/#tension3>). The communities, who experience transiency through the changed heritage environment, in this instance the FCCS's members, acquire familiarity with the heritage place and unique knowledge through regular and lengthy engagement with the canal. Local communities, such as the canal boaters, who use the waterways routinely perceive it as a familiar place. Familiarity here is perceived by the canal boaters as being able to navigate boats in the canal and unfamiliarity is perceived as not being able to navigate boats (as far as I am aware, none of the officers of Scottish Canals knows how to navigate boats on the canal).

2.2.1.4 The changes in the local environment through place-making and the way the place is occupied is liminal

Changes in the locality (place-making) create barriers in the locality (Gray, 2018) and the porosity of these barriers are liminal. The communities that occupy the heritage environment of the waterways have gone through the process of urban regeneration and they have seen, and felt, their locality change through the process. Engagement with the environment presents barriers due to lack of opportunities as I have argued in Chapter II. Places that the canal passes through have been affected by deprivation and that affects opportunities for engagement in the everyday life and sharing of knowledge for the place. Liminality is sensed when the only engagement with the waterway is through the towpath, as the water is out of reach for most people to interact with in a positive way (people may jump in or interact with the water in an unsafe way). The physical environment of the canal and the river is a place in-between the water and the edge of it (the bank- towpath), therefore engagement is restricted as the place feels dangerous or unsuitable for use.

'We need to celebrate the canal. It passes through deprived areas so it can promote life skills and a sense of wellbeing. When engaging with it, we recognise that it's part of our lives'

(Chairperson, GRACE, Celebratory event, Kirkintilloch).

Additionally, member of FCCS pointed out that familiarity with the monument's water element and an understanding of its importance, like the canal sections in Kirkintilloch where boats were built and goods

transported in the industrial period, is achievable by celebrating the positive impact of the heritage asset to local lives.

‘Just walking, some feed the ducks...people don’t have meaningful engagement with the canal. Use the canal for what it is!’

(Fieldnotes, FCCS Member2, Informal conversation).

Place-making processes, for example the development of new boat moorings and pontoons along the waterways, have assigned emphasis to engagement with the lifeworld of the waterways. (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/locality/>). The development of the towpath of the FCC, and in some cases the ‘living by water’ promotion of the place (Scottish Canal, 2020), interferes with the operation of the boats in the canal,

‘[H]ouse boats affect the space where boats manoeuvre’ (Fieldnotes, FCCS member 1, Informal conversation).

Therefore, place-making, and the agencies that dominate the decision making processes, promote the development of the canal place as a residential and leisure environment (Gillick and Ivett, 2018), a strategic plan to generate income (Vallerani, 2018), whereas canal boat use by transient community groups, conceptualised as voiceless due to lack of agency, who experience marginalisation is presented with barriers. Thus, for the transient communities to directly engage with the canal via water, services and resources need to be in place in order to create a more accessible interaction open to all communities. Similarly, by the river Clyde, place-making projects such as the Riverside museum and the Tall Ship (CMT) share the same building. The Riverside is a local authority museum and the Tall Ship is a museum-ship and an independent charity. The Tall Ship, as an independent, small charity, depends on resources from the local authority (such as the provision of the building and spaces for storage, in order for the smaller organisation to maintain activities such as the boat building workshop (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/interviews/>).

‘It means the benefit is that we do not, as far as I know, pay any rent for the building, and we get...water and electricity for free, which given we are a charity and...money’s gone, it’s always an object in this day and age. Without that support, we wouldn’t be able to do the things that we do. So...that’s a massive help for us. Beyond that, we don’t

have a lot of interaction with the museum [Riverside], I personally don't have a lot of interaction with the council'

(Workshop leader talking about the relationship between the Riverside Museum and The Tall Ship at the Riverside, The Tall Ship, Interview extract).

The changes in the heritage localities in focus that were introduced during regeneration guided a new kind of symbiosis in the heritage environment. Thus, the Riverside Museum 'helps' the independent heritage asset (The Tall Ship, an independent charity) to survive. On the same level, at the FCC, Scottish Canals supports the FCCS through provision of office space and mooring facilities for the Society's boats. Local communities around the canal could indirectly access the FCCS's boats through membership. There is also the option to join one of the free cruises the FCCS offers during events throughout the year. Information on those free cruises are shared publicly, however many people still do not know about these free provisions. Another barrier is proximity, as FCCS's boats are located either at the outskirts of Kirintilloch which is not easily accessible by public transport or in the Kirkintilloch marina, near the centre of the town. Regardless of the relatively easily-accessible locations, one would need to have information on when to use the free provisions, which is a barrier to engagement. At the same time, engaging directly with boats independently of a society or a club is an exclusive activity as it requires transportation, free time, information, skills and access to boats either through hire or purchase (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/participation/>), Therefore, a sense of uncertainty in the locality is suggested here (limited opportunities in being on water), as community groups find engaging with the heritage place (the water environment of the canal) less public (Varna, 2016). Nevertheless, even boaters and organisations that regularly use the waterways face barriers in engagement with the water.

'We know that most canal users are not boaters. The towpath will continue in use. But boats bring life and heart to the canal'

(Canal News, 2018, following the announcement of the temporary closure of through navigation of FCC).

An exemplar of this is the case with the bridges' failures in 2018, when due to declining maintenance, boats could not pass through bridges and thus the canal through-navigation was stopped for a few months. Regeneration has placed emphasis on the development of the canal's towpath and river's waterfronts (Vallerani and Visentin, 2018), which has affected the importance of direct engagement with the water and the

use of boats. Issues such as the failure of bridges reveal the barriers to participation, and unless the issues are mitigated through intervention (such as campaigning) then they are not perceived as priority problems by the authorities (Canal News, 2018). At the beginning of the fieldwork, I participated in a campaign for the repair of the canal's failing bridges, which comprised a flotilla of canal boats from Glasgow to Auchenstarry Marina in Kilsyth (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/the-researcher/>).

2.2.1.5 Barriers created due to perceived marginalisation in the heritage environment reflect liminality.

Participation in the heritage environment presents barriers for communities who occupy the place and who are not directly involved in the decision-making process. Kennedy (2017) explains that the widely used method of public consultation by local authorities and the government, the charette, is inconclusive in its efficiency and success in engaging and including all in the newly developed neighbourhoods in the pre decision stages of regeneration urban planning (:116). Therefore, marginalisation, as discussed in Chapter II, being complex, results in parts of the communities near the waterways being voiceless. When indirect exclusion becomes, unintentionally, common practice, the locality becomes liminal, as being in-between familiar and unfamiliar, with uncertain senses of belonging. Activation of the heritage environment by direct involvement in decision making, such as building a boat and use it in the canal and the river, reveals the hidden tensions in the renewed place. Working with transient community groups such as the ones affected by immigration and displacement, I observed that the *giving back to the community* factor in the everyday provides a method of feeling familiar with the environment and gain a sense of belonging for the place they now inhabit.

'Our members are proud for the opportunity to give back to the local society and belonging to the community in Glasgow. Opportunity to explore parts of North Glasgow, which brings memories of the countries they left behind, A place that belongs to them'

(Director, MIN, CanalCraft the Film)

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/canalcraft-film-and-publication/>)

Liminality in the locality impacts on sense of belonging and integration, however, and transient communities struggle to find opportunities to directly engage with their locality. The communities affected by immigration and perceived marginalisation express a desire to create a space of belonging, where at the same time the transiency they experience deprives them of the opportunity. Engaging MIN through the FCC and the river

Clyde in the case study took place through a funded project, with limited timeframe, which provided a budget for essential needs (travel and childcare expenses) to be in place before organising any activities.

2.2.1.6 Living with water is a liminal state in the transient local environment, implying different levels of engagement with heritage.

Local communities who experience the waterway of the FCC and live in close proximity to the water also experience the liminality of the heritage environment. During the Scoping study, I had conversations with local communities and I was interested to find out what they think about the concept of heritage (I asked them to write words that come to their minds when they hear 'canal' and 'heritage').

'I know what the canal is, I can tell you that. I don't know what heritage is, never heard that before'

(Participant 3, Scoping study, Women's Centre, Kirkintilloch).

I observed that established local communities (such as the women who attend regularly activities at the local Women's Centre) who experience transiency through difficulties in reaching services and resources available, appear to be excluded from awareness of the heritage assets in their locality, and ultimately they are unaware of the terminology. Heritage, although as a term is not recognised widely in the communities I was studying, is understood as the historicity of the place. However, it was clear to me that there were gaps in understanding of the term as it is acknowledged by AHD (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/scoping-study/#consultsessions>).I observed gaps in engagement of the local communities who are perceived as marginal with the local heritage, and a lack of awareness of its meaning as a monument. This illustrates the in-betweenness of an environment that on one hand is loaded with historical activity and on the other hand is the same environment of the everyday life realm. Liminality is connected to transiency through the place-making process, a process that was based on the post-industrial heritage assets in order to create new places , but at the same time 'leaving behind' parts of the communities in the locality.

'In the main road there are many people, traffic, noise. By the canal it's quieter, calm, you notice things, people smile at you on the path. People don't smile on the main road'

(Participant 2, Informal chat, Women Centre).

The heritage environment of the canal with the towpath next to the water constitutes a different place of connection with everyday encounters. Walking the towpath as part of living in the place, situates users in an

in-between place of utility and calmness, and this reflects in behaviours. The watery environment is different (Sander and Zhao, 2015) and generates different reactions from the users.

‘You know, being on the canal with the boat and for the first time seeing the place you live in from the water and noticing green areas next to it, for some it is not a place of harm anymore, I don’t think about harming myself in it anymore, but a place of peace. And that’s important and all that’

(Participant 1, Informal conversation, GRACE group)

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/canalcraft-a-case-study/>).

During fieldwork, there were times when participants mentioned the canal in conversations, implying harm. This demonstrates that the watery environment of the canal, although a monument, is connected with local life, however, social issues faced by transient communities are not eliminated with regeneration. Place-making, with the alteration of the environment, has not resolved deeper feelings of alienation in locality, specifically linked with marginalisation relating to deprivation (Chang and Gunnell, 2018), as in the places the canal runs through in Kirkintilloch, and there is a limited positive engagement with the canal. Participating in meaningful engagement with the water through the boats can create awareness of the positive connections communities have with the waterway (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/participation/>).

‘Then in modern times, we are in Govan, we have the River Clyde, which is really famous for boats, and built some of the biggest boats in the world. So shipbuilding and boats is very much about old heritage and modern heritage’

(Interviewee 3, Interview extract, GalGael).

GalGael is in Govan, where the locality benefited from shipbuilding and communities depended on it for their livelihood. Utilising pride of place and its history and the ways in which it is pertinent to today’s sense of a place, could rebuild communities’ sense of ownership in the locality (GalGael, 2017) . During the interview with GalGael, I observed the formula of the cultural organisation using the livescape to build confidence in its members. The cultural organisation utilises the past in order to engage with the present through the synergy of tangible and intangible heritage –woodwork, historic boats, poetry, events (GalGael Charter, 2017). In this instance, the livescape reveals the positive and negative types of engagement.

‘This year, we put in 1,800 hours of volunteering to allow the boats to operate’

(AGM Report 2018, FCCS).

The FCCS offer volunteering opportunities through engagement with the boats. These opportunities are open to the local communities through membership, which is annually renewed. The organisation offers training on boat handling, assessment on certificates for navigation, hands-on experience in canal boat maintenance and engineering (see Appendix I). Without the continual use of the canal and routine maintenance and handling of the boats, the organisation could not survive. Operating the boats offering cruises resembles a full time job, and situates them somewhere between leisure and work. Throughout the society’s history, the tasks have been shared between the members with no downtime, as the boats need constant maintenance.

‘I would love to work on the canal. Imagine having a floating cafe, how popular it would be. And have local people to work on it’

(Fieldnotes, Scoping Study, Youth Club, Kirkintilloch).

Informal conversations uncover an imagination of how the place could be, transformed into a viable environment and imagined by local communities (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/scoping-study/#consultsessions>). Evidence suggests that place-making has created areas that communities could use, such as for cafes and restaurants on the canal. However, using the example of Speirs Wharf (Port Dundas canal side-residence development), the facilities are exclusive, leaving the local community out. There is an exception, a café established by a charity working with ex-offenders, however this café is not in a prime location next to the canal.

‘The [young people] are all sitting at the pontoon outside the boathouse. It is sunny and warm and they decided to have lunch there. We all sat there for ages eating lunch and chatting, watching the fish jump out of the water. Everybody seems happy and involved in conversation. This is nice. We will all need to go back to work soon’

(Fieldnotes, Boat building, Kirkintilloch).

Lunch breaks from the boat-building workshops were elevated to a valuable engagement with heritage. They became opportunities to stop and observe the environment around us. As participants engaged with building an object that floats, and learned about buoyancy, the water (canal) acquired a new interest. Now, everybody

noticed how the water behaved because they could imagine putting their boat in it. Life on the canal also became significant; anything that could interact with the object that they built was now important and noticeable – discussing the pontoon, water flow, situating the canal through conversation as part of the life in the town (Kirkintilloch) and its role in their lives.

2.2.1.7 The perceived significant/non-significant places and events in the changing heritage place present liminality. Liminality reflects uncertainty and thus change (transiency).

‘Well, when I was registered [in the FCCS] I asked him [her uncle] too and there’s a sort of description of life along the canal and the incidents that happened. The people that went swimming and the people that attacked boys like him for the lemonade bottle money, and it was a rough place to be brought up, but it’s all part of the my family’s personal canal association’

(FCCS member 1, Oral history, interview extract).

Participants in the study referred to occurrences that suggest the mundane elements of life around the canal and the river created a familiar and yet uncanny environment, where people felt at home and yet not exactly safe. A place acquires significance through the events that occur in it and they have importance (memories) for the people involved (Hall, 2012; Stevenson, 2013). Here the incidents are considered as associations with the canal, implying engagement.

‘The three women from MIN are at the front of the boat singing, dancing and taking selfies with their phones. A from the Women’s Centre is there with them recording the canal with her phone and laughing at the little party. There is a lot of laughter. M and her daughter are singing songs from home [Nigeria]’

(Fieldnotes, Boat handling, 3rd June). (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/boat-handling/#cruise1>)

During the cruises, as participants embarked the boat and experienced the canal from the point of view of the boat, which is a different kind of connection with the water, there were new understandings of the heritage environment being generated. Small events such as the singing and dancing that took place demonstrated awareness of the place: we sing because we are on water.

‘None of us ever really noticed the canal before. It was just there. Sometimes we saw boats coming through. But we didn’t know why, how and where they were going to’
(Participant 4, Boat building, Kirkintilloch).

During the boat-building workshops, the relationship between the participant groups and the canal and river was unpacked. This data example shows that although the canal is part of the life realm in Kirkintilloch, at the same time it appears to have no particular significance for the local communities, it is just there, without being understood as a heritage asset. The Millennium Link project (Appendix I) was part of a wider place-making strategy for the re-opening of the FCC to boat navigation (Vallerani and Visentin, 2018). Data suggested that transient communities who experienced the change of the canal’s regeneration did not have an active role in the changes in their own environment, and this is demonstrated through the lack of understanding about the place.

‘Our society campaigned since we started in 1980 for the reopening of the then derelict canals. Canal restoration has brought new vitality to many canal side communities with clear benefits spreading well beyond the canals themselves. What we experience now with the closure of the bridges is death by a thousand cuts. If boats can’t get through, the canal will deteriorate and close to navigation again’
(Chair talking to members, Fieldnotes, Training sessions, FCCS).

Direct engagement with the heritage environment and awareness of it also brings to the surface uncertainties about the changing place. The FCCS campaigned for projects like the Millennium Link. This is an exemplar of the heritage practice as a continuous process (Smith, 2006) as an act for preservation purposes (keeping the boats running on the canal), and awareness of disruptions (the failure of three bridges to open). Activism occurs because of awareness and empowerment (Portfolio, , <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/tensions/>), and opportunities are created for community voices to be heard (Kosmala and Beall, 2019). The tension that emerges here via the livescape is a sense of ownership for the heritage locality; that emerges through activation, in this case continuous activism and protest.

2.2.1.8 Everyday life and urban and inland waterways.

I consider the everyday life of the FCC and the river Clyde for the local transient communities who experience the changes of the place-making process as analogous to Lefebvre's (1991) lived space, and that is demonstrated in the following examples through familiarity with the local environment. However, the livescape reveals gaps in the familiar (public) character of the heritage place (Varna, 2016) and the understanding of the locality from a different perspective, as transient communities struggle to engage directly with the waterways. As the FCC and the river Clyde were once the principal providers of livelihoods of these now changed places, and are still perceived as such in living memory, so transient communities voice demands for the place to become viable for the local communities that need work and for an active environment for them to engage with the waterways again (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/scoping-study/>).

'These are the back routes where we pass'

(Participant 2 realising that the place where they usually walk through looks different from the water, Boat-handling cruise, 3rd June).

'The canal was built for commerce and for giving people a living. Why can't we bring that back and use the canal to create jobs for people?'

(Member 2, Women's Group, Informal conversation).

In this theme, the data exposed the lived space and the livescape is underpinned within the framework of alternative heritage (Merrill, 2014). Place-making changes generate engagement with the heritage environment, when at the same time this kind of engagement does not fall within the AHD understandings.

'Part of the plan was to create a viewing platform where the new towpath will be. Local residents rejected the plan for the platform because it was thought that it will encourage antisocial behaviour with the local youth'

(Officer, Hillhead Housing Association, Informal conversation).

The tension that emerges here through the livescape, is that familiarity with the heritage locality does not fit an AHD mode of directed engagement with heritage. One could argue that even perceived anti-social behaviours could still count as engagement, as they are acts in the everyday realm (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/scoping-study/>).

2.2.1.9 Vital waterways: does matter, matter? Places and objects affect the heritage process through activation. The activation of objects generates knowledge.

Objects, as the non-human elements in the heritage place and their political power and agency in affecting behaviours and understandings of engagement (Bennett, 2010; Neimanis, 2012), is the notion of this theme created by the collected data. During the workshops, the intangible and tangible heritage assets of the post-industrial waterways unlocked the hidden strength of materials and non-materiality in the formation of the landscape that is becoming through actions (Zhang and Han, 2022). This theme and its subthemes focus on the ways that materials and actions together create knowledge in the canal and the river, as not necessarily aligned with the AHD, eventually generating agency through engagement with the water.

According to the review of literature on the more-than-representational (Lorimer, 2005), the taskscape (Ingold, 2000), and the vitality of materials (Bennett, 2010), activation is the catalyst that transforms places and human and non-human elements in a locality, in the heritage process. In the same way as the taskscape emerges through the historicity of the tasks, the heritage livescape emerges through the activation of the same elements. (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/boat-building/>).

‘The boat builder is now helping the [young people] to put the boat on the water. The boathouse is ideal for trying the boat out for the first time. Only two of the [young people] can go in the boat. I am going in with them. Three of us are on the boat now. C is rowing as they had previous experience. The boat floats! Everybody is clapping and laughing. A lot of excitement. S is taking photographs’

(Fieldnotes, Boat building, Kirkintilloch).

The exemplar of being on the water and experiencing it first hand by actively engaging with the element, demonstrates the ability of the boat to create awareness of the environment, and an incentive and struggle to learn about it. It also demonstrates the tension of unfamiliarity with an important element of the waterway, the boat.

‘Crewmember now stands in the middle of the group and is pointing out of the window at the canal’s sections (we are at the crossway): “This part takes you to Bowling and into the Clyde.”

“Oh my God” (Participant 2 and 3 exclaimed),

“And this part goes to Edinburgh” (Crewmember).

“Oh my God!” (Participants exclaim).

Crewmember continues: “Yes, and up to Falkirk on the Wheel, and down to the Forth and then the sea”

(Fieldnotes, Boat handling, 3rd June)

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/boat-handling/#cruise1>)

The livescape is revealed here by the gaps in awareness of the physical environment and how the canal is positioned in the greater geographic area and in relation to known places. The canal’s physical features and their significance can be understood by being on the boat. However, the consideration of space in this study is limited to examining the corporeal notion of the livescape, as experience, thus this is beyond the scope of this study.

In this study, I consider the workshop as a collective of objects (apart from the people) that directly affect the engagement with heritage. Heritage assets within the AHD framework are considered as autonomous, at least by the visitors, and their vitality could be neglected as a viable mode of engagement.

‘I think [the workshop] is important for the organisation, certainly because the ships are prone to wear and tear. We’re getting a lot more people on the ship now and so we have to be aware that a lot of it has to be, you know, bits and pieces have to be replaced, cleaned, refurbished, more so nowadays than even in the days when I was up at Yorkhill. We have a higher footfall, so there’s a lot more wear and tear to it’
(Volunteer, The Tall Ship, Interview).

‘They are wonderful tools but [generally] quite dangerous. You need to work it [the plane] towards you. The way the body works, it’s actually hard to hurt yourself with them’

(Boat builder, Boat building, Kirkintilloch).

(see online Portfolio, Boat 3, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/boat-building/>)

During activation of the heritage place, I observed that using the body to activate the tools and understand them generates knowledge and also implies danger. Here, as with boat handling and living near the water,

familiarity with woodworking tools is considered as a not-so-safe mode of engagement. This is in contradiction with the AHD approach towards the preservation of traditional craft, such as boatbuilding – by the time of the study, boatbuilding had just come off the register of endangered traditional crafts (Heritage Crafts Association, 2021). Workshops are considered as places for expertise and not to be used by the public. Yet, the objects that the workshop contains contribute in the understanding of the heritage livescape.

‘Working on the boat is plain sailing’

(Participant 2 making puns, Boat building, Kirkintilloch).

Creating puns with the objects or the workshop generated engagement. Understanding the tools and finding working with them daunting is part of learning the heritage environment.

‘...and that project took four years. When I first started, the point that they were at was putting red copper rivets through some of the planks. And actually due to the number of copper rivets, it went on for about three months. So for the first three months or so that was all I did was put in copper rivets, into Starcross. But I continued to work on her alongside other boats’

(Interviewee 2, Interview extract, The Tall Ship).

Objects as small as rivets generate significant meaning in a working environment. In a workshop situation, the riveting of a boat is a slow but immersive job that promotes collaboration and conversation and the forming of relationships with others. The scales of tensions are apparent here, not as in DeLanda’s (2016) theory of assemblages but as the unveil of the nuances of the contestation.

‘A put the boat in the water and sat in. He said we should wait for 10 minutes for any leaks to appear. Then D tried to step in the boat. We heard a cracking sound and then a crack appeared at the bottom of the boat. I wanted to cry. We damaged it! There it was a metal bollard submerged and we couldn’t see it. ‘Well, now we know it’s there!’ D said. A and D look very upset. We wouldn’t be able to try the boat out before we fix it’

(Fieldnotes, Boat building, Maryhill).

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/tensions/#tension2>)

Experiencing accidents, loss, and damage during activities reinforces the sense of place and knowledge of place through activation.

2.2.1.10 Activation of objects generates ownership of place. Activation of objects exposes tensions in the altered heritage environment.

'The boatmaster now explains the tiller to the participant from the [women's group]. They listen to the instructions and gesture they understand by the way the boat responds to them moving the tiller. "Turn the rudder to the right now if you want to turn left." "I would need to set her up now, won't I?", the participant asks as the boat passed a curve'

(Fieldnotes, Boat-handling cruise, 3rd June).

The tiller on the boats is predominately the object that helps to direct the navigation and turn the boat to the desired direction. It helps in avoiding obstacles and keeping the boat in the desired direction. Also, it is an object that connects communities with the boats, in an activated environment, as it is an easy way to operate a canal boat, thus, more accessible to use. The same principle stands with the coracles. They are an easy boat-building project, which could quickly connect communities with the water.

'For instance, having been known for building traditional boats has been wonderful. But we're now about to build some coracles. This is a really traditional boat made from willow, you don't need to know any maths or any of that. So anybody, this is really about anybody, can do this. And I believe some indigenous communities that, totally, we'd built boats in the past and community would take part. The whole community will take part and the whole community take the boat to the water. And so this is what's going to be happening in April, we're going to be building two coracles, which will allow anybody of any ability to take part and then there's going to be an open water experience with that'

(Interviewee 1, Interview extract, GalGael).

'But they can't fill it to a metre because they lose their bridge. So when they did it in a hurry, it was done by non-canal users, engineers, and organisations. And if you look at the marina that we're standing on here, it was designed originally not by canal users but

regretfully by architects and engineering companies who regretfully did not have experience; a lovely marina, but if you look at some of the pontoons they don't fit and in fact a number of them had to be re-established'

(Member 3, FCCS, Oral History Interview extract)

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/locality/>)

Through activation one can understand the place, and tensions appear when there are gaps in understanding. In this exemplar, the changed heritage environment of the marina in Kirkintilloch alters participation, and the activation of the environment with the boats exposes the gaps. Without activation (lived space) there is no understanding; thus, the Marina was designed (abstract space) by people who do not use it (agencies operating in the area such as Scottish Canals and East Dunbartonshire Council).

2.2.1.11 Intangible heritage manifests in objects' ability to activate the place.

'So different to be on a boat, and to be rowing the boat and to see the Clyde that you maybe grew up around. I grew up in Govan so I grew up around the Clyde, but it's very different being in the Clyde on a boat. So yeah, it's a very, very important thing, is deeply empowering for people, and it's community again, because you can't survive in a boat unless you get known. And you're in the boat but doesn't go very fast if you don't know time together. So what's good about the boat is it builds community again, we have to tune into one another, to get our timing right. You can't cause havoc on a boat, because everybody is in danger. So we have to find ways to go along together. So yes, for all these reasons, boats are important'

(Interviewee 1, Interview extract, GalGael).

Being on the water with a boat requires discipline and skills, coordination, camaraderie, and co-operation. Rowing a boat on a river is a disciplined act. Activating the waterway with a boat creates a space for all to share and provides a sense of ownership and agency (Portfolio, , <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/tensions/>)

'Away from the troubles'

(Boat handling, Participant 4 when asked about the canal).

Being on a boat feels like being in a contained space.

'I see they have a desire to [...] do things for the ship. They're generally quite reliable when they appear, mostly every Wednesday. You know, still reliability. And they're determined to get the jobs around done for the purposes of helping the ship, basically' (Volunteer, The Tall Ship, Interview extract).

Going to work in a workshop for a historic ship, regularly, is a routine and an activation of the heritage environment. Fixing and repairing is part of having and preserving a heritage asset.

'I like the diversity of the work. So from one day to another, you're rarely doing the same thing, which keeps the job very interesting. And from a community engagement point of view, we take a lot of volunteers from fairly, you know, they can be from fairly disadvantaged backgrounds, [...] people that, for whatever reason, usually aren't at work, that can be for a number of reasons. And it can be very rewarding to build [...] skills and confidence and self-sufficiency and these people to sometimes return to work or to further education college and just see their confidence really grow' (Workshop leader, The Tall Ship, Interview extract).

Being routinely in a workshop and following tasks is a heritage process situated in the life realm. It is more than visiting a museum and engaging with objects in an AHD structural manner (Harrison, 2013). It is actively contributing to the development of the community and it is affecting the community through the engagement.

2.2.1.12 Activation induces familiarity in the community, working together as a group gives a sense of belonging.

'Well, I didn't know anything about the workshop. So I only knew The Tall Ship as there's a visitor attraction, as a child, but beyond that, didn't know anything' (Workshop leader, The Tall Ship, Interview extract).

Place-making processes such as the regeneration of the river Clyde waterfront affected the way cultural organisations on the river approach their heritage assets (Appendix I). The emphasis is on visitor attractions, which gives prominence to the place as somewhere to visit, and this is controlled and guided by the AHD since the official heritage organisations (The Tall Ship, the Riverside Museum) decide how engagement will occur in the place. On the other hand, for example, engagement with the workshop of The Tall Ship embeds a sense of freedom and creating a space of making, which transforms heritage activity into learning. On the canal, as with

The Tall Ship at the river Clyde, when communities have the opportunity to engage through activities and learn about boats, it affects familiarity and a sense of ownership to the place. It brings communities closer to the heritage assets and closer to the place.

'It's been a big thing for me. It actually changed my life because before I would basically stay in my bedroom, afraid that I'd be bullied or something. I don't know. Since CanalCraft, that's basically what brought me out in the adult world. I'm becoming 18 next year, and that made me get up early in the morning and get to the canal, build a boat and paint it. It got me into a new routine'

(Participant 1, LGBTQ+ group, Celebratory event, Kirkintilloch)

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/celebratory-events/#celeb2>)

'C arrived at the event and they look the same as before. They had expressed the desire, by the end of the boat-building workshops that they wanted to change. They started coming to the group [LGBTQ+] meetings too. They asked for their name to change on the certificate. They didn't get up to speak with the rest of the group, like they didn't want their face to show in any of the photos and videos. But they came to the event after they came out to me that day as we were picking lunch, and that's important'

(Informal discussion, Participant 1, Boat building, Kirkintilloch; talking about a participant coming out as trans during workshops).

Activation has a transformative power for people, objects, and the environment, as it generates common purpose. For the participants, boat building was the incentive to alter their life because those actions, relationships, conversations, and creations have the power to change.

'It was an enormous gush of wind that pushed us right to the side! How many cups of tea did you spill?' (Boatmaster).

'None' (Participants).

'So, it wasn't that bad!' (Boatmaster)

(Fieldnotes, Boat handling, 3rd June)

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/boat-handling/#cruise1>)

The experience of steering a boat and a gush of wind bumping it to the side is a shocking situation that puts pressure on one's sense of security. After that experience one understands the physical existence of the canal, not as a monument but as a real thing that contains individuals and also a community; understands the canal's dimensions and variabilities as one understands the importance of belonging and co-depending on one another. Thus, activation of the livescape reveals the symbiotic relations of all elements in the heritage environment, without hierarchies and hegemonic attitudes to agency (Neimanis, 2017).

2.3 Tensions

2.3.1 Familiarity of Place, Proximity and ease of access in the Post-industrial Waterways.

'What do I like about the workshop? Right [...] there's people in it, basically. There's a sense of camaraderie and [...] that's the main thing really. And we're doing something with a common purpose, really. You know, the centre point is the Ship, and we're all focused on helping to improve it'

(Volunteer, The Tall Ship, Interview extract)

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/participation/>)

There is lack of facilities for boat building around the FCC and the river Clyde. Existing workshops are not available or open to the public, and access to the water in the two waterways is restricted. Usually, access happens through groups and this is not a free option, as groups depend on memberships in order to operate. Therefore, there are multiple barriers to individuals or transient communities to access and engage with the water through boats.

'We had a meeting about the future of the boats. MIN have nowhere to store them and G wants to take the men on the canal with the boats but they are not a 'boat person'. So, for the group to keep using their boats they'd have to have the means to transport them to the canal and someone to organise this. There is nobody from the group that could take this on. Without a dedicated person to organise water-based activities, members could not use the boats'

(Fieldnotes, meeting at MIN, Maryhill)

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/participation/>)

‘There is nowhere to store the boats. The FCCS do not have facilities near the water to store a wooden boat safely. We need to find another canal organisation to take the boat so organisations could use them when they need them. Also, we need to organise events so people could use the boats. There is a lot of effort’

(Fieldnotes, Maryhill).

Slipways are features in the landscape that are important in order to be able to launch boats. They act as gateways and by letting boats in the water they make the waterways accessible. The lack of slipways presents barriers in participation (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/participation/>)

‘Here at the Stables [Kirkintilloch] is the only slipway available for boats around here and we [FCCS] manage it, so if people want to use it they have to contact us. There is a slipway in Firhill Basin in Maryhill and Scottish Canals have the keys. There is no other slipways on this section of the canal’

(Member 4, FCCS, Informal conversation).

‘There is a slipway at Kelvin Harbour. We [CMT] control it, so if people want to use it, they ring. I am not sure if people know that but when they ask at the [Riverside] museum they tell them to ring us. The river is tidal and dangerous and this is why access is controlled. You don’t want just anybody to get in it’

(Fieldnotes, CMT, informal conversation)

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/tensions/#tension4>)

Controlling a slipway is agency because it gives power to allow boating in the canal. Controlling the access and use of the water is AHD sustained as practice.

‘I learned that I needed to include costs for travelling expenses, childcare, and lunches. I had underestimated the workshops’ costs. I didn’t even think that these groups couldn’t get out of the house without support’

(Fieldnotes)

Frequently, transient local communities need to secure basic needs before they participate, and this is a barrier.

Figure 11: Tensions emerging from the activated and contested livescape.

On the left are elements of the livescape from which tensions emerge.

2.3.2 Knowledge and sense of ownership of public space in the Post-industrial Waterways.

‘People who work at the college during the spring break stop to ask about the workshop:

“This is fascinating! Building boats here!” I explained how difficult it was to find a place for the workshops around the canal’

(Fieldnotes; Boat building, Maryhill).

When attempting to activate the heritage livescape (lived space), tensions appear and it unfolds.

‘Despite the closure of the bridges, we managed to keep the boats going’

(FCCS AGM, Chairman’s speech)

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/participation/>)

‘We can’t afford to hold the lunch in the Town Hall as the Council asks to use their caterers. So we will have the lunch at St. Ninians. H from the women’s group will cook and will get help from someone else from the group. H is looking forward to being in charge of the lunch’

(Fieldnotes, Celebratory event, Kirkintilloch).

‘I love every aspect of this; the crew and everybody here, the lunch, the canal, it was opportune to go and join the crew there. I did the sailing myself! It was really fun. It’s a milestone. I’ve never done that. I’ve never gone that far in a boat before’

(Boat handling, 3rd June, Participant 1).

Being on a boat is a personally transformative experience as it provided new knowledge for being in a familiar environment.

‘On the whole, the public does not know about the workshop. Almost everybody that comes in here their first response is “I never knew this was here”’

(Workshop leader, The Tall Ship, Interview extract)

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/interviews/#interview1>)

Boat-building workshops where communities can meet are not visible because they are not part of the place-making process. They are not part of the heritage practice but they are viewed as a supporting element of the

heritage assets. This reveals tensions in engagement with heritage and public space, as workshops connect heritage practice with local communities (Niedderer and Townsend, 2014; Sennett, 2008).

‘There aren’t really any other opportunities for the public to come in, although that’s something that I’m looking to change because I’d like the public to be more engaged with the workshop. But finding how to do that without it being a problem from a risk point of view is quite difficult, but there’s something that ultimately I’d like to aim for’
(Interviewee 2, Interview extract, The Tall Ship,).

Activating generates understanding, as demonstrated in this data example, which implies that the ones who use the canal regularly are the ones who understand it and consequently the ones with the knowledge.

‘This is where [...] Scottish Canals ought to take a leaf out of the past and every time they decide to do something look at it and get advice from people who understand’
(Member 2, FCCS, Oral History Interview extract)
(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/canalcraft-a-case-study/#oralhistory>)

2.3.3 Practice of Heritage in the Activated Livescape.

The research, through studying and analysing these organisations and their projects, identified the gaps that still exist in engagement of the local communities with the urban waterways (Bell et al., 2017). The FCCS, CMT, and GalGael have encouraged engagement through embarkation, boat building, woodworking and engineering skills transmission, and familiarity with the water, which is a dominant feature of the place they live.

‘Well, that’s, right at the moment, a little bit up in the air, to continue to do the work that we’re doing through various different projects, but what those projects are, right now I couldn’t actually tell you, you know, that’s currently being discussed, some policy decisions to make, but we’ll be continuing to do the same work that we’re doing just now. I’m just not sure what the projects will be yet’
(Interviewee 2, Interview extract, The Tall Ship).

Cultural organisations rely on their boards of Trustees to be able to offer participation and this sometimes presents barriers.

2.3.4 Activism is a form of heritage practice (participation).

Craft is a form of practice, preservation of memory and activism (participation). Craft-based participation in the heritage landscape disrupts the routine of the everyday life that is imposed by hierarchies of knowledge.

‘I got involved with [The Tall Ship] because I felt it was completely different to anything I had experienced before. I was glad to come back to the Clyde, and as I was brought up in Yorkhill, it was my own territory, so to speak. And, I was familiar with the area that it was in. And, I’ve always been quite attracted to naval things and marine things, that sort of thing, anyway’

(Volunteer, The Tall Ship, interview extract).

This example demonstrates engagement with the river through working on the ship and in the workshop. For the ship to float, work need to be in place regularly. This process is heritage participation.

‘It’s hard to say because although I’m involved in the workshop, I’m involved in the electric part of it, so I don’t actually help. Well, if I must, I would help to do things regarding the ship or the other ships and the craft that they make. But I haven’t really got involved in making any of the craft or anything like that. I tend to look after the interactives on the ship and we take measurement from the ship as we did this morning actually’

(Volunteer, The Tall Ship, Interview extract).

‘Someone came to the event and told us that this is the first boat to be built here in 60 years! This used to be a boatbuilding yard before they built the boathouse’

(Participant 1, Informal conversation)

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/heritage/#kirkintilloch>)

Building a boat in the same location as a historic boatyard is preservation of memory. For this to happen a new workshop had to be set up.

Practicing heritage in a heritage asset, one has to abide by an AHD framework, as decisions are made by heritage professionals or the equivalent. This state of practice generates tensions when transient communities of the locality are involved, when it is shown that knowledge exists in the heritage environment, outside the

hierarchies of organisations. Decision making becomes problematic when knowledge doesn't get recognised officially.

'In terms of the decision making process, most of the decision making tends to be sort of more policy decisions, and that happens at the Trust level. So in that regard, not very much, but in terms of on the ground decisions in the workshop, how tasks should be performed, then they have as much input as any staff member. Though their opinion is always listened to'

(Workshop leader, The Tall Ship, Interview extract).

'Well, the organisation benefits massively, not just from the labour and experience that these people bring in, but it provides a really broad cross section of society, they're able to give ideas that we might not otherwise have'

(Interviewee, Interview extract, The Tall Ship,)

(Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/interviews/#interview1>)

2.4 Conclusion

The results above, supported by extracts from the collected data, compose the emergence of the livescape, as conceptualised through the tensions generated in the activated heritage urban waterways. The evidence was organised in themes and concepts that underpinned the study. The data supported that the post-industrial waterways are liminal spaces, and the theme of liminality was supported by the subthemes of the binary understandings of heritage in the post-industrial landscape in Glasgow, such as natural and cultural, tangible and intangible, and the monumentality of the place as opposed to experience.

Furthermore, as in-between spaces such as the waterways reveal tensions in the heritage environment through the heritage process of activation of the place (Smith, 2016), these tensions exist in-between the everyday and the familiar. The familiarity of the everyday life in this study is juxtaposed with transiency in the locality, another liminal state in the specific heritage environment, which leads to the liminality of the familiar and un-familiar sense of place. The gaps in familiarity, data revealed, are based on the changes realised by the place-making processes in the locality and the way the place is occupied. These changes, the evidence supported, create barriers in participation and engagement in and with the heritage assets of the area, and the

porosity of the barriers creates a sense of in-betweenness. Perceived marginalisation by the local community groups contributes to the blockage in participation and the sense of liminality, and this exclusion from engaging directly with the water of the heritage waterways whilst living near the water, reinforces the tension in the heritage environment.

Engaging with everyday life on and around the post-industrial canal and river, for work and leisure, induces tensions, as the places used to provide a livelihood for surrounding communities. The livescape as a model of engagement works on a granular scale, because this way, as also a model of inquiry, it is able to expose tensions within the locality otherwise hidden or overlooked. Place-making processes have prioritised the place as a tourist and visitors' destination, which create a liminal state. Considering a place or event (tangible/intangible heritage) significant or insignificant, also creates feelings of uncertainty, transiency, and tensions.

The non-human elements of craft (objects such as boats and tools) in the heritage waterways of focus have vitality, and the results of the study indicated that by way of craft (activation) they provide ownership of place and agency, as they affect the heritage practice and process. Sense of ownership of place is achieved by the generation of knowledge the objects induce when they are part of the activated heritage place, whilst barriers in activation of the place create tensions (broken down bridges obstructing navigation, lack of opportunities to have a boat on the canal on a regular basis). Results suggested that the liminal state of tangible and intangible heritage assets (Smith, 2006) in the post-industrial waterways is established by the activation of the place by objects. Thus, activation induces familiarity in the community, working together as a group gives a sense of belonging and the evidence provided demonstrated this in the Workshops, the Boats, the Cruises, and the Events.

Familiarity is connected with proximity and ease of access in the place of the post-industrial waterways. This was evident in the opportunity to be on the water in a boat, or have the ability and means to maintain or build boats. Although as a researcher and a boater/paddler myself, I had access to boating groups and equipment, the community groups I worked with could not easily access the canal and the river. Local community groups that are already empowered, the results suggested, are able to create opportunities to activate the heritage environment, through activism, a form of heritage participation, as they have access to boats and the skills and opportunities to handle them. This ability generates a sense of ownership of place and agency. As craft (in this

case boat building, maintenance, and handling) is a form of activism, it could also be heritage practice, as the preservation of memory (keeping the waterways active with boats and the canal open). At the same time, non-activation also induces tensions in the heritage place, demonstrated by the absence of opportunities to engage for transient, local communities. Evidence supported that activation possesses its own language, which is communicated in this instance by the use of tools, in workshop environments in the heritage landscape.

There is evidence through the data that activation is characterised as significant and non-significant as it is connected to the everyday life and the routines of living. When craft-based activation, such as boat building, takes place in the heritage place, which is managed within the framework of AHD, it disrupts the hierarchy of knowledge as it generates new knowledge for the transient local communities. The study's results demonstrated that craft-based activation promotes community building through groups and volunteering, and this introduces new tensions to the heritage livescape, which affect the heritage process.

Chapter V Conclusion and Recommendations

In this PhD research I examined local communities' participation with the post-industrial cultural landscape in Glasgow, focusing on heritage assets (Stevenson 2013). I have then identified possibilities for the same communities to participate in the heritage landscape and the potentialities for further participation within it.

In doing so, I firstly conceptualised transiency as a notion that affects the heritage environment of the waterways in Glasgow and the ways transiency has shaped participation and involvement with that environment. At this point, I answer the question that I discussed in Chapter I, of how community groups who experience transiency and appear marginalised and disadvantaged, engage with the heritage of the waterways. I have discussed the concept of transiency throughout the thesis and I have created a diagram (Figure 2, Chapter II Section 2.2) which highlights the main components that comprise the notion of transiency for this study. The reports both from the Scoping Study (Appendix II) conducted in the Forth and Clyde canal areas of Maryhill, Lambhill and Kirkintilloch, and from the Seminar organised at the Riverside Museum (Appendix II) on the river Clyde, suggested that local communities who experience the places of the canal and the river on an everyday basis experience transiency. Such transiency has been experienced over recent decades through the changing urban environment of the city of Glasgow, the altered landscape, with processes of place-making influencing the way urban spaces are occupied, and thus creating controlled environments with regulated purposes. This was illustrated through the analysis chapter (Chapter IV) by examples of interactions in the locality between human and non-human elements, the wild life, such as the interactions communities have when they walk on the towpath near the swans' nest and through being on water and understanding the locality by thinking from the water's perspective, as when navigating a boat and understanding how canal features and currents affect navigation and thus, why canals are built in a particular way. I used examples from the data to build the notion of transiency emerging in the contested heritage landscape. The place-making processes have particularly targeted and utilised heritage assets on both the river and the canal as I discussed in Chapter I when I presented Glasgow's waterways' tangible and intangible elements in the historic localities that form the post-industrial maritime and inland waterways heritage. Transiency, because of the altered and fluent landscape, contains unfamiliar approaches to landscape of the heritage locality, and this is indicated by the lack of opportunities to participate in activities that would

generate knowledge and thus familiarity by increasing interactions with the different elements that constitute public space within the locality.

In answering the second complementary question to the main research question, considering the monumentality of the post-industrial urban waterways, and to what extent transient communities perceive that heritage as large-scale monuments, I presented the tension of knowledge formation, as emerging through agency, with respect to access to participation in the heritage assets. Access to participation means direct engagement with heritage by empowerment and not dominated by initiatives dictated by authorised agencies, such as local authorities, the government and agencies that dominate knowledge ownership such as heritage institutions. Furthermore, during the Scoping Study I observed that marginalisation and mobilisation sometimes occurred due to forced migration, and also through multiple deprivation caused by difficulties in accessing resources, with both factors contributing to transiency and barriers to knowledge generation by local communities in the heritage locality. The primary results suggested that place-making processes affect local knowledge formation and familiarity with respect to the heritage environment, monumentality and scale of monuments, and this indicated (that familiarity with the heritage waterways through direct practice and involvement generates knowledge), and particularly knowledge relevant to the everyday life of the local communities, which induces sense of ownership and publicness (Varna and Tiesdell, 2013) in the urban heritage landscape. As place-making processes, informed and buttressed by AHD, with respect to the post-industrial river and canal in Glasgow, altered these environments, transient local communities developed gaps with respect to their practicing and presenting involvement with heritage in the place they occupied. In order to answer the research question, as to how communities participate with local heritage and how their participation informs the heritage process, and to ensure the research was as informed as possible, it was necessary to then engage with communities at an individual and small group level.

Secondly, and adding to the question on monumentality, as the river Clyde and the FCC are the main monumental scale heritage assets in this study, I examined involvement of transient local communities with cultural organisations, understood as additional heritage assets on these waterways. These organisations were The Tall Ship (Clyde Maritime Trust), GalGael, and the Forth and Clyde Canal Society. My own positionality as a researcher but also as a participant in auto-ethnographic research, were considered when answering the question. As well as being the researcher for this project I was also engaged in these

environments in two other respects: as a boater and paddler who used the two waterways regularly, and as a professional with working experience with the cultural organisations, as I mentioned in detail in Chapter III, section 2.3.3. I observed that the engagement that did occur reflected the heterogeneity of the locality. This means that different groups participated in different ways, including through cultural organisations, thus affecting the level of familiarity they gained with the heritage landscape. Broadly speaking, community groups that have limited access to opportunities for engagement (participating in activities involving water is expensive and demands access to resources) have limited understanding of the landscape as there will be perspectives that are not open to them. Thus, perception of the post-industrial waterways as a large-scale monument depends on availability of resources and capacity to engage with them.

The opportunity to design and organise a funded community heritage project, CanalCraft (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/canalcraft-film-and-publication/#review>), was discussed in detail in Chapters III and IV. This community heritage project became the platform from which I based the case study of this research. In the course of the case study and the three interviews, observations provided made through fieldwork, and ethnographic and auto-ethnographic data collected from meetings, events, exhibitions, oral history interviews, activities, celebratory events and conversation and dialogue became the main method of data collection. As the research was practice-led, this generated the creation of a body of work disseminated in a Portfolio of outcomes, drawing from these activities, films, events and images (Portfolio, <https://elenakoumpouzi.com/>).

The case study's results illustrate positive responses from the communities to a focus on alternative ways of accessing and engaging with the heritage environment. Boat handling and boat-building as activities, although exclusive, costly, and complex to organise, brought to light the notion that groups could try new methods of engagement with their environments and the scope of their possibilities.

Finally, the research illustrated that, by activating the heritage assets, local and transient communities can identify the tensions (Smith, 2006) in that space: transiency, knowledge, familiarity and sense of ownership, and through these tensions then gain better and more complete understandings, acquire further knowledge, and gain agency not only in the heritage process but also in the decision making process in their locality.

Given these findings the research succeeded in achieving its aim in developing a model for rethinking community heritage engagement. The model answers the other question as to what the possibilities for

participation are in the waterways and in what way those local communities can acquire knowledge of the heritage local environment through participation, in order to affect the heritage process. The livescape, as a model of engagement, in this study, developed from Lefebvre's lived space (1991) and aimed to make the lived space more visible. As lived space is derived from interactions in the realm of everyday life, employing the livescape as a model of engagement uncovers the tensions in the heritage landscape; such as hierarchical attitudes to knowledge, familiarity, transiency, and the sense of owning space. The livescape as a model of participation provides alternative practical access points and ways of engagement with local heritage assets. The livescape enables the development of better and more complete understandings of the heritage process through challenging the domination of hegemonic knowledge, and thus informs the heritage process, by revealing these tensions.

The activated livescape has the potential to be utilised as a model of engagement in other fields. As such it has significant potential and scope beyond its application, as here, with respect to the field of critical heritage studies. This will be discussed further later below.

The conceptualisation and development of the activated and contested heritage livescape is the main contribution of this research, and holds potential for critical application beyond the field in which it has been developed. The livescape is situated and operates within the communities in focus, uncovering gaps in participation and barriers to community heritage engagement, and for this study it comprises the heritage process. The contribution of this study is the activated and contested livescape and this contribution is manifested theoretically, methodologically and empirically.

Theoretically, the livescape is linked to the concept of the heritage landscape (Werner, 2008; Wylie, 2007), as experienced in everyday life through actions and interactions (Ingold, 2012; Harrison, 2013; Lorimer, 2005) in terms of the relationships between human, non-human elements and places (Neimanis, 2012; Bennett, 2010). These interactions and relationships of elements and places are affectual to the heritage locality (Thrift, 2004; Powell, 2010; Massumi, 2015; Müller, 2015; Tolia et al., 2017) and process (Smith 2016), and the livescape, operating in the transient urban landscape, uncovers the tensions that shape the place (the lived space).

The question that was posed in Chapter I, what are the heritage assets (the heritages) in the waterways and how do transient local communities view them, is related to the kind of value local communities apply to the locality. In the existing literature on the areas of this study there are concerns about how local communities

experience the heritage landscape, memory and the ways monumentality shape the urban place (Crinson, 2005; McDowell, 2008). In areas of the locality that were considered under-developed, local communities still engaged with the heritage asset, but may have done so in an unauthorised way, for example the testimony of local women in Maryhill of diving in the canal as kids. In the regenerated urban space, AHD (Smith, 2006) is dominant with respect to the ways in which experience is shaped, and in conceptions of the heritage landscape and of the heritage locality on a spatial level, through understanding and presenting these in terms of binary characterisations - of heritage as either natural or cultural (Lowenthal, 2005; Harrison et al., 2020), and either tangible or intangible (Smith and Akagawa, 2009; Lenzerini, 2011). In the activated livescape, these binary characterisations are challenged and notions of liminality (Massumi, 2015; Downey, 2016) are emphasised by the transient heritage place, which is shaped by place making processes and the changed urban environment, such as the notion of the cultural city (Hall, 2000; Landly, 2006) and the way the cultural city then shapes local communities' sense of familiarity with and ownership of the urban space (Bauman, 2001; Watson and Waterton, 2010). Developing from Lefebvre's notion of lived space (Lefebvre, 1968, 1991, Lefebvre et al., 1996) which is the space experienced in the everyday life realm (Hall, 2012; Courpasson, 2017), the livescape opens up the tensions contained within that space. Here, the last question can be answered if there is already participation in local heritage, perhaps not in the ways anticipated by AHD, and what way this affect the heritage process. Activation of the heritage landscape by its local communities (O'Kelly, 2009; Leeson, 2018) through the livescape reveals hegemonic attitudes towards the ways lived space is experienced under dominant conceptions of knowledge (Berg, 2004; Sennett, 2008), such as those of museums and heritage safeguarding institutions (Bagnall, 2007). The livescape, by activating the heritage environment of the everyday realm, challenges these modes of knowledge, through forming new understandings of heritage through notions of vitality and the conception of the insignificant in the heritage landscape (Hamdi, 2004; Bennett, 2010). Thus, with respect to the conceptualisation of the livescape, there are a range of areas of scholarly knowledge to which the concept could contribute, in particular the fields of critical heritage and urban geography with respect to the processual notion of heritage, knowledge hierarchies, and community participation in relation to sense of ownership and agency.

The livescape's scope as a model of engagement provides a theoretical framework that opens new possibilities in conceptualising the heritage landscape and the heritage process. These new forms of interaction and

conceptualisation mean that actions from everyday life, even if they are mundane, insignificant, or considered as waste, gain significance, as they serve the heritage process. The application of everyday forms of interaction, as significant events and activities for the heritage process, assigns validity to what were non-authorised knowledges and local wisdom, deriving also from non-anthropocentric knowledge creation (Neimanis, 2012). Thus, within the theoretical framework of the livescape, the processes of the landscape and the heritage process within it happen simultaneously, and the model challenges and develops further the platform of discourse on hegemonic views and exclusive and limiting attitudes to management and power sharing, decision-making and urban spatial injustice (Harvey, 2008, 2012) in the locality.

Methodologically, the study's main contribution is the application of the livescape in examining the dynamics of interactions and uncovering gaps in participation with the heritage landscape. Through a carefully planned case study, whose flexibility allowed for change, taking account of the transient parameters of the heritage locality, the activated livescape emerged through a set of activities, celebratory events, and an exhibition in the localities researched. This happened through the employment of alternative methods of activating the heritage livescape, which were actions and activities that the chosen sampling groups do not usually engage with due to transiency (Haeffner et al., 2017), as analysed in Chapter III. The activities, including boat handling and boat building, are usually exclusive to groups that can easily access resources that allow them to engage directly with the water element of the locality. The sampled groups, by activating the livescape, engaged directly with the canal and the river, in the localities that they occupy. The method examined the tensions that emerged through the development of these engagements in the regenerated urban heritage landscape. The activities I observed through the case study, as well as the information derived from the interviews with the cultural organisations operating in the heritage place, suggested that the heritage livescape is contested when activated, revealing the tensions as seen in the diagram about the Livescape (Figure 11, Chapter IV, Section 2.3.1). Thus, the livescape's contribution as a model of engagement is the uncovering of the tensions in the locality that affect engagement with heritage, and thus influencing the heritage process, by revealing a ever-becoming heritage locality.

The livescape contributes empirically through its provision of a model of engagement. For transient communities, who are marginalised because of their exclusion from the decision-making process, face barriers to direct engagement with, and do not have a voice regarding decision-making in, the contemporary urban

heritage landscape. Experiencing local heritage through their everyday life and through doing so activating the livescape creates new participation pathways, as driven by the tensions exposed. Thus, by activating the livescape, knowledge hierarchies and dynamics in place-making are exposed and challenged, as the knowledge exposed of those in the locality rather than hegemonic knowledge guides their engagement. Participation from the ground up becomes not an alternative but a normative way to guide the heritage process, as this process emerges from the realm of the everyday.

Disseminating the results of the case study through two celebratory events, returning reflections on what was gained from their engagements back to the community, reframes how heritage is understood and the key to doing so is challenging the hegemonic attitudes concerning the process of heritage. Bringing the results of the interactions back to the community empowers those communities by showing what can be achieved, understood and learned, and clearly asserts the fact that communities have hidden wisdom and knowledge that can guide them in both gaining familiarity with their locality and a sense of ownership and belonging.

During the case study, a body of work was built that aimed to uncover lived experience with respect to both the urban canal and the river. This body of work is presented in the online Portfolio as a form of exhibition, which consists of curated material created from the collected data during the case study, including the activities, actions, and interviews. The Portfolio consists of images and videos from the digital diaries during fieldwork (Nimkulrat, 2007); films made during the case study by the researcher as a participant; documentation from the celebratory events and the exhibitions; documentation from the activities and the outcomes of the workshops. The Portfolio is online, in accessible language and widely available: it illustrates the activated (participation) and contested (tensions) livescape. In this study I argue and illustrate that heritage is processual and is something to be accessible and lived (experienced).

The study's outputs are as follows: firstly, the preliminary stage of the research consisted of a Scoping Study and a Seminar. The Seminar aimed to scope the river's heritage environment and community participation options and opportunities as they existed at the time (see Appendix II). Secondly, the Portfolio, which consists of a body of work highlighting the objects, videos, film and images from the planned activities and events. Thirdly, the two Celebratory Events, one in Maryhill and the other in Kirkintilloch on the FCC, which disseminated the information from the case study. Fourthly, an Exhibition at the Kirkintilloch Heritage Centre, co-curated by participants from the groups in focus and local museum professionals. Fifthly, a series of papers

presented across three conferences (and a book chapter in an academic book on urban festivals (Koumpouzi et al., 2020; 2022). Finally, the two interviews one with a volunteer and the workshop manager from the CMT (the Tall Ship), and the other with a community officer from GalGael .

Through these main pathways, with this study, as I aimed to examine transient communities' participation and involvement within the post-industrial cultural landscape in Glasgow, focusing on heritage assets , I uncovered gaps in participation with the heritage environment of the post-industrial waterways for transient communities who do not have opportunities to engage directly with the waterways. The study, as I have discussed in the limitations section (see Chapter I, Section 5) could not solve the issues concerning complex relations with respect to the marginalised and disadvantaged communities who occupy the locality of the canal and the river and the liminal environment of the historic. I indicated these problematized relations by presenting the limited opportunities for these community groups to access the river and the canal with making and using their boats. Place-making has developed the waterways as leisure destinations by utilising their heritage and cultural values, however, transient communities face barriers in accessing such activities, creating tensions in the publicness of the heritage space. It is with respect to these issues that the other aim has been achieved, to identify possibilities for the same communities to activate this heritage landscape and aspects of further participation. The study contributes through the livescape which uncovers tensions in participation, and aids the development of a critical rethinking of community heritage engagement. The case study has left a legacy for the localities in which the activities took place providing new information to think through and, relatedly, new options to consider. East Dunbartonshire Council has already incorporated boat-building into their program for their yearly festival, the Canal Festival at Kirkintilloch, which takes place at a regenerated post-industrial location, in the same way that this occurred in the case study.

Concluding, the activated heritage livescape could have practical applications in situations where the heritage process is unclear and engagement problematic. The livescape could be applied to many different environments where interactions take place and hierarchies present barriers to engagement. The livescape as both a method of inquiry and a method of engagement with social space, uncovers the lived space, the environment that those in the locality experiences, and facilitates the re-thinking of engagement. The livescape operates at a *granular* level, working at a small scale in the locality, in order to delve deeply into the perceptions and realities of relationships and interactions with the life realm and heritage. I propose the

livescape as a method of unpacking tensions, that can then inform challenges to hierarchies and hegemonic attitudes towards participation in a social space, and in that way to guide the heritage process.

1. Recommendations for further research

The livescape as a model of engagement, as explained in the introduction, would benefit from being further explored by means of a wider and broader case study, or a number of case studies, that would take place in different contexts. The case study for this research was limited in scope, due to the limitations of the research time available as part of an academic PhD and the timescale for the community heritage project; thus, to one year. Further research could take place and collect data over a longer time period, which would provide the opportunity to engage in a considerably larger sample of both observations and material for analysis. An extended time period would benefit the research by allowing more time for engaging with a wider range of participants and doing so in greater depth and would also allow for less compromises to be made in terms of the activities that have to be fitted in within the research time period. Furthermore, the case study used boat building and handling as activation for the heritage environment, which at the time was an endangered traditional craft. Further research could explore different means and ways of livescape activation, perhaps through exploring other endangered craft activities and skills. Further research should take place across a wider range of different contexts and in different heritage environments. Such research would also benefit from a larger, more varied and diverse and sample of participants. There are potential benefits to be had through seeking out opportunities for engaging in research through online interaction either instead of or as complementary to physical interactions. This recommendation would help in addressing any situation comparable to the problems that have existed with groups meeting up in contexts of the COVID-19 pandemic and associated lockdowns and other restrictive measures and considerations (this includes, at any period of time given ongoing pandemic contexts with respect to those both at high risk and suffering from long covid. The plans for the presentation of the results and outcomes of this research were negatively impacted by COVID-19 pandemic restrictions, as what became the Portfolio was originally planned to be a live exhibition, on a venue near the FCC, and visitors of the exhibition would had been encouraged to get in of one of the boats and be on the water. However, other research projects, taking place over a similar time period, had to limit their data collection because groups could not meet in physical spaces. As such, there are a range of reasons for engaging in further research with respect to the activated livescape, through the use of

appropriate digital platforms. Meeting in such ways would greatly widen the range of people and groups that would find such engagements accessible.

2. Recommendations as to the application of research findings

Further recommendations, as based on the findings of this research, concern heritage management. As the activated livescape challenges hierarchical attitudes of knowledge, it could be applied to solve problems in how heritage management is delivered, by revealing tensions in the locality. Similar benefits, as flowing from the activated livescape's ability to uncover tensions, could be gained with respect to heritage preservation priorities. Such uses and benefits are possible because the livescape reframes the way heritage is understood by its disadvantaged communities and through doing so challenge the way in which preservation priorities are considered by AHD. Given this, further research could investigate the possibility of developing methods to apply the livescape with the intention of developing transient communities' involvement and agency in the heritage process and thus with respect to preservation strategies. Such considerations hold out the possibility for opening an inquiry platform and a more critical discourse as to the ways in which those living in localities view the importance of heritage as it emerges through the activated everyday life and become involved in making decisions about the development of the place they live in.

The findings of this study emerged from an exploration of the live heritage landscape of the urban post-industrial waterways in Glasgow (specifically the river Clyde and the Glasgow stretch of the Forth and Clyde Canal), and its interaction and involvement with the transient communities who live, work and socialise in their localities. These localities of the waterways are understood as the altered regenerated place, where culture and heritage have played an important role in their development and regeneration. The transiency experienced in the locality by marginalised and disadvantaged groups presented barriers to their engagement, as demonstrated by restricted participation and interrupted interactions with the heritage environment. This study revealed such gaps in understandings, by reframing how heritage is understood and practiced. By activating the heritage livescape, the study uncovered the misunderstandings of heritage practice in the everyday life, and facilitate the regaining of skills, and acquirement of knowledge and thus familiarity with the local heritage landscape. Familiarity and knowledge induce a sense of ownership with respect to an environment where transient communities have limited opportunities to bring about desired change. Activation of the livescape thus involves rethinking the way heritage is experienced and challenges practices

that alienate those in the locality creating barriers to their directly experiencing their own historic environment in the present.

Appendices

Appendix I

Oral History Interviews

The Forth and Clyde Canal Society has been involved in canal activism for the last 55 years. This is a story that has been recorded before (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UoAV0RtXnO8&t=6s>) but not in a structured oral history research. It has been 19 years after the Society achieved its goal for the Forth and Clyde Canal to re-open and there were still gaps in the recording of memories of the campaign and the role of members of the Society, specially the women.

These memories are from the members of the Society but also by people from local heritage organisations, volunteers, who worked along with them and supported them in their efforts. I conducted 15 interviews.

Thus, during the community heritage project CanalCraft, which was the platform upon which I built the case study for the research, the oral history activity was planned. Some of the interviews happened in the FCCS's offices and some in the interviewees homes. I overviewed the arrangements of the interviews, co-designed the questions with the interviewees and I was responsible for the safe storage of the interviews. I was also responsible for the collection of all extra documentation from the interviews, for example photos, video footage and archival material.

Content redacted due to unpublished work without informed consent for publication. Please contact the author for further information.

The final interviews have been deposited at the East Dunbartonshire archives, Scottish Canals Archive and the Society's new digital archive. They are also available for schools and other educational organisations and they are accompanied by instructions and equipment for groups to record their own experience of the canal, with the facility to embed these stories on the FCCS's website. This has created an on-going engagement between the canal and other communities, beyond the end of the CanalCraft project.

Questions for the Interviews

1. How and when did you first know / learn about the F & C Canal
2. How did you learn about the FCCS? Chance? Introduced by a friend?
3. What made you decide to join the Society?
4. What was the first major event that you participated in? Trip? Rally? Celebration? Anniversary?
Training night? Party? Public sailing? Doors Open Day? Clean-up? Walk?
5. What do you think is the most attractive thing about membership?
6. And the least?
7. What aspect of the Canal are you most interested in? Boats? Walking / cycling? Wildlife - Flowers & plants / animals / birds / people? History? Industry? Future use?
8. Which is your favorite stretch of the Canal and why?
9. What events stand out most in your memory and why?
10. What is the most amusing episode / event / happening you recall?
 1. exciting
 2. dangerous
 3. sad
 4. momentous
11. What did you take part in that made the most difference to regenerating the Canal?
12. What were the major issues confronting the Canal Society at its formation?
 - i. after 10 years
 - ii. after 20 years

iii. after 30 years

iv. now.

13. What relationship did the Canal Society have with *British Waterways (Board)*?
14. How did this evolve / improve / deteriorate over the years?
15. How do you see the situation since the formation of Scottish Canals?
16. Were there many women in the Society? What was their role?
17. Did you use to have specific uniform when at the canal?
18. Did you make friends?
19. Were you involved with the same jobs as the men?
20. Did you feel that the local community was involved with the campaign?
21. What would you change if you could go back?
22. What would you do extra if you could go back?
23. What do you think of the canal now?
24. How do you imagine the future of the Forth and Clyde Canal Society? The canal?

Appendix II

Scoping Study Report

The purpose of the scoping study was to observe, question and survey the heritage environment, the locality and the individuals involved directly and indirectly with the intangible and tangible heritage and location of the urban waterways of the river Clyde and the Forth and Clyde Canal. The scoping study developed from the aims and objectives of the research and it was designed based on ethnographic work, which included consultation sessions during groups' established activities, questionnaires and group observations, and a seminar. There are specific geographical areas where the research will focus on, based on criteria of ease of access to people for the consultation sessions and the seminar. This is particularly the case of the Tall Ship at the Riverside and GalGael Trust. Both organisations are accessible to me for interviews and supporting material. My previous work at the Tall Ship and my involvement to the first Clydebuilt festival as co-organiser has given me access to events' information (Clydebuilt Festival 2018) from within. The scoping study included preliminary consultations with community groups from the geographical area of focus: Maryhill, Milton, Lambhill and Kirkintilloch

1. Aims

1. Local community's understanding of heritage and the historic environment in the post industrial areas on the river Clyde and the Forth and Clyde canal.
2. Elements in understanding of locality affecting engagement with historic assets, such as unfamiliarity and spatial experience.
3. The duality of 'water' and 'boat' as active objects and possibilities of affecting city dwellers' behaviour.
4. Current place-making processes in Glasgow's waterfronts and waterways, and how they connect with the community's understanding of the locality.

5. Current heritage management (AHD) around Glasgow's urban and inland waterways, and how it correlates with the local community's understanding of the place.

2. Objectives

1. Survey the localities by observation, participation, work and collaborations. Devising possibilities for gathering information in the specific localities.
2. Design a methodology for a case study which will create synergies between the river and the canal waterways, based on notions of boating, being in and on water and the environment. Encourage local groups to discover their own possibilities of engagement by increasing local engagement.
3. Design a methodology to examine examples of cultural organisations whose core aim is the promotion of post-industrial heritage in Glasgow and greater Glasgow: The Tall Ship at Riverside, GalGael, and Forth and Clyde Canal Society.
4. Collect data via observations, qualitative public and internal surveys, archival material and promotional literature.

The scoping study focused on extracting general information from the community groups, individuals and heritage organisations as prospect participants in the case study. Initially, the purpose of the study addresses considerations on the case study design and of the understanding of the groups' dynamics.

3. Consultation Sessions

The consultation sessions of the scoping study included the groups of Maryhill Women's Centre, LoveMilton Youth Club, Lambhill Stables Women's Club and Youth Club, Hillhead Community Centre Youth Club and KLC Youth Group (Kirkintilloch) and they all took place during May 2018.

3.1 Method used on Consultation Sessions

The scoping study undertook semi- structured consultation sessions with community groups in areas around the canal that had potential for activities. The consultation sessions were based on discussions about heritage and where we find heritage; the canal and the uses of the canal as part of their neighbourhood; preferences on proposed activities and suggestions for new activities.

The consultations were based on questionnaires and flexible discussions, whereas the seminar was based on talks by cultural organisations on the river Clyde and the Forth and Clyde canal.

Questions for the questionnaires for the consultation sessions: On Heritage: a) What is heritage?, b) Where do we look for heritage?, c) Are you interested in visiting sites, places where heritage is kept/shown? On the canal and the river: a) In single words tell me what you think of the canal/river, b) Do you live near the canal/river? c) Do you think the canal should stay open?, d) Do you use the canal? How? e) Would you like to use the canal? How? The style of the consultations was based on brainstorming, discussions and postcard filling for ideas/suggestions.

3.1.1 Questionnaires

Open ended questions for meetings with organisations

The group meetings took place during the groups' scheduled meetings, they lasted for half an hour and they were informal. The questions were open ended and they aimed to provoke discussion on the subjects of heritage, the canal and canal use.

Participants were asked to write down their thoughts if they prefer, anonymously, in a notebook.

3.1.2 Questions

Please describe what you think when you hear the word heritage.

Where do you look for heritage?

Do you live near the canal?

Describe the canal

Do you use the canal? How?

Your ideas for using the canal

3.1.3 Suggested activities

Suggested activities and ideas for the case study were making a film; making Snap Chat stories to share activities; Making small boats and oars; learn about navigation and handling boats; Learn about bridges; Learn how to collect information and build an archive; Learn about the science of being on the water safely.

At the end of every session, I created a diary of the session with notes on the group (ages, numbers, gender, background) and notes on the professionals/managers that I worked with in order to access the groups.

Furthermore, professionals who work in the organisations, had an impact on conversations/answers (some staff are also participants) and their role was also considered. The answers of the questionnaires were counted, cards with responses were noted in groups (if there is recurrence in responses) and brainstorming maps were recorded and analysed for recurrences (in that case lists will be formed from the recurrences).

Results were compared between the different groups and analysed according to the aims of the case study.

For example, questions on 'heritage' provided information on how many prospect participants and their everyday environment know about the concept of heritage and the level of engagement that they find attractive/suitable/interesting.

3.2 Results

According to the results of the scoping study's consultation sessions, that included around 100 participants, the majority of participants had never heard the word heritage before; they didn't know where to look for heritage and they have never been in a museum (except when at school). During the scoping study, it was

revealed that local communities hold negative attitudes towards the canal (dirty, dangerous, crime area, people drowned).

The most popular suggested activities were: create digital stories; make a film; boat-building and oars and boat handling. Other popular ideas were: community picnics; events with music and running activities on the canal boats.

Activity	Lambhill Stables Youth club 20 kids	LoveMilton Youth Club 8 kids	Focus Group (Kirkintilloch) 11 kids	Kirkintilloch Youth Club 16 kids	Women's Centre Maryhill 12 Ladies	Lambhill Stables Women's Club 7 Ladies	Results
Make a Film	6	4	9	13	2	3	37
Make Snap Chat Stories	9	6	9	15	1	3	43
Make a small boat and oars	13	7	5	11	4	1	41
Learn about bridges and	5	3	5	6	3	1	23

make models							
Learn to handle canal boats	6	5	5	8	3	2	29
Learn how to make a resource	6	4	4	7	2	5	28
Learn about being safely on water and the science of it	6	4	8	9	4	3	34
None of the Activities				1	8	1	10
Votes cast	51	33	45	70	27	19	245

The scoping study indicated significant interest from young people and women's groups in the case study and we have secured commitment in principle to participate and support the study.

There is a particular appetite to learn more about the canal, and to mobilise community resources around a set of activities recording and celebrating community heritage. There is clear potential for capacity building, skills development, new knowledge production and heritage education with these groups if appropriate expertise as is proposed in this application can be made available to them.

We also referred to the 2013 consultation results from Trails and Tails, an HLF funded project, which took place in East Dunbartonshire and the report from Anchor and Sail, an HLF project that took place at the Riverside, in partnership with The Tall Ship at Riverside and GalGael. Both these projects identified significant interest in boatbuilding heritage, traditional skills and community heritage more generally.

These consultations indicated the level of understanding, interest and information that exists in the communities of focus of the study. The sessions will happen in an informal manner, during scheduled sessions in the organisations the research project will work with, for example during Women's club meetings, regular Meet ups, Youth Clubs' sessions. Consequently, numbers varied and they were not controlled, which was not an issue at this stage. The importance was to familiarise myself with the groups and vice versa.

4. Seminar

The seminar was organised by the Forth and Clyde Canal Society, CanalCraft project and the University of the West of Scotland and it took place at the boardroom of the Riverside Museum, on 3rd December 2018.

The seminar was planned to last half a day with a welcoming coffee at 10am and until 13.30pm. The participants were selected to represent heritage organisations, boat building and boating projects on the river Clyde and the Forth and Clyde canal.

4.1 Aim

The aim of the seminar was to do a preliminary examination on small craft and their societal value to communities adjacent to the waterways, and to scope actors who support craft aiming to re connect people with their urban waterways.

4.2 Participant organisations

Glasgow Life (Riverside Museum) Emily Malcolm

Clyde Maritime Trust – Andy Aire, Lachlan Cunningham

Glasgow Coastal Rowing Club – Gordon McCracken

Archipelago Folkschool – Ben Wylde

Glasgow Building preservation Trust – Andrew MacConnell

GalGael – Tam McGarvey

Auld kirk Museum – Peter McCormack

Scottish Waterways Trust/ Forth and Clyde Canal Society – Tommy Lawton

Lambhill Stables - Carol Primrose, Michael Nakonecznyj

4.3 Talks

Professor Katherine Kirk from the University of the West of Scotland and Women Engineers Society opened the seminar by introducing the importance of research in the field of engineering and technologies in relation to engagement with the post-industrial heritage of the river Clyde and its canal. Professor Kirk pointed out that interdisciplinary methods of research could be employed in achieving a sustainable future for the preservation of heritage of the waterways in cities.

Eleni Koumpouzi, Phd researcher in the University of the West of Scotland, introduced the theme of the seminar with a quick address.

Emily Malcom, curator of Maritime Transport at Glasgow Life, gave a short overview of Glasgow collections and small craft, in terms of exhibits at the Riverside Museum (the new Transport museum) and the collections available to the public at the Glasgow Resource Centre. She also mentioned the museum's extensive collection of models, of ships and smaller craft and the new catalogue that is being created which will be a resource to researchers of boat building and shipbuilding.

The Tall Ship's workshop was represented by two speakers, the Ship's manager Andy Aire and the Ship's Workshop manager Lachlan Cunningham. Andy Aire gave an overview of the boat-building history of the Clyde

Maritime Trust since its formation in the early 1990s. He explained that the Ship's workshop mainly assists to the preservation and the on going restoration of the Glenlee. However, as the Ship originally had boats on her, the workshop started restoring and making small craft to go on the Ship as part of the restoration. Work on one lifeboat started at the beginning of the new millennium and while the Glenlee was moored next to the Pumphouse. Those boat building projects started with volunteers and later on with the Heritage Lottery funded project Anchor and Sail, they attracted more people to work on the boats. Andy Aire pointed out that boat building projects run mainly with volunteers, do not progress and they are usually abandoned. He identified this challenge as an effect of the age group of the volunteers that the Tall Ship usually attracts, which is of an older generation, with frequently health issues and general vulnerability.

Andy Aire added that Anchor and Sail project produced a new boat for the Tall Ship, that was constructed from scratch and that the outcome of the project provided the organisation with 2 apprenticeships and 10 new volunteers of a younger age, that are still involved with the workshop.

Lachlan Cunningham, went on giving a brief description of the Captain's Gig's building process and the restoration of Lifeboat 2 and an overview of the new projects the workshop works on at the moment. He talked briefly about Starcrest, a leisure boat, built in Margate, that has been a long term, 60% restoration project of 4 years. When finished, the vessel will become a floating classroom on the river Clyde.

Both speakers emphasised the desire of the organisation to promote boat building and expand its potential and capacity with future boat building projects.

Gordon McCrchan from Glasgow Coastal Rowing Club gave a brief history of the club and its connection to the river. He talked about how the club started owning skiffs and competing to international competitions and regattas.

In 2016 they had an arrangement with GalGael to refurbish two of their skiffs and then moor them at Kelvin Harbour, from where they started regular rowing sessions.

Gordon emphasised how the club has tried to be an inclusive club, using social media to attract new members and people who are not used to the water. The club has 90 members, with rowers from the age of 20 to 70).

They have set up Evenbrite sessions as trials for newcomers to try being on a craft on the river and they try to encourage as many people as possible. They had 600 sessions on the water since they started.

The Clyde Maritime Trust has offered them a barge to have their meetings and storage space and they are hoping soon to develop training courses on boating skills and skippers' skills.

He also pointed out that the club wants to attract people who don't necessarily have a competitive nature and it promotes the improvement of mental health, physical health and general wellbeing by being on the water.

The club also promotes appreciation of the nautical, boatbuilding heritage of the river Clyde and during sessions skippers encourage members to identify the river's heritage from the perspective of the water. Gordon said that the skiffs have helped them to do other things on the river, other than rowing.

He also mentioned that one of the club's great concerns is the litter on the river Clyde and that they organise many sessions of litter picking and they have collaborated with Environmental agencies on this task.

They have also taken part in the Glasgow International Art Festival and they have collaborated with artists creating music videos.

The last two years they have been involved in a new project with the Clyde Maritime Trust, where members restore in the Tall Ship's workshop the skiffs and they learn basic boat building skills.

Concluding, he pointed out that there is a clear demand from people to get on the water and get access to the river, which is the major feature of the city. The rowing club believes that they could contribute in encouraging people to start enjoying the Clyde.

Archipelago Folkschool's Director Ben Wylde came up to talk briefly about his new venture, the Folkschool, which aims to reconnect people with craft.

Ben believes that boat building, crafts such as blacksmithing, pottery, woodworking, textile and community involvement should work all together and have an artistic approach, combining STEM education with traditional craft and encouraging creativity through the principal of making and slow processes.

Ben then moved on to talk about his experience in designing, fundraising and running Anchor and Sail, a Heritage Lottery funded project and a collaboration between Clyde Maritime Trust and GalGael Trust. The project lasted for three and half years, with a budget of £500,000. It addressed the lack of boat building traditional skills in Glasgow, where in the whole of Scotland there were 30 commercial boat builders, all of an older age and male. The project addressed the issues of a small industry and focused on young people and women and people from disadvantaged backgrounds. The project brought together two different

organisations, created to women apprentices, 131 volunteers and four boats, two of those were built from scratch. The project also opened the workshop of the tall Ship to people, through events and specifically with Clydebuilt festival.

Ben gave a brief evaluation of the project stating that it's a lot to be done in building small vessels, as big long projects do not turn the teaching value that they had expected. He gave the example of Starcrest, an almost 5 year project, where to keep momentum going, it is a huge task. He added that apprenticeships need to be paid the living wage and that projects like these need to take into consideration the benefits system in relation to volunteering for disadvantaged people who would want to get involved and benefit long term from a project like this.

He also mentioned the challenges with finding and keeping volunteers interested and committed in the project and also his working experience as leader having planned more things that could be accomplished, so a smaller program would had been more effective.

One of the most valuable lessons that came out of the project is the realisation that boat building projects need to have an end purpose because there is no need for boats to be built and not being used. Anything that floats, it's great, not just ambitious projects.

Ben talked about the creation of Clydebuilt festival. Last year, in 2018, 7000 people attended and the event hosts one of the biggest boat race in the UK, Castle to Crane that runs from Dunbarton Castle to Finnieston Crane. He described the festival as a heritage project of its own, that tried to offer things to people who do not think traditional boats are for them.

More people got in the water because of the Anchor and Sail, boat building still going on on the river, wood working careers for the volunteers, when people's lives turned around. The legacies of the project have gone far beyond the project.

Next speaker, Andrew McConnell from the Glasgow Building Preservation Trust, spoke about the West Boathouse project. He first gave a historic overview of the river as a boating river and the 200 year life of rowing clubs.

He made a particular mention to the weir, as an industrial architectural marvel and intervention and its impact to the river Clyde. The weir made the upper river available to boaters, stabilised the river banks and improved aesthetics to the river. He pointed out that rowing clubs were developed because of the weir.

The West boathouse, built in 1905, survived two tenants. Andrew spoke of old skills on traditional boats having been lost. Glasgow since then has changed, and there are no tenement housing any more. The West boathouse supported many athletes who became famous.

Rowing is a technical sport, with narrow equipment so it is not for everyone and not very accessible. His team realised that they could be using the river in other ways and not just about getting medals. The team recognised that the river could serve a wider audience.

The benefits from being on the river were great: improving well being, training, meeting people, learning new things and exercise. They realised that the river could become a bridge rather than a barrier and for this reason many clubs have become together to join the project.

Andrew went on to talk about the dysfunctional relationship with the river. People in Glasgow identify where they are from, for example Clydebuilt, heavy industry, the East End and at the same time they identify the river as being a boundary between ganglands, dangerous, unsafe and a not clean territory. So the river has provided so many barriers to people enjoying and engaging with the river.

The new project was set up to serve more than two clubs and to attract new users.

It encourages people to see the river in a different way, so they have developed a new interpretation plan and try to identify and promote what is special with the heritage of the river Clyde.

In a nutshell, the West boathouse project aims to use the building as a gateway to use the river more.

A 360° video was created in order to help people visualise how it feels to enjoy the river from a boat.

During Doors Open Day, clubs tried to encourage people to be on the

water and they succeeded. They have to address not only physical but also social barriers to get people to get to the water.

The project is looking to start conversations on the waterside and for this reason they will organise schools regatta days to try and get people in boats and enjoy the experience for being there.

‘On a sunny day in Glasgow, where else would you be?’

Next speaker was Tam McGarvey from GalGael Trust.

Tam gave a historic overview of how GalGael first started and the aims of the project.

The story of GalGael started in 1990s when members started protesting for social space in the city (for example near the woodland for the M77). Members grew food, had camps organised and started discussions and protests about ecological and social matters.

The organisation decided to start working towards what they were for and not what they were against, when one member had the idea to start building boats! They moved to Govan where they were a lot of unemployment. They got a boat in a shape of a Viking ship and then a second one when they started to engage people with rowing. It was a Viking ship on the Clyde!

Many people who engaged came from difficult backgrounds and rowing the boat gave them a sense of purpose and changed preconceptions about engaging with heritage as they found the activity very rewarding and something to be proud of.

The ship was a contrast with the modern architecture. It was a shock to see a historic ship on the river but ‘it felt like connecting us with the ancestors.’

Tam pointed out that in GalGael soon realised that they were interested in people’s reality and that in order to get into reality they had to be physically immersed into it.

They started taking part in events with the boat, which was like a piece of sculpture and also putting up events, reconnecting coastal communities and reclaiming natural and cultural heritage. They wanted to give people a sense of place, to overcome the negativity about the past and what has happened to them with unemployment and deprivation. Sense of place and narratives. A sense of purpose to overcome negative feelings about those people (unemployed).

They started dressing up and encouraging people to feel proud for their ancestors, get a sense of place and be proud of where they live.

At the workshop, they tried to create a ‘home’ where people could connect with something positive and get a sense of purpose. Connect with something positive and give people positive values and a sense of purpose.

The sea became a highway and not a barrier any more.

The boat started having problems because the emphasis was on people more, so they brought her out of the water and tried to fix it.

The guys built things together again. Castle to Crane race involvement. Connecting people with heritage and the story of the river. Connected people with the river. They learn about navigating the boat and they feel proud of it.

Getting people back on the water, connecting them with their history.

The boat was involved in the last Outlaw King movie.

There was a coffee break where people networked. After the break the second session was focused on the canal and the heritage organisations on the canal and how they engage with the local communities.

The Forth and Clyde Canal was represented by Peter McCormack, Collections manager of the Auld Kirk museum, who talked briefly about Kirkintilloch and the canal; the new Heritage centre called 'Made in Kirkintilloch', at the refurbished Town Hall and the displays about the canal in the Auld Kirk museum. He concentrated on the new displays of interactive touchscreens, in the new heritage centre and specifically the ones about the boatyards in Kirkintilloch, that have utilised oral history interviews from the 1970s where characters from the boatbuilding yards give their testimony of the life on the canal shores building boats. Visitors could explore the story of the yards and the boat building heritage of the place.

Peter explained how the 'Made in Kirkintilloch' centre works as a first stop shop for the heritage of the local industries, where visitors could be directed back to the Auld Kirk museum to explore the exhibits there and for further research they could visit the Local History Studies and the Archives at the William Patrick Library.

Next speaker Tommy Lawton, who is a long term volunteer with the Scottish Waterways Trust and the Forth and Clyde Canal Society, gave a detailed talk with photographic material on the construction and the kind of boats that sailed on the canal. He connected the story of the canal with the boats that serve in it and the boats, like the puffers, that helped in the communities development in the West of Scotland.

Last speakers were from Lambhill Stables, Carol Primrose and Michael Nakonecznyj, who both focused on the story of Lambhill Stables and the heritage work that takes place in the community hub in promoting the rich

heritage of the area, which includes the Antonine wall, the coal and ironworks industry. They talked about the last heritage project Canal, Coal and Cottages and the challenges the project faced in engaging the local community with the local history. Carol focused on the ongoing heritage work and collaboration with the Open Museum, their display cabinets and live history events during the hub's open days.

Michael talked about the small boat the hub owns and the different work he undertakes on the boat. Michael and his team have worked extensively in clearing the stretch of the canal near the stables from litter and the litter picking has been very successful in enabling navigation. He explained the dangers in navigation because of the quantity and the quality of the litter in the canal, he spoke about local community's attitude towards the inland waterway and how he would like to see people caring about the preservation of this monument. Local negative perceptions of the canal was a common acknowledgement in all the talks from the canal representatives.

Michael described also the enthusiasm and high demand for the boat tours he leads during events on the canal. His boat has capacity for up to 12 people and during the boat tours he helps visitors visualising the lost industry, houses and local life in the area. Michael comes from a mining local family and himself worked in the local industry, such as the local brick factory, thus he has a good living memory of the period he describes. He has also developed a file with information, newspaper cuts, personal photos and texts that he has collected over the years, so people who embark on his boat could see evidence from the stories he describes on the tour.

4.4 Results

At the end of the seminar, there were plenty of questions from the audience, predominately about boat building projects and facilities suitable for these kind of activities. Participants agreed that there are not suitable facilities for small boat building projects on the Forth and Clyde canal and the only one at the moment on the Clyde are the Tall Ship workshop and GalGael, which now works on a part time basis.

There were questions about the future of navigation on the Forth and Clyde canal, due to the recent failure of the bridges in Twechar and Bonnybridge. The Chair of the Forth and Clyde canal society was there to answer the questions, however he could only speculate as Scottish Canals are responsible for the maintenance of the bridges.

Finally, there was a suggestion for more discussions based on the future of the waterways, the craft that travels on them, public engagement and more projects that connect people with the urban waterways. There was a general demand for the formation of a forum with the common aim to advocate for small craft and the preservation of the traditional skills that are in danger to be lost.

After the end of the seminar, the groups that took part agreed that the conversation that started with this seminar needs to continue and that the formation of an umbrella body is perhaps necessary to guide the discussions in the right direction.

4.5 Evaluation

There were 32 attendees and 12 completed questionnaires

Comments

- Too long
- More variety
- Connect people of waterways
- More collaboration
- Invite tourists-leisure

- Groups unknown
- Time too short
- Not enough time for speakers

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